

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

College of Engineering and Technology

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019-2020

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

III SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SMA31	Numerical Techniques and Integral Transforms	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV32	Strength of Materials	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV33	Fluid Mechanics	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV34	Principles of Civil Engineering Surveying & Advanced Techniques	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL35	Earth Science Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL36	Civil Engineering Material Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL37	Civil Engineering Surveying Practice Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL38	ESEP-Civil Engineering ISAP(Information Search Analysis and Presentation) Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
9	19SQA39	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 1 (ESEP 1)	2	0	0	50	-	50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 1							
		Total Credit						800	26

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

IV SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SMA41	Probability Theory and Statistical Methods	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV42	Structural Analysis - I	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV43	Hydraulics & Hydraulic Machines	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV44	Concrete Technology & Building Materials	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL45	Fluid Mechanics Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL46	Building Construction Practice Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL47	Concrete Technology Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL48	ESEP-Basic Soil Mechanics Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
9	19SQA49	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 2 (ESEP 2)	2	0	0	50	50	50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 2			2				
		Co-Curricular Activities/ Sports (ESEP)							-
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING
V SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV51	Structural Analysis -II	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV52	Design of RCC Structural Elements	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV53X	Core Elective-1	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV54X	Optional /Soft Elective	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL55	Construction Technology Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL56	Civil CAD Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL57	Geotechnical Engineering Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL58	ESEP -MOOC			2	50		50	02
9	19SQA59	Part–A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 3 (ESEP 3)	2	0	0	50		50	02
		Part–B: International Certification Course on Current Trends							
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 1		Optional / Soft Elective	
19SCV531	Geo -Technical Engineering	19SCV541	Management & Entrepreneurship
19SCV532	Substructure Construction Technology	19SCV542	Principles of Architecture
19SCV533	Advanced Soil Mechanics	19SCV543	Principles of Construction Management
19SCV534	Soil Structure Interaction	19SCV544	Principles of Town Planning & Urban Development
19SCV535	Soil & Rock Mechanics	19SCV545	Ground Improvement Techniques

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

VI SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV61	Advanced Design of RC Structures	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV62	Environmental Engineering	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV63X	Core Elective-2	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SXX64X	Open Elective - 1	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL65	Civil Design Laboratory (Design of C-D Structures)	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL66	Highway Material Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL67	Extensive Survey Project	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCV68	ESEP-Mini Project				50	-	50	
9	19SQA69	Part-A:Employability Enhancement Skill Programme 4(ESEP 4)	2	0	0	50		50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends	0	0	0		-	-	
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 2		Open Elective - 1	
19SCV631	Transportation Engineering	19SCV641	Occupation Health & Safety in Construction Industry
19SCV632	Highway Geometric Design	19SCV642	Air Pollution & Control
19SCV633	Urban Transport Planning	19SCS641	Web 2.0
19SCV634	Reinforced Earth Structures	19SCS642	Designing Embedded Systems
		19SEC641	Cryptography and Network Security
		19SEC642	Python Application Programming
		19SME641	Total Quality Management
		19SME642	Micro – Electromechanical Systems.

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

VII SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV71	Design & Drawing of Steel Structures	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV72X	Core Elective-3	3			50	50	100	03
3	19SCV73X	Core Elective-4	3			50	50	100	03
4	19SCV74X	Open Elective-2	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV75	Quantity Surveying & Valuation	4		2	50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL76	Environmental Engineering & Water Quality Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL77	Project Phase I	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCV78	ESEP-Computer Aided Design Structural Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
8	19SQA79	ESEP-Employability Skill Enhancement Programme -Patent Filing & IPR	2	0	0	50	-	50	02
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 3		Core Elective - 4		Open Elective - 2	
19SCV721	Quantity Analysis & Quality Control	19SCV731	Pre-Stressed Concrete	19SCV741	Research Methodology
19SCV722	Solid Waste Management	19SCV732	Design of Bridges	19SCV742	Environmental Impact Assessment
19SCV723	Sustainable Development in Civil Engineering	19SCV733	Finite Element Analysis	19SCV743	Introduction to Smart City
19SCV724	Water Resources Management	19SCV734	Structural Dynamics	19SCS741	Social and Web Analytics
19SCV725	Industrial Waste Water Treatment	19SCV735	Earthquake Resistant Structures	19SCS742	Information Security
19SCV726	Contract Procedures & Arbitration	19SCV736	Matrix Method of Structural Analysis	19SCS743	Software Testing
19SCV727	Building Services, Facilities, Planning & Management	19SCV737	Theory of Plates & Shells	19SEC741	Artificial Intelligence
19SCV728	Rural Water Supply and Drainage System	19SCV738	Advanced Concrete Technology	19SEC742	Virtual Reality
19SCV729	Pavement Design	19SCV739	Advanced Foundation Design	19SEC743	Telecommunication Management
				19SME741	Nano Technology
				19SME742	Operations Management
				19SME743	Quality Control

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

VIII SEMESTER

SL. No	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV81	Seminar				100		100	02
2	19SCVL82	Internship				50	50	100	03
3	19SCVL83	Project (with patent Application)				100	100	200	13
		Total Marks/Credit						400	18

Srinivas University
College of Engineering and Technology
Mukka, Mangaluru – 574 146

III & IV SEMESTER

B.TECH
CIVIL ENGINEERING

SCHEME & SYLLABUS
2019

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
College of Engineering and Technology

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2019-2020

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

III SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SMA31	Numerical Techniques and Integral Transforms	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV32	Strength of Materials	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV33	Fluid Mechanics	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV34	Principles of Civil Engineering Surveying & Advanced Techniques	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL35	Earth Science Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL36	Civil Engineering Material Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL37	Civil Engineering Surveying Practice Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL38	ESEP-Civil Engineering ISAP(Information Search Analysis and Presentation) Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
9	19SQA39	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 1 (ESEP 1)	2	0	0	50	-	50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 1							
		Total Credit						800	26

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

IV SEMESTER

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			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SMA41	Probability Theory and Statistical Methods	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV42	Structural Analysis - I	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV43	Hydraulics & Hydraulic Machines	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV44	Concrete Technology & Building Materials	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL45	Fluid Mechanics Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL46	Building Construction Practice Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL47	Concrete Technology Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL48	Basic Soil Mechanics Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
9	19SQA49	Part-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 1 (ESEP 1)				50	-	50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends - 1							
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

III Semester B.Tech
NUMERICAL TECHNIQUES AND INTEGRAL TRANSFORMS

Sub Code : 19SMA31
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of this course is to introduce students to the mostly used analytical and numerical methods in the different engineering fields by making them to learn Fourier series, Fourier transforms, z-transforms and numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

On completion of this course, students are able to

- CO1:** Know the use of periodic signals and Fourier series to analyze circuits and system communications.
- CO2:** Explain the general linear system theory for continuous-time signals and digital signal processing using the Fourier Transform
- CO3:** Employ appropriate numerical methods to solve algebraic and transcendental equations
- CO4:** Solve first order ordinary differential equations arising in flow problems Using single step and multistep numerical methods.
- CO5:** Apply the concept of Z- transform to engineering problems

MODULE –I

Fourier series: Periodic functions, Dirichlet's condition, Fourier series of periodic functions with period 2π and with arbitrary period $2c$. Half range Fourier series, practical harmonic analysis-Illustrative examples from engineering field. **10 Hours**

MODULE-II

Fourier Transform: Infinite Fourier transforms, Fourier sine and cosine transforms. Inverse Fourier transforms, Problems.

Numerical Methods: Numerical solution of algebraic and transcendental equations by Regula- Falsi Method and Newton-Raphson method. **10 Hours**

MODULE- III

Numerical solution of ordinary differential equations: Numerical solution of simultaneous first order ordinary differential equation and first degree, Taylor's series method, Modified Euler's method, Rungekutta method of fourth order. Milne's and Adam's bashforth predictor and creditor method. **10 Hours**

MODULE IV

Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations:

Numerical solution of simultaneous differential equation, Numerical solution of second order ordinary differential equations, Runge-Kutta method and Milne's method. (No derivations of formulae). **10 Hours**

MODULE V

Difference equations and Z-transforms: Difference equations, basic definition, z-transform-definition, standard z-transforms, damping and shifting rules, initial value and final value theorems (without proof) and problems. Inverse z-transform-problems and applications to solve difference equations. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS

PART A: **TEN** multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

01 Mark x 10 Question = **10 Marks**

PART B: **TWO** question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Mark x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed.(Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.
3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: "Engineering Mathematics", Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C.Ray Wylie, Louis C.Barrett : "Advanced Engineering Mathematics", 6th Edition, 2. McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S.S.Sastry: "Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis", 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B.V.Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal, "A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics", Laxmi Publications. Latest edition, 2014.
5. Chandrika Prasad and Reena Garg "Advanced Engineerig mathematics, Latest edition, Khanna Publishing, 2018.

**III Semester B.Tech
STRENGTH OF MATERIALS**

Sub Code : 19SCV32
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To provide basic concepts and principles of Strength of Materials
- To give an ability to calculate stresses and deformation of objects under external loadings.
- To give an ability to apply the knowledge of strength of materials on engineering applications and design problems.
- To apply the fundamentals of simple stresses and strains, and to facilitate the concept of bending and its theoretical analysis.
- To apply fundamental concepts related to deformation, moment of inertia, load carrying capacity, shear forces, bending moments, column and struts, Principal Stresses and Strains.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the behavior of materials under loading.
CO2: Students will be able to understand and calculate the different types of stresses.
CO3: Students will be able to understand and calculate the shear force and bending moment for beams with different types of loadings
CO4: Students will be able to calculate the Deflection of beams for different loading conditions
CO5: Students will be able to discuss the Torsional effects on materials.

MODULE 1

Simple Stresses and Strains

Introduction, Definition and concept and of stress and strain. Hooke's law, Stress-Strain diagrams for ferrous and non-ferrous materials, factor of safety, Elongation of tapering bars of circular and rectangular cross sections, Elongation due to self-weight. Saint Venant's principle, Compound bars, Temperature stresses, Compound section subjected to temperature stresses, state of simple shear, Elastic constants and their relationship. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving.

MODULE 2

Compound Stresses: Introduction, state of stress at a point, General two dimensional stress system, Principal stresses and principal planes. Mohr's circle of stresses

Thin and Thick Cylinders: Introduction, Thin cylinders subjected to internal pressure; Hoop stresses, Longitudinal stress and change in volume. Thick cylinders subjected to both internal and external pressure; Lamé's equation, radial and hoop stress distribution. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving.

MODULE 3

Shear Force and Bending Moment in Beams: Introduction to types of beams, supports and loadings. Definition of bending moment and shear force, Sign conventions, relationship between load intensity, bending moment and shear force. Shear force and bending moment diagrams for statically determinate beams subjected to Point load, Uniformly distributed loads, Uniformly varying loads, Couple and their combinations. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving.

MODULE 4

Bending and Shear Stresses in Beams: Introduction, pure bending theory, Assumptions, derivation of bending equation, modulus of rupture, section modulus, flexural rigidity. Expression for transverse shear stress in beams, Bending and shear stress distribution diagrams for circular, rectangular, 'I', and 'T' sections. Shear center (only concept). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving.

MODULE 5

Torsion in Circular Shaft: Introduction, pure torsion, Assumptions, derivation of torsion equation for circular shafts, torsional rigidity and polar modulus Power transmitted by a shaft, combined bending and torsion. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS

PART A: **TEN** multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

01 Mark x 10 Question = **10 Marks**

PART B: **TWO** question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Mark x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Strength of Materials**, Subramanyam, Oxford University Press, Edition 2008
2. **Mechanics of Materials**, B.C Punmia Ashok Jain, Arun Jain, Lakshmi Publications, New Delhi.
3. **Strength of Materials**, Basavarajaiah and Mahadevappa Universities Press (2009).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Strength of Materials**, Singer Harper and Row Publications.
2. **Elements of Strength of Materials**, Timoshenko and Young Affiliated East-West Press.
3. **Mechanics of Materials**, James M. Gere (5th Edition), Thomson Learning

Web links:

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112107146/>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105105108/>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112107147/18>
<http://www.nptelvideos.in/2012/11/strength-of-materials-prof.html>

**III Semester B.Tech
FLUID MECHANICS**

Sub Code : 19SCV33
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To make the student to understand fluid properties and fluid pressure measurements.
- Teach Hydro-Kinematics
- Introduce Boundary Layer Theory
- Analyze flow through pipes, Turbines and Pumps
- To solve the problems related to water hammer effects

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to understand the fluid characteristics and their application in different material in manufacturing industries.
- CO2:** Students will be able to measure the pressures at various conditions with different types of pressure devices
- CO3:** Students will be able to calculate the discharge of fluids
- CO4:** Students will be able to calculate the forces acting on submerged bodies
- CO5:** Students will able to apply their knowledge in addressing the problems in closed pipes.

MODULE 1

Fluids & Their Properties: Concept of fluid, Systems of units. Properties of fluid; Mass density, Specific weight, Specific gravity, Specific volume, Viscosity, Cohesion, Adhesion, Surface tension & Capillarity. Fluid as a continuum, Newton's law of viscosity (theory & problems). Capillary rise in a vertical tube and between two plane surfaces (theory & problems). vapor pressure of liquid, compressibility and bulk modulus, capillarity, surface tension, pressure inside a water droplet, pressure inside a soap bubble and liquid jet. Numerical problems. Fluid Pressure and Its Measurements: Definition of pressure, Pressure at a point, Pascal's law, Variation of pressure with depth. Types of pressure. Measurement of pressure using simple, differential & inclined manometers (Theory & problems). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 2

Hydrostatic Forces on Surfaces : Definition, Total pressure, centre of pressure, total pressure on horizontal, vertical and inclined plane surface, total pressure on curved surfaces, water pressure on gravity dams, Lock gates. Numerical Problems.

Fundamentals of fluid flow (Kinematics): Introduction, Methods of describing fluid motion. Velocity and Total acceleration of a fluid particle. Types of fluid flow, Description of flow pattern. Basic principles of fluid flow, three-dimensional continuity equation in Cartesian coordinate system.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 3

Fluid Dynamics: Introduction. Forces acting on fluid in motion. Euler's equation of motion along a streamline and Bernoulli's equation. Assumptions and limitations of Bernoulli's equation. Problems on applications of Bernoulli's equation (with and without losses). Numerical Problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 4

Orifice and Mouthpiece: Introduction, classification, flow through orifice, hydraulic coefficients, Mouthpiece, Numerical problems.

Notches and Weirs: Introduction. Classification, discharge over rectangular, triangular, trapezoidal notches, Cippoletti notch, broad crested weirs. Numerical problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 5

Flow through Pipes: Introduction. Major and minor losses in pipe flow. Darcy-Weisbach equation for head loss due to friction in a pipe. Pipes in series, pipes in parallel, equivalent pipe-problems. Minor losses in pipe flow, equation for head loss due to sudden expansion. Numerical problems. Hydraulic gradient line, energy gradient line. Pipe Networks. Water hammers in pipes, Problems.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each.

01 Mark x 10 Question = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE fullquestions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module.

08 Mark x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **'A TextBook of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'**- R.K.Rajput, S.Chand& Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. **'Principles of Fluid Mechanics and Fluid Machines'**- N.Narayana Pillai, UniversitiesPress (India), Hyderabad, 2009 Edition.
3. **'Fluid Mechanics and Turbomachines'**- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **'Fundamentals of Fluid Mechanics'** – Bruce R. Munson,DonaldF.Young, Theodore H. Okiishi, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. **'Introduction To Fluid Mechanics'** – Edward j. Shaughnessy,jr; Ira m. Katz;; James p Schaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition.
3. **'Text Book Of Fluid Mechanics&Hydraulic Machines'**- R.K.Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
4. **'Fluid Mechanics'** – Streeter, Wylie, Bedford New Delhi, 2008(Ed).

III Semester B.Tech
PRINCIPLES OF CIVIL ENGINEERING SURVEYING & ADVANCED
TECHNIQUES

Sub Code :	19SCV34	IA Marks	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	4	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To understand the basic concepts of engineering survey and use of different survey equipments.
- To understand the concepts of compass and theodolite survey.
- To understand the basic concepts of total station and their importance.
- To survey and prepare the land survey maps using total station.
- To make the students able to do base line measurement and handle Auto Level & Total Station in the field for various surveying works.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the standard maps developed by survey of India and competent authorities.
- CO2:** Students will be able to understand and use of higher end survey instruments like total stations to achieve more accuracy.
- CO3:** Students will be able to employ appropriate survey methods in land survey, construction projects and to generate data & maps.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand Basics of vertical representation, contouring, mapping fundamentals.
- CO5:** Students will be able to understand Establishment of control point, details of Digital Land Surveying.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Civil Engineering Surveying :

Definition of Surveying, Objectives and importance of Surveying. Classification of Surveys. Principles of Surveying. Units of measurements, Surveying measurements and errors, types of errors, precision and accuracy. Classification of maps, map scale, conventional symbols, topographic maps, map layout, Survey of India Map numbering systems.

Measurement of Horizontal Distances: Measuring tape and types. Measurement using tapes, Taping on level ground and sloping ground. Errors and corrections in tape measurements, ranging of lines, direct and indirect methods of ranging, Electronic distance measurement, basic principle. Booking of tape survey work, Field book, entries, Conventional symbols, Obstacles in tape survey, Numerical problems **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

Measurement of Directions and Angles:

Compass survey: Basic definitions; meridians, bearings, magnetic and True bearings. Prismatic and surveyor's compasses, temporary adjustments, declination. Quadrantal bearings, whole circle bearings, local attraction and related problems

Traversing:

Traverse Survey and Computations: Latitudes and departures, rectangular coordinates, Traverse adjustments, Bowditch rule and transit rule, Numerical Problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

Leveling:

Basic terms and definitions, Methods of leveling, Dumpy level, auto level, digital and laser levels. Curvature and refraction corrections. Booking and reduction of levels. Differential leveling, profile leveling, fly leveling, check leveling, reciprocal leveling. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

Curve Surveying

Curves – Necessity – Types, Simple curves, Elements, Designation of curves, Setting out simple curves by linear methods (numerical problems on offsets from long chord & chord produced method), Setting out curves by Rankine's deflection angle method (numerical problems). Compound curves, Elements, Design of compound curves, Setting out of compound curves (numerical problems). Reverse curve between two parallel straights (numerical problems on Equal radius and unequal radius). Transition curves Characteristics, numerical problems on Length of Transition curve, Vertical curves – Types – (theory).

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

Introduction to Total Station: Parts of total station, accessories of total station, handling and setting of total station, measurement of distance using total station, measurement of vertical and horizontal angles using total station, various errors in total station. Error propagation and surveying specification. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

01 Mark x 10 Question = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Mark x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS

1. **'Surveying'** Vol-1 – B.C. Punmia ,Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. **Surveying and Levelling** – R Subramanian. Oxford University Press (2007)
3. **Text Book of Surveying** – C. Venkataramiah. Universities Press.(2009 Reprint)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
2. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
3. **Surveying Vol. I**, S.K. Duggal, Tata McGraw Hill - Publishing Co. Ltd., New Delhi.
Survey of India Publication on map.

III Semester B.Tech EARTH SCIENCE LABORATORY

Sub Code : 19SCVL35

Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T

Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 3

Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To Understand the Earth System
- To know about the material present i.e. minerals and rocks
- Understand Structural deformations and impacts
- Know subsurface exploration methods
- Know groundwater availability and domains; recharge

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to understand different geological structures and their impact on civil engineering structures.
- CO2:** Students will be able to decide the suitable site selection for civil engineering structures
- CO3:** Students will be able to know different geological hazards and its mitigation
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand the different method of geological exploration
- CO5:** Students will able to identify the different rocks and minerals based on their properties and also use of different rock and mineral.

Experiments

1. Identification of minerals as mentioned in theory, their properties, uses and manufacturing of construction materials.
2. Identification of rocks as mentioned in theory, their engineering properties and uses in construction and decorative purposes.
3. Dip and Strike problems: Determination of dip and strike direction in Civil Engineering projects (Railway lines, tunnels, dams, reservoirs) –graphical or any other method.
4. Bore hole problems: Determination of subsurface behavior of rocks, their attitude related to foundation, tunnels, reservoirs and mining. Triangular and Square land, assuming ground is horizontal.
5. Calculation of Vertical, True thickness and width of the outcrops.
6. Interpretation of Electrical resistivity curves to find out subsurface information such as thickness of soil, weathered zone, depth of hard rock and saturated zone
7. Interpretation of Toposheets and geological maps related to Civil Engineering projects.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. M P Billings, Structural Geology , CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi
2. B.S.SatyanarayanaSwamy , Engineering Geology Laboratory Manual , DhanpatRai Sons, New Delhi.
3. L R A Narayan, Remote sensing and its applications, University Press.
4. P.K.MUKERJEE, Text book of Geology , World Press Pvt. Ltd., Kolkatta
5. John I Platt and John Challinor, Simple Geological Structures, Thomas Murthy & Co, London.

III Semester B.Tech
CIVIL ENGINEERING MATERIAL TESTING LABORATORY

Sub Code :	19SCVL36	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Helps for selecting and verifying materials and to evaluate material quality, performance and many other applications.
- To give a broad understanding of common materials related to Civil engineering with an emphasis on the fundamentals of structures.
- Ability to use techniques skill and modern engineering tools necessary for engineering.
- Understanding of professional and ethical responsibility in the areas of material testing
- Ability to communicate effectively the mechanical properties of materials.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Students will be able to understand the basic knowledge of material in finding the strength in tension compression, shear and torsion.

CO2: Students will be able to identify, formulate and solve structural elements subjected to flexure

CO3: Students will be able to analyse the bending stress on different types of sections

CO4: Students will be able to understand the properties of different construction materials.

CO5: Students will able to understand the impact loading on materials.

Experiments

1. Tension test on Mild steel and HYSD bars.
2. Compression test of Mild Steel, Cast iron and Wood.
3. Torsion test on Mild Steel circular sections
4. Shear Test on Mild steel.
5. Impact test on Mild Steel (Charpy&Izod)
6. Hardness tests on ferrous and non-ferrous metals – Brinell's and Rockwell.
7. Tests on Fine aggregates –Specific gravity and Sieve analysis
8. Tests on Coarse aggregates –Specific gravity and Sieve analysis
- 9 Compression Test on wood.

NOTE: All tests to be carried out as per relevant BIS Codes

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Testing of Engineering Materials, Davis, Troxell and Hawk, International Student Edition – McGraw Hill Book Co. New Delhi.
2. Mechanical Testing of Materials”, Fenner, George Newnes Ltd. London.
3. “Experimental Strength of Materials”, Holes K A, English Universities Press Ltd. London.
4. “Testing of Metallic Materials”, Suryanarayana A K, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
5. Relevant IS Codes
6. “Material Testing Laboratory Manual”, Kukreja C B- Kishore K. Ravi Chawla Standard Publishers & Distributors 1996.
7. Concrete Manual, M.L.Gambhir –DhanpatRai& Sons- New Delhi.

III Semester B.Tech
CIVIL ENGINEERING SURVEYING PRACTICE LABORATORY

Sub Code :	19SCVL37	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Apply the basic principles of engineering surveying and measurements
- Follow effectively field procedures required for a professional surveyor
- Use techniques, skills and conventional surveying instruments necessary for engineering Practice.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to apply the concept of accuracy of the line diagram.
- CO2:** Students will be able to know the concept of elevation between two points using fly leveling technique
- CO3:** Students will be able to understand the measurement of vertical angles using Theodolite.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand Curve setting by different methods.
- CO5:** Students will able to understand the surveying by using total station.

Experiments

1. To check the accuracy of the line diagram of the building plan by 3,4,5 method.
2. To determine difference in elevation between two points using fly leveling technique & to conduct fly back leveling. Booking of levels using both HI and Rise & Fall methods using Dumpy Level.
3. Study of theodolite -measurement of vertical angles, Measurement of horizontal angles by method of repetition.
4. Measurement of horizontal angles by method of reiteration.
5. Trigonometric Leveling - Heights and distance problem (Two Exercises)
6. Heights and distance using Principles of tachometric surveying (Two Exercises)
7. Curve setting – different methods. (Two Exercises)
8. Determine of area using total station.
9. Traversing using total station
10. Contouring using total station
11. Determination of remote height using total station
12. Stake out using total station.
13. Distance, gradient, diff, height between two inaccessible points using total station.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol.-1, B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. 'Plane Surveying' Vol-1-A.M. Chandra, Newage International ® Ltd.
3. 'Plane Surveying' – ALAK, S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS :

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
2. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
3. Surveying Vol. I, S.K. Duggal

**ESEP-CIVIL ENGINEERING ISAP (INFORMATION SEARCH
ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION)
LABORATORY**

Sub Code :	19SCVL38	IA Marks	25
Hrs/ Week :	1L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	25

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To teach information search.
2. To develop the general knowledge among the students in their core branch.
3. To make the students aware of the latest developments in their branch.
4. To teach the Oral and PPT presentation techniques.
5. To overcome the stage fear of the students.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to expose to national and international journals.
- CO2:** Students will understand the latest technological developments in their branch.
- CO3:** Students will be learning the slide preparation, presentation skills.
- CO4:** Students will be learning the soft skills required for the seminars.
- CO5:** Students will develop public speaking.

Experiments

1. Information search and topic selection for the presentation.
2. Synthesizing the information.
3. Oral presentation
4. Preparation of the Report
5. PPT preparation
6. PPT presentation
7. Analyzing the Presentation

Scheme of Examination:

- ONE question from major experiments: 13 marks
ONE question from minor experiments: 12 marks
Total: 25 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. "Communication Skills" by Sanjay Kumar and PushpaLata
2. "How to Win Friends and Influence People" by Dale Carnegie
3. "The Quick And Easy Way To Effective Speaking" by Dale Carnegie
4. "Communication Skills for Professionals" by Konar N.

PART – A: EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME - 1

Subject Code	19SQA39	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations with Domain specific training in respective branches.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Learn domain specific knowledge
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART – A

Number System –

- a. Number system
- b. Power cycle
- c. Remainder cycle
- d. Factors, Multiples
- e. HCF and LCM
- f. Trailing Zeroes,

Data arrangements and Blood relations –

- a. Linear Arrangement
- b. Circular Arrangement
- c. Multi-dimensional Arrangement
- d. Blood Relation
- e. Option elimination method in Blood Relation

Time and work –

- a. Work with different efficiencies
- b. Alternate day work
- c. Pipes and cisterns
- d. Work equivalence
- e. Division of wages
- f. Leaving the work concept with example

Coding & decoding, Number Series, Analogy, Odd man out –

- a. Different types of Problems on Coding and Decoding
- b. Mixed Series, alternate Series, mixed operational series
- c. Analogy
- d. Odd Man Out

Reading comprehension –

- a. Types and Tackling Strategies.
- b. Understanding meaning of a text.
- c. Drawing Connections.
- d. Summarizing and Synthesizing.
- e. Building Vocabulary.
- f. Speed Reading Strategies.

Antonyms & Synonyms –

- a. Understanding root words.
- b. Prefixes.
- c. Suffixes.
- d. Vocabulary building.
- e. Putting words into context.
- f. Word Power made easy.
- g. Elimination.

PART – B

Strength of Materials

Engineering Mechanics

Building Materials

Fluid Mechanics

Survey

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books:

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART – B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	19SQA39	IA Marks	-
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Have exposure on the latest development
- CO2: Acquire new skills
- CO3: Become Industry ready
- CO4: Have more confidence
- CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method

- Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

PROBABILITY THEORY AND STATISTICAL METHODS

Subject Code	19SMA41	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L) + 1(T)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

Course Objectives:

The purpose of this course is to make students well conversant with the following

1. Numerical methods to solve ordinary differential equations
2. complex analysis techniques applied to diverse situation in engineering
3. sampling theory will reflect the range of variation in the population
4. Laplace transforms
5. numerical methods for ordinary differential equations

Course Outcomes: On completion of this course, students are able to:

- CO1: Understand the analyticity, potential fields, residues and poles of complex potentials in field theory and electromagnetic theory.
- CO2: Use Laplace transforms to determine general or complete solutions to linear ODE.
- CO3: Initial-value problems, Runge-Kutta methods, large systems and method of lines; error estimation and control; continuous output; event location.
- CO4: One-step and multi-step methods for non-stiff systems of ordinary differential Equations.
- CO5: Draw the validity of the hypothesis proposed for the given sampling distribution in accepting or rejecting the hypothesis.

Module 1

Analytic function : Review of a function of a complex variable, limits, continuity and differentiability. Analytic functions-Cauchy-Riemann equations in Cartesian and polar forms (no proof). Properties and construction of analytic functions by Milne Thomson method. Singularities, Poles, Residues, Cauchy's residue theorem (statement only).

Teaching Pedagogy:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 2

Probability: Introduction. Sample space and events. Axioms of probability. Addition and multiplication theorems. Conditional probability – illustrative examples. **Probability Distributions:** Random variables (discrete and continuous), probability mass/density functions. Binomial distribution, Poisson distribution. Exponential and normal distributions, problems

Teaching Pedagogy:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 3

Complex integration. Line integral of a complex function-Cauchy's theorem and Cauchy's integral formula and problem. Residue theorem. Bilinear transformations- problem. **Joint probability distribution:** Joint Probability distribution for two discrete random variables, expectation, covariance, correlation coefficient

Teaching Pedagogy:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 4

Statistical Methods: Review of measures of central tendency and dispersion. Correlation-Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation-problems. Regression analysis- lines of regression (without proof) –problems

Curve Fitting: Curve fitting by the method of least squares- fitting of the curves of the form, $y = ax + b$, $y = ax^2 + bx + c$ and $y = ae^{bx}$

Teaching Pedagogy:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

Module 5

Sampling Theory: Sampling, Sampling distributions, standard error, test of hypothesis for means and proportions, confidence limits for means, student's t-distribution, Chi-square distribution as a test of goodness of fit

Teaching Pedagogy:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the Concept

10 Hours

INTERNAL MARKS DISTRIBUTIONS:

3 internals are conducted for 20 marks each and it will be reduced to 30 marks. Continuous evaluation = 15 marks.

Seminars, quiz, Surprise test, assignments. Attendance carries 5 marks.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. 1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions. Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. E. Kreyszig: Advanced Engineering Mathematics, John Wiley & Sons, 10th Ed. (Reprint), 2017.
2. B.S. Grewal: Higher Engineering Mathematics, Khanna Publishers, 44th Ed., 2017.
3. Srimanta Pal & Subobh C Bhunia: "Engineering Mathematics", Oxford University Press, 3rd Reprint, 2016.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. C.Ray Wylie, Louis C.Barrett : "Advanced Engineering Mathematics", 6th Edition, McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1995.
2. S.S.Sastry: "Introductory Methods of Numerical Analysis", 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010
3. B.V.Ramana: "Higher Engineering Mathematics" 11th Edition, Tata McGraw-Hill, 2010.
4. N.P.Bali and Manish Goyal, "A Text Book of Engineering Mathematics", 2016

**IV Semester B.Tech
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS –I**

Subject Code	19SCV42	IA Marks	: 50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. The objective of this subject is to expose students to various methods of structural analysis
2. Apply the knowledge of Civil Engineering in calculating slope and deflection of beams.
3. Identify, formulate and solve engineering problems
4. Analyze structural systems and interpret data
5. Engage in lifelong learning with the advances in Structural Engineering.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to discuss & classify statically determinate & indeterminate structures.
- CO2:** Students will be able to identify, analyse and solve problems on deflection of beams
- CO3:** Students will be able to apply the concept of Strain Energy and also Redundant Frames.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand the importance of horizontal thrust in maintaining of Two – Three hinged parabolic arches for external loading & analyze the same.
- CO5:** Students will able to discuss & classify the concepts of influence lines for deciding the critical forces & sections while analyzing and designing.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION AND ANALYSIS OF PLANE TRUSSES

Structural forms, Conditions of equilibrium, Compatibility conditions, Degree of freedom, Linear and nonlinear analysis, Static and Kinematic Indeterminacies of structural systems, Types of Trusses, Assumptions in analysis, Analysis of determinate Trusses by method of Joints and method of Sections. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

MODULE 2

DEFLECTION OF BEAMS

Definition of Slope, Deflection and Curvature, Sign conventions, Derivation of moment-curvature equation. Double Integration method and Macaulay's method: Slope and deflection for standard loading cases and for determinate prismatic beams subjected to point loads, UDL, UVL and Couple. **Moment Area Method:** Application of Moment Area Method for determinate prismatic beams, Beams of varying section.

Conjugate Beam Method: Real beam and conjugate beam, conjugate beam theorems, Application of conjugate beam method of determinate beams. **12 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

MODULE 3

ENERGY PRINCIPLES AND ENERGY THEOREMS

Principle of virtual displacements, Principle of virtual forces, Strain energy and complimentary energy, Strain energy due to Axial force, Bending, Shear and Torsion, Deflection of determinate beams and trusses using total strain energy, Deflection at the point of application of single load, Castigliano’s theorems and its application to estimate the deflections of trusses, bent frames, Special applications-Dummy unit load method. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

MODULE 4

ARCHES AND CABLE STRUCTURES

Three hinged parabolic arches with supports at the same and different levels. Determination of normal thrust, radial shear and bending moment. Analysis of cables under point loads and UDL. Length of cables for supports at same and at different levels. **08 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

MODULE 5

INFLUENCE LINES AND MOVING LOADS

Concepts of influence lines-ILD for reactions, SF and BM for determinate beams-ILD for axial forces in determinate trusses-Reactions, BM and SF in determinate beams using rolling loads concepts. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK**

each. 1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Theory of Structures**, Pandit and Guptha, Vol. – I, Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.
2. **Basic Structural Analysis** Reddy C. S., Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.
3. **Strength of Materials and theory of structures** Vol I & II, B.C. Purnia, R.K., Jain Laxmi Publication New Delhi

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Elementary Structural Analysis**, Norris and Wilbur, International Student Edition. McGraw Hill Book Co: New York
2. **Structural Analysis**, 4th SI Edition by Amit Prasanth&AslamKassimali, Thomson Learning.
3. **Analysis of Structures**, Thandava Murthy, Oxford University Press.

Web links: <https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105107122/>, <https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105107122/8>,
<http://structural->, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mbfayL-AX4&ab_channel=APSED,
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=17wzQJ8IkdE&a_b_channel=CIVILERA,
[https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ON81MWhcq5o &ab_channel=sadiqzubair](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ON81MWhcq5o&ab_channel=sadiqzubair)

**IV Semester B.Tech
HYDRAULICS & HYDRAULIC MACHINES**

Subject Code :	19SCV43	IA Marks :	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Principles of dimensional analysis to design hydraulic models and design of various models
2. Design the open channels of various cross sections including the design of economical sections
3. Energy concepts of fluid in open channel, energy dissipation, water surface profiles at different conditions
4. The working principles of the hydraulic machines for the given data and analyzing performance of turbines for various design data.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to apply the concept of model and dimensional analysis using fundamental concepts.
- CO2:** Students will be able to apply specific energy concepts in the analysis of open channel flow
- CO3:** Students will be able to utilize the concepts uniform and critical flow through open channels
- CO4:** Students will be able to demonstrate gradually varied flow and rapidly varied flow analysis and its computations.
- CO5:** Students will be able to demonstrate and apply basic concepts related to Turbines and Pumps.

MODULE 1

DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS AND MODEL STUDIES :

Introduction, Systems of units, Dimensions of quantities, Dimensional Homogeneity of an equation. Analysis- Raleigh's method, Buckingham's Π theorem- problems. Model Studies, Similitude, Non-dimensional numbers: Froude models-Undistorted and Distorted models. Reynold's models-Problems. 10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS:

Introduction, Geometric properties of Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels. Chezy's equation, Manning's equation-problems. Most economical open channels- Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels- problems. **10**

Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

For CIE only:

1. Visit laboratory / nearby site to have an idea about channels types, operations.

MODULE 3

NON-UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS:

Introduction, Specific energy, Specific energy diagram, Critical depth, Conditions for Critical flow-Theory & problems. Hydraulic jump in a Horizontal Rectangular Channel- Theory and problems. Dynamic equation for Non-Uniform flow in an Open channel.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

For CIE only:

Visit laboratory / nearby site to have an idea about flow in channels types operations

MODULE 4

IMPACT OF JET ON FLAT VANES:

Introduction, Impulse- Momentum equation. Direct impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, Oblique impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, Direct impact on a moving plate, Direct impact of a jet on a series of a jet on a series of flat vanes on a wheel. Conditions for maximum hydraulic efficiency. Impact of a jet on hinged flat plate- problems.

IMPACT OF JET ON CURVED VANES

Introduction, Force exerted by a jet on a fixed curved vane, moving curved vane. Introduction to concept of velocity triangles, Impact of jet on a series of curved vanes-problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

PELTON WHEEL

Introduction to Turbines, Classification of Turbines. Pelton wheel- components, working and velocity triangles. Maximum power, efficiency, working proportions- problems.

KAPLAN TURBINES

Introduction, Components, Working and Velocity triangles-problems. Draft Tube: Types, efficiency of a Draft tube. Cavitation in Turbines.

CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS

Introduction, Classification, Priming, Heads and Efficiencies. Equation for work done, minimum starting speed, velocity triangles. Problems.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

For CIE only:

1. Priming of centrifugal pumps done at a house/college/agricultural field.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK**

each.1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from eachmodule 08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS

1. ‘A TextBook of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines’- R.K.Rajput, S.Chand& Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. ‘Text Book Of Fluid Mechanics&Hydraulic Machines’- R.K.Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
3. ‘Fluid Mechanics and Turbomachines’- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. ‘Introduction to Fluid Mechanics’ – Robert w. Fox: Philip j. Pritchard: Alan t. McDonald, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. ‘Introduction To Fluid Mechanics’ – Edward j. Shaughnessy,jr; Ira m. Katz;; James p Schaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition.

Web links

- <https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112105183/4> ,5,6
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112105183/7> , 8,9,10
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112105183/11> ,12,13,14
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112105183/16,17,18,19,20>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/112105183/16> ,17,18
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/1>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/2>

**IV Semester B.Tech
CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY & BUILDING MATERIALS**

Subject Code	19SCV44	IA Marks	: 50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4 (L)	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	50	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	02

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To Emphasis upon importance of concrete as versatile construction material & its suitability & adaptability in construction
- To study Concrete making materials & ingredients. Various parameters affecting properties of concrete including concrete mix proportioning.
- To provide need based Knowledge of methods to obtain various types of concretes.
- Conceptual understanding of Reinforced Cement Concrete & Properties and design of structural elements like slab, beam column and footings as per Indian Standard Codes.
- To study the concept of concrete its properties & to impart knowledge about its mechanized design & methods in light of modern construction.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to decide the use of supplement cementitious materials in concrete, use of different Admixtures and its applications as per requirement.
- CO2:** Students will be able to do typical concrete mix for required strength of concrete.
- CO3:** Students will be able to understand the durability of concrete, assessment and inspection of hardened concrete.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand the properties, uses, advantages and disadvantages of different materials used in construction
- CO5:** Students will be able to understand the component of building with their function & construction procedures.

MODULE 1

Concrete Ingredients

Cement – Cement manufacturing process, chemical composition and their importance, hydration of cement, types of cement. Testing of Cement, Fine Aggregate, Coarse Aggregate, Water And Admixtures. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

Workability-factors affecting workability. Measurement of workability, segregation and bleeding. Process of manufacturing of concrete, curing. Good and bad practices of making and using fresh concrete and effect of heat of hydration during mass concreting at project sites.

10Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

Concept of Mix Design with and without admixtures, variables in proportioning and Exposure conditions, Selection criteria of ingredients used for Mix Design, Procedure of mix proportioning. Numerical Examples of Mix Proportioning using IS-10262-2009

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

Stone as Building Material: Requirement of good building stones, Dressing of stones, Deterioration and Preservation of stone work.

Bricks: Classification, Manufacturing of clay bricks, Requirement of good bricks. Field and laboratory tests on bricks; compressive strength, water absorption, efflorescence, dimension and warpage. Cement Concrete Blocks, Stabilized Mud Blocks, Sizes, requirement of good blocks. Mortar: types and requirements. Timber as Construction Material

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

Doors, Windows and Ventilators: Location of doors and windows, technical terms, Materials for doors and windows, Paneled door, Flush door, Collapsible door, Rolling shutter, PVC Door, Paneled and glazed Window, Bay Window, French window. Ventilators. Sizes as per IS recommendations
Formwork: Introduction to Form Work, Scaffolding, Shoring, Under Pinning.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK**

each. 1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module 08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS

1. **Engineering Materials**, Rangawala P.C. Charter Publishing House, Anand, India.
2. **Engineering Materials**, Sushil Kumar, Standard Publication and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. **Concrete technology** – Theory and practice, M..S. Shetty, S. Chand and Co, New Delhi, 2002.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. ‘**A Text Book Building Materials**, by P.G. Varghese, Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., Publication.
2. **Advances in Building Materials and Construction** by Mohan Rai and M.P. Jain Singh – publication by CBRI, Roorkee.
3. **Concrete Technology**, Neville A.M and Brooks J.J — ELBS Edition. London
4. **Concrete Technology** – Gambhir M.L –Dhanpat Rai and Sons, New Delhi.

Web links and Video Lectures (e-Resources):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MOaC4Om4yNU>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CLmCpmhRWGU>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zNmzS6OOMFA>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EIDX28_8eQ&list=PL8BA090E69BF01BC2

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dFyxYwn663Q>

**IV Semester B.Tech
FLUID MECHANICS LABORATORY**

Sub Code :	19SCVL45	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Introduction to Fluid state of matter.
- Making students understand the importance of Fluid and its flow.
- To make student explore the various equations and the concepts related fluid motion and equilibrium.
- To make students understand the correlation between theory and practical by making them do practical's which are physical simulations of the theory such as Bernoulli's equation, Venturimeter, orifices etc..

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to calculate the discharge of fluid in pipes and in Open Channel Flows.
- CO2:** Students will be able to measure the pressure at various conditions with different types of pressure measuring devices.
- CO3:** Students will be able to gain knowledge in Hydraulic Machines (Pumps And Turbines).
- CO4:** Students will be able to analyze the impact of jet on vanes which is a base for analysis and design of turbo machines.
- CO5:** Students will able to possess the skills to solve problems in Uniform, Gradually and Rapidly varied flows in steady conditions.

Experiments

1. Calibration of V-notch, Rectangular and Cipolletti notch.
 2. Calibration of Broad- Crested Weir
 3. Calibration of Venturiflume
 4. Calibration of Venturimeter and Orificemeter.
 5. Determination of Darcy's friction factor for a straight pipe
 6. Determination of Hydraulic coefficients of a vertical orifice
 7. Determination of vane coefficients for a flat vane & semicircular vane
 8. Performance characteristics of a single stage centrifugal pump
 9. Performance characteristics of a Pelton wheel
 10. Performance characteristics of a Kaplan turbine
-

Continuous Internal Assessment

1	Mini –Project	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment using rubrics	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	02
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks (Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks (Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

TEXT BOOKS

1. Experiments in Fluid Mechanics – Sarbjit Singh- PHI Pvt. Ltd.- NewDelhi- 2009-12-30

2. Hydraulics and Hydraulic Mechines Laboratory Manual – Dr. N. Balasubramanya.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. ‘Introduction to Fluid Mechanics’ – Robert w. Fox: Philip j. Pritchard: Alan t. McDonald, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.

2. ‘Introduction To Fluid Mechanics’ – Edward j. Shaughnessy,jr; Ira m. Katz:: James pSchaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition

‘Hydraulics and Fluid Mechanics’ – Dr. P.N. Modi&Dr S.M. Seth, Standard Book House- New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

Online resources

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/1>

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/2>

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/4>

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/7>

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/13>

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105103096/23>

IV Semester B.Tech
BUILDING CONSTRUCTION PRACTICE LABORATORY

Sub Code :	19SCVL46	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Ability to explore career options and the building construction industry and to develop sound safety practices
- Ability to demonstrate the desirable work habits, appreciate and demonstrate high standard of workmanship.
- Identify masonry tools and materials and to develop and apply basic skills in masonry work
- To develop and apply basic skills in bar bending schedule and to identify exterior tools and materials.
- To have knowledge on practical Plumbing and Electrical Layout.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to understand the marking for buildings.
- CO2:** Students will be able to understand better masonry procedure.
- CO3:** Students will be able to understand plastering works and flooring.
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand quality control in building construction.
- CO5:** Students will able to understand existing Bye-Laws

Experiments:

1. Center line marking for buildings.
2. Single line layout drawing as per prevailing building Bye- Laws.
3. Foundation markings.
4. Brick/Stone/Block Masonry Construction.
5. Preparation of bar bending schedule for a residential building.
6. Preparing Plumbing layouts.
7. Preparing Electrical layouts.
8. Hands on experience plastering and painting.
9. Hands on experience on vitrified/granite floorings.
10. On site qualitative analysis of construction works.
11. On site workability and compressive strength testing.
12. On site soil testing.

Continuous Internal Assessment:

1	Mini –Project	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment using rubrics	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	02
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks) Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. A Text Book Building Materials, by P.G. Varghese, Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., Publication.
2. Advances in Building Materials and Construction by Mohan Rai and M.P. Jain Singh – publication by CBRI, Roorkee.
3. Concrete Technology, Neville A.M and Brooks J.J — ELBS Edition. London
4. Concrete Technology – Gambhir M.L –Dhanpat Rai and Sons, New Delhi.

Web Links

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/1>,
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/6>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/11>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/9>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/10>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/14>

IV Semester B.Tech
CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY LABORATORY

Sub Code :	19SCVL47	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To Emphasis upon importance of concrete as versatile construction material & its suitability & adaptability in concrete construction
- To study knowledge of Concrete making materials & ingredients &. Various parameters affecting properties of concrete including concrete mix proportioning.
- To provide need based Knowledge of methods to obtain various types of concretes.
- Conceptual understanding of Reinforced cement concrete & Properties and design of structural elements like slab, beam column and footings as per Indian standard codes.
- To study the concept of prestressed concrete its properties & to impart knowledge about its mechanized design & methods in light of modern construction.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to know the properties of basic building materials
- CO2:** Students will be able to grasp the knowledge of workability in concrete.
- CO3:** Students will be able to know the properties of fresh and hardened concrete.
- CO4:** Students will be able to prepare concrete mix design.
- CO5:** Students will able to know the properties of hardened concrete by non-destructive tests.

Experiments

1. Tests on Cement: Normal Consistency, Initial and Final Setting time, Compressive strength Test and specific gravity
2. Tests on Aggregates: Specific gravity test and Sieve analysis, Aggregate shape tests (combined index and angularity number)
3. Tests on Concrete: Design of concrete mix as per IS-10262-2009
4. Tests on fresh concrete: Slump, Compaction factor and Vee Bee test
5. Tests on hardened concrete: Compressive strength test, Split tensile Strength Test, Flexural strength test and NDT test by rebound hammer.

Continuous Internal Assessment

1	Mini –Project	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment using rubrics	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	02
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. M.L.Gambir, "Concrete Manual", Danpat Rai and sons, New Delhi
2. Shetty M.S, "Concrete Technology", S. Chand & Co. Ltd, New Delhi.
3. Mehta P.K, "Properties of Concrete", Tata McGraw Hill Publications, New Delhi.
4. Neville AM, "Properties of Concrete", ELBS Publications, London.
5. Relevant BIS codes.

Web links

<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/1>,
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/6>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/11>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/9>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/10>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/14>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/19>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/23>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/27>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/31>
<https://nptel.ac.in/courses/105102012/36>

**IV Semester B.Tech
ESEP-BASIC SOIL MECHANICS
LABORATORY**

Sub Code : 19SCVL48
Hrs/ Week : 1L+1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 25
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks: 25

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Provide Students with Basic Understanding.
- To carry out laboratory tests and to identify soil as per IS codal procedures
- To perform laboratory tests to determine index properties of soil

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** On the completion of this course students are expected to attain the following outcomes; Will acquire an understanding of the procedures to determine index properties of any type of soil
- CO2:** Students will be able to conduct appropriate laboratory/field experiments and interpret the results and Classify soil type based on index properties and field identification

THEORY

Introduction to Soil Mechanics Introduction, origin and formation of soil, Phase Diagram, phase relationships, definitions and their inter relationships.

Determination of Index properties-Specific gravity, water content, in-situ density and particle size analysis (sieve and sedimentation analysis), Atterberg's Limits, consistency indices, relative density, activity of clay, Plasticity chart, unified and BIS Soil Classification.

Soil Structure and Clay Mineralogy Single grained, honey combed, flocculent and dispersed structures, Valence bonds, Soil-Water system, Electrical diffuse double layer, adsorbed water, base-exchange capacity, Isomorphous substitution. Common clay minerals in soil and their structures-Kaolinite, Illite and ontmorillonite and their application in Engineering

Compaction of Soils: Definition, Principle of compaction, Standard and Modified proctor's compaction tests, factors affecting compaction, effect of compaction on soil properties, Field compaction control - compactive effort & method of compaction, lift thickness and number of passes, Proctor's needle, Compacting equipments and their suitability.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Basic Soil Properties.
 2. Water content determination by oven drying method and infrared moisture method.
 3. In-situ density test by Core cutter method.
 4. Relative density test for sand.
 5. Specific gravity test (Pycnometer and density bottle method).
 6. Consistency limits.
 7. Grain size analysis: Sieve Analysis.
 8. Hydrometer Analysis (Demonstration).
 9. Light Compaction
 7. Soil Classification.
-

Continuous Internal Assessment:

1	Mini –Project	Regular mode of Assessment	05
2	Assessment in each Lab session for 1 mark (10 Lab Sessions)	Regular mode of Assessment using rubrics	10
3	Maintaining the Record Note Book	Regular mode of Assessment	03
4	Viva at the end of each lab session	2 marks for each Module	02
5	Attendance	As per the guidelines given in the regulations	05
Total			25

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

Two experiments are to be performed by the students in the examination.

Experiment 1: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5 Marks)

Experiment 2: 20 Marks

(Initial writing 5 Marks+ Experiment 10 Marks+ Calculation/result 5

Marks) Viva: 10 Marks

*Change of experiment/s: Allowed change of maximum 2 experiments with 10% reduction in Marks (5 Marks) for one experiment. (When a candidate changes both the experiments, 10 Marks will be deducted from his/her total Marks).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Gopal Ranjan and Rao A.S.R., Basic and Applied Soil Mechanics- (2000), New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Punmia B C, Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering- (2012), Laxmi Publications.
3. Murthy V.N.S., Principles of Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering- (1996), 4thEdition,UBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
4. Braja, M. Das, Geotechnical Engineering; (2002), Fifth Edition, Thomson Business Information India (P) Ltd., India.

Web links and Video Lectures (e-Resources):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hNNilk-OKaw&list=PL9gC9b3b4pMvoQ4Sj8imonJgfDW2GxPTF>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pM-w_cvk1nA

<https://youtu.be/cltEEEQa7KI>

<https://youtu.be/kXkp3AaP7sw>

<https://youtu.be/AM-NrQoRIYY>

<https://www.aboutcivil.org/index-properties-of-soil.html>

<https://faculty.uml.edu/ehajduk/Teaching/14.330/documents/14.330SoilClassification.pdf>

https://aftabur.weebly.com/uploads/1/0/6/0/10606953/ch3_clay_mineralogy_soil_structure.pdf

<https://theconstructor.org/geotechnical/compaction-of-soils3/1053/>

<https://environment.uwe.ac.uk/geocal/SoilMech/shear/shear.htm>

<https://www.soilmanagementindia.com/consolidation-of-soil/consolidation-of-soil-meaning-and-mechanics-typesterzaghis-theory-and-determination/165>

PART-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme - 2

Subject Code	19SQA49	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations. Domain specific training in respective branches with tests.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A**Percentages, Simple interest and Compound interest –**

- Percentages as Fractions and Decimals
- Percentage Increase / Decrease
- Simple Interest
- Compound Interest
- Relation between Simple and Compound Interest
- Finding CI without using formula

Data interpretation and Data sufficiency –

- Data Interpretation – Tables
- Data Interpretation - Pie Chart
- Data Interpretation - Bar Graph
- Data Interpretation - Line Graph
- Data Sufficiency

Alligation and Mixture, Ratio and Proportion, Partnerships –

- Basic Concept of Alligation and Mixture
- concept of mixture containing more than two Ingredients
- Concept and Problem solving technique in Ratio and Proportion
- Partnership "

Permutation, Combination and Probability –

- a. Fundamental Counting Principle
- b. Permutation and Combination
- c. Computation of Permutation
- d. Circular Permutations
- e. Computation of Combination
- f. Probability
- g. Total Probability
- h. Finding Probability without using Combination
- i. Finding Probability using Pascal Triangle

Sentence correction –

- a. Subject Verb Agreement.
- b. Pronoun Reference and Agreement.
- c. Verb Tense.
- d. Modifier.
- e. Parallelism.
- f. Idioms.
- g. Comparisons.
- h. Prepositions.
- i. Determiners.

PART - B

Structural Analysis

Hydrology

Irrigation Engineering

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple choice questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART – B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	19SQA49	IA Marks	-50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Have exposure on the latest development
- CO2: Acquire new skills
- CO3: Become Industry ready
- CO4: Have more confidence
- CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method

Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

Srinivas University
College of Engineering and Technology
Mukka, Mangaluru – 574 146

V & VI SEMESTER

B.TECH
CIVIL ENGINEERING

SCHEME & SYLLABUS
2019

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING
V SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV51	Structural Analysis -II	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV52	Design of RCC Structural Elements	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV53X	Core Elective-1	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV54X	Optional /Soft Elective	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL55	Construction Technology Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL56	Civil CAD Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL57	Geotechnical Engineering Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCVL58	ESEP -MOOC			2	50		50	02
9	19SQA59	Part–A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 3 (ESEP 3)	2	0	0	50		50	02
		Part–B: International Certification Course on Current Trends							
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 1		Optional / Soft Elective	
19SCV531	Geo -Technical Engineering	19SCV541	Management & Entrepreneurship
19SCV532	Substructure Construction Technology	19SCV542	Principles of Architecture
19SCV533	Advanced Soil Mechanics	19SCV543	Principles of Construction Management
19SCV534	Soil Structure Interaction	19SCV544	Principles of Town Planning & Urban Development
19SCV535	Soil & Rock Mechanics	19SCV545	Ground Improvement Techniques

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING VI SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV61	Advanced Design of RC Structures	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV62	Environmental Engineering	4			50	50	100	04
3	19SCV63X	Core Elective-2	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SXX64X	Open Elective - 1	4			50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL65	Civil Design Laboratory (Design of C-D Structures)	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL66	Highway Material Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCVL67	Extensive Survey Project	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	19SCV68	ESEP-Mini Project				50	-	50	
9	19SQA69	Part-A:Employability Enhancement Skill Programme 4(ESEP 4)	2	0	0	50		50	02
		Part-B: International Certification Course on Current Trends	0	0	0		-	-	
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 2		Open Elective - 1	
19SCV631	Transportation Engineering	19SCV641	Occupation Health & Safety in Construction Industry
19SCV632	Highway Geometric Design	19SCV642	Air Pollution & Control
19SCV633	Urban Transport Planning	19SCS641	Web 2.0
19SCV634	Reinforced Earth Structures	19SCS642	Designing Embedded Systems
		19SEC641	Cryptography and Network Security
		19SEC642	Python Application Programming
		19SME641	Total Quality Management
		19SME642	Micro – Electromechanical Systems.

**V Semester B.Tech Civil Engineering
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS – II**

Sub Code: 19SCV51
Hrs/ Week: 4
Credits: 4

IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. The course provides students with the principles of elastic structural analysis and behavior of indeterminate structures.
2. Classical and modern analysis techniques are introduced to arm the students with the necessary tools to better appreciate the real behavior of structures.
3. To analyze rigid jointed sway frames
4. To understand the structural behavior before and after application of loads.
5. Able to analyze various structures.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand statically indeterminacy and adopt an appropriate structural analysis technique
- CO2:** Able to use slope deflection method and rotation contribution method for various civil engineering structures.
- CO3:** perform basic calculations to determine redundant forces and displacements, appreciate the difference between idealized structures, models and real structures.
- CO4:** Able to identify determinate, indeterminate, stable and unstable structures.
- CO5:** Possess an understanding of the physical response of structures to various loads and to identify the kinematic indeterminacy of structures.

MODULE 1

SLOPE DEFLECTION METHOD: Introduction, Sign convention, Development of slope-deflection equations and Analysis of Beams and Orthogonal Rigid jointed plane frames (non-sway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid)

SWAY ANALYSIS: Analysis of rigid jointed plane frames (sway, members assumed to be axially rigid and kinematic redundancy ≤ 3) by slope deflection methods.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

MOMENT DISTRIBUTION METHOD: Introduction, Definition of terms-Distribution factor, Carry over factor, Development of method and Analysis of beams and orthogonal rigid jointed plane frames (nonsway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid)

SWAY ANALYSIS: Analysis of rigid jointed plane frames (sway, members assumed to be axially rigid and kinematic redundancy ≤ 3) by moment distribution methods.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

KANIS METHODS: Introduction, Basic Concept, Analysis of Continuous beams and Analysis of rigidjointed non-sway plane frames. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

FLEXIBILITY MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS: Introduction, Development of flexibility matrix for plane truss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements and Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by flexibility method with static indeterminacy. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

STIFFNESS MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS: Introduction, Development of stiffness matrix for planetruss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements and Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by stiffness method with kinematic indeterminacy. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten MCQ to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (1 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Hibbeler R C, -Structural Analysis||, Pearson Publication
2. L S Negi and R S Jangid, —Structural Analysis||, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd.
3. D S Prakash Rao, -Structural Analysis: A Unified Approach||, Universities Press
4. K.U. Muthu, H.Narendra etal, -Indeterminate Structural Analysis||, IK International Publishing Pvt. Ltd.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Basic Structural Analysis- Reddy C.S. - Second Edition, TataMcGraw Hill Publication CompanyLtd.
2. Theory of Structures Vol. 2 - S.P. Gupta, G.S. Pandit and R.Gupta, Tata McGraw Hill PublicationCompany Ltd.
3. Structural Dynamics-by M.Mukhopadhyay,
4. Structural Analysis-II -S. S. Bhavikatti – Vikas Publishers, NewDelhi.
5. Basics of Structural Dynamics and Aseismic Design ByDamodhar Swamy and Kavita PHILearning Private Limited
6. Structural Analysis- D.S. Prakash Rao, A Unified Approach,University Press
7. Structural Analysis, 4th Edition, Amit Prasanth & Aslam Kassimali, Thomson Learning.

V Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF RCC STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

Sub Code : 19SCV52
Hrs/ Week: 4
Credits: 4

IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Identify, formulate and solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to different kinds of loading.
2. Follow a procedural knowledge in designing various structural RC elements.
3. Impart the culture of following the codes for strength, serviceability and durability as an ethics.
4. Provide knowledge in analysis and design of RC elements for the success in competitive examinations.
5. To introduce the various philosophies of R.C. design and to study in detail the limit state design of structural elements such as beams, columns and footings

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Understand the design philosophy and principles.
CO2: Solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to flexure, shear and torsion.
CO3: Demonstrate the procedural knowledge in designs of RC structural elements such as slabs, columns and footings
CO4: Able to prove the cracking in structural concrete members and its calculation
CO5: Able to understand the detailing of RC structural elements

MODULE 1

GENERAL FEATURES OF REINFORCED CONCRETE: Introduction, Design Loads, Materials for Reinforced Concrete and Code requirements. Design Philosophy – Limit State Design principles. Philosophy of limit state design, Principles of limit states, Factor of Safety, Characteristic and design loads, Characteristic and design strength. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

PRINCIPLES OF LIMIT STATE DESIGN AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF R.C. SECTION:

General aspects of Ultimate strength, Stress block parameters for limit state of collapse, Ultimate flexural strength of singly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of doubly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of flanged sections, Ultimate shear strength of RC sections, Ultimate torsional strength of RC sections, Concepts of development length and anchorage, Analysis examples of singly reinforced, doubly reinforced, flanged sections, shear strength and development length. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

DESIGN OF BEAMS: General Specification for flexure design of beams-practical requirements, size of beam, cover to reinforcement-spacing of bars. General aspects of serviceability-Deflection limits in IS: 456

– 2000. Design procedures for critical sections for moment and shears. Anchorages of bars, check for development length, Reinforcement requirements, Slenderness limits for beams to ensure lateral stability, Design examples for simply supported and Cantilever beams for rectangular and flanged sections.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF SLABS: General consideration of design of slabs, Rectangular slabs spanning one direction,

Rectangular slabs spanning in two directions for various boundary conditions. Design of simply supported, cantilever and continuous slabs as per IS: 456 – 2000.

DESIGN OF STAIR CASES: General features, types of stair case, loads on stair cases, effective span as per IS code provisions, distribution of loading on stairs, Design of stair cases. With waist slabs.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

DESIGN OF COLUMNS: General aspects, effective length of column, loads on columns, slenderness ratio for columns, minimum eccentricity, design of short axially loaded columns, design of column subject to combined axial load and uniaxial moment and biaxial moment using SP – 16 charts.

DESIGN OF FOOTINGS: Introduction, load for footing, Design basis for limit state method, Design of isolated rectangular footing for axial load and uniaxial moment, design of pedestal.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions,

Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Unnikrishnan Pillai and Devdas Menon, — Reinforced Concrete Designll , McGraw Hill, New Delhi
2. Subramanian, -Design of Concrete Structuresll, Oxford University Press
3. H J Shah, -Reinforced Concrete Vol. 1 (Elementary Reinforced Concrete)ll, Charotar Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Limit State Design of Reinforced concrete-by P.C. Varghese, PHI Learning Private Limited 2008-2009
2. Fundamentals of Reinforced concrete Design-by M.L.Gambhir, PHI Learning Private Limited2008-2009.
3. Reinforced concrete Design-by Pallai and Menon, TMH Education Private Limited,
4. Reinforced concrete Design-by S.N.Shinha, TMH Education Private Limited,
5. Reinforced concrete Design-by Karve & Shaha, Structures Publishers Pune.
6. Design of RCC Structural Elements S. S. Bhavikatti, Vol-I, NewAge International Publications,New Delhi.
7. IS456: 2000 and SP16

**V Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 1- I
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING**

**Sub Code : 19SCV531
Hrs/ Week: 4
Credits: 4**

**IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50**

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To explain role of water in soil behavior and how soil stresses, permeability and quantity of seepage
2. To determine shear parameters and stress changes in soil due to foundation loads
3. To estimate the magnitude and time-rate of settlement due to consolidation
4. To explain how earth pressure theory is important in retaining structure design
5. To explain the concept of bearing capacity and how to estimate the safe bearing capacity for various foundation system including settlement consideration

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand to the concept of soil stress behavior and permeability characteristics
CO2: Possess knowledge on stress strain parameters of soil
CO3: Understand the concept on earth pressure characteristics
CO4: Knowledge on bearing capacity for various foundation system
CO5: Selection of shallow foundation system

MODULE 1

CLASSIFICATION OF SOILS: Purpose of soil classification, Particle size classification –IS classification, Textural classification. IS classification - Plasticity chart and its importance, Field identification of soils.

FLOW OF WATER THROUGH SOILS: Darcy's law- assumption and validity, coefficient of permeability and its determination (laboratory and field), factors affecting permeability, permeability of stratified soils, Seepage velocity, Superficial velocity and coefficient of percolation, quick sand phenomena, Capillary Phenomena. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Concept of shear strength, Mohr-coulomb theory, conventional and modified failure envelopes, Effective stress concept total stress, effective stress and Neutral stress, Concept of pore pressure, Total and effective shear strength parameters, factors affecting shear strength of soils, Sensitivity and Thixotropy of clay.

DETERMINATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Measurement of shear parameters- Direct shear test, unconfined compression test, Triaxial compression test and vane shear test, Test under different drainage conditions. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Definition, Mass-spring analogy, Terzaghi's one dimensional consolidation theory-assumption and limitations (no derivation), Normally consolidated, under consolidated and over consolidated soils, pre-consolidation pressure and its determination by Casagrande's method. Consolidation characteristics of soil (C_c , a_v , m_v and C_v).. Laboratory one dimensional consolidation test, Determination of consolidation characteristics of soils-compression index and coefficient of consolidation (square root of time fitting method, logarithmic time fitting method).

FOUNDATION SETTLEMENT: Importance and Concept of Settlement Analysis, Immediate, Consolidation and Secondary settlements (no derivations, but, computation using relevant formula for Normally Consolidated soils), Tolerance. BIS specifications for total and differential Settlements of footings and rafts. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

STRESSES IN SOILS: Boussinesq's and Westergaard's theories for concentrated, circular and rectangular loads. Comparison of Boussinesq's and Westergaard's analysis. Pressure distribution diagrams, Contact pressure, Newmark's chart (only theory)

LATERAL EARTH PRESSURE: Active and passive earth pressures, Earth pressure at rest. Rankine's and Coulomb's Earth pressure theories--assumptions and limitations, Earth pressure distribution.

STABILITY OF EARTH SLOPES: Types of slopes, causes and type of failure of slopes. Definition of factor of safety, Stability of infinite slopes, Stability of finite slopes by Taylor's stability number. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

BEARING CAPACITY: Definitions of ultimate, net and safe bearing capacities, Allowable bearing pressure. Terzaghi's and Brinch Hansen's bearing capacity equations -assumptions and limitations, Bearing capacity of footing subjected to eccentric loading. Effect of ground water table on bearing capacity. Field methods of evaluation of bearing capacity - Plate load test, Standard penetration test and cone penetration

PROPORTIONING SHALLOW AND PILE FOUNDATIONS

Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the selection of depth of foundation, Factors influencing Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the choice of foundation, Proportioning isolated, combined, strip and mat foundations, Classification of pile foundation, Pile load capacity, Proportioning pile foundation. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Soil Engineering in Theory and Practice- Alam Singh and Chowdhary G.R. (1994), CBSPublishers and Distributors Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg.-Punmia B.C. (2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co., New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Foundation Analysis and Design- Bowles J.E. (1996), 5thEdition, McGraw Hill Pub. Co. NewYork.
2. Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering- Murthy V.N.S. (1996), 4th Edition, UBSPublishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. Basic and Applied Soil Mechanics- Gopal Ranjan and Rao A.S.R. (2000), New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
4. Geotechnical Engineering – Venkatrahmaiah C. (2006), 3rd Edition, New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
5. Soil Mechanics- Craig R.F. (1987), Van Nostrand Reinhold Co. Ltd.
6. Principles of Geotechnical Engineering- Braja M. Das (2002), 5th Edition, Thomson BusinessInformation India (P) Ltd., India.
7. Text Book of Geotechnical Engineering- Iqbal H. Khan (2005), 2nd Edition, PHI, India.

**V Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 1- II**

SUBSTRUCTURE CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY

Sub Code : 19SCV532
Hrs/ Week: 4
Credits: 4

IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine shear parameters and stress changes in soil due to foundation loads
2. To estimate the magnitude and time-rate of settlement due to consolidation
3. To understand the concept of design on shallow, raft, pile foundations
4. To understand the design of retaining walls
5. To understand the concepts of pile and machine foundations

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Understand to the concept of soil stress behavior of soil and stress strain parameters of soil
- CO2: Possess knowledge on settlement characteristics of soil
- CO3: Understand the concept on design on shallow, raft, pile foundations
- CO4: Design retaining walls
- CO5: Understand design concepts of pile and machine foundations

MODULE 1

SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Concept of shear strength, Mohr-coulomb theory, conventional and modified failure envelopes, Effective stress concept total stress, effective stress and Neutral stress, Concept of pore pressure, Total and effective shear strength parameters, factors affecting shear strength of soils, Sensitivity and Thixotropy of clay.

DETERMINATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Measurement of shear parameters- Direct shear test, unconfined compression test, Triaxial compression test and vane shear test, Test under different drainage conditions. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Definition, Mass-spring analogy, Terzaghi's one dimensional consolidation theory-assumption and limitations (no derivation), Normally consolidated, under consolidated and over consolidated soils, pre-consolidation pressure and its determination by Casagrande's method. Consolidation characteristics of soil (C_c , a_v , m_v and C_v). Laboratory one dimensional consolidation test, Determination of consolidation characteristics of soils-compression index and coefficient of consolidation (square root of time fitting method, logarithmic time fitting method).

FOUNDATION SETTLEMENT: Importance and Concept of Settlement Analysis, Immediate, Consolidation and Secondary settlements (no derivations, but, computation using relevant formula for Normally Consolidated soils), Tolerance. BIS specifications for total and differential Settlements of footings and rafts. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

SHALLOW FOUNDATIONS: Basic requirements of foundation –Types and selection of foundations. Bearing capacity of foundations, structural design of isolated, combined, eccentric, strip, and strap footings, Detailing of reinforcement.

RAFT FOUNDATIONS: Types of rafts, SBC of raft foundation and structural design of different raft foundations, Detailing of reinforcement. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF RETAINING WALLS: Stability Checks and structural design of gravity, Cantilever retaining walls, Detailing of reinforcement. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

PILE FOUNDATIONS: Types of piles, Load carrying capacity of single and pile groups, structural design of piles, pile caps and pile-raft foundation, Detailing of reinforcement.

Machine Foundations: Vibration analysis of machine foundation – Design of foundation for Reciprocating machines and Impact machines – as per I S Codes, Detailing of reinforcement.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Varghese P.C. Design of RC foundations, PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
2. Unnikrishnana Pillai & Devadas Menon, Reinforces Concrete Design, McGraw Hill Publishing Pvt. Ltd.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Bowles J.E., -Foundation Analysis and Designll, McGraw Hill Publishing co., New York, 1986
2. Tomlinson. M.J, -Foundation Design and Constructionll, Longman, Sixth Edition, New Delhi, 1995.
3. Das, B.M., Principles of Foundation Engineering, Design and Construction, Fourth Edition,PWS Publishing, 1999.
4. Narayan V. Nayak, Foundation design manual, Dhanpat Rai & Sons, 2006.
5. Prakash Shamsher and Puri Vijay K, Foundations for Machines, Analysis and Designll JohnWiley and Sons, USA, 1988.
6. IS 2911: Part 1: Sec 1: 1979 Code of practice for design and construction of pile foundations: Part 1 Concrete piles, Section 1 Driven cast in-situ concrete piles.

V Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 1 - III
ADVANCED SOIL MECHANICS

Sub Code : 19SCV533

Hrs/ Week: 4

Credits: 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine shear parameters and stress changes in soil due to foundation loads
2. To estimate the magnitude and time-rate of settlement due to consolidation
3. To determine shear parameters of cohesion and cohesion less soils.
4. To explain the concept of slope stability analysis for various slope conditions including graphical methods.
5. To understand elastic theories of stress distribution

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand to the concept of soil stress behavior of soil and stress strain parameters of soil

CO2: Possess knowledge on settlement characteristics of soil

CO3: Understand shear parameters of cohesion and cohesionless soils.

CO4: Understand the concept on slope stability analysis for various slope conditions including graphical methods

CO5: Understand elastic theories of stress distribution

MODULE 1

Concept of shear strength, Mohr-coulomb theory, conventional and modified failure envelopes, Effective stress concept total stress, effective stress and Neutral stress, Concept of pore pressure, Total and effective shear strength parameters, factors affecting shear strength of soils, Sensitivity and Thixotropy of clay. Measurement of shear parameters- Direct shear test, unconfined compression test, Triaxial compression test and vane shear test, Test under different drainage conditions.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

Mass-spring analogy, Terzaghi's one dimensional consolidation theory-assumption and limitations (no derivation), Normally consolidated, under consolidated and over consolidated soils, pre-consolidation pressure and its determination by Casagrande's method. Consolidation characteristics of soil (C_c , a_v , m_v and C_v). Laboratory one dimensional consolidation test, Determination of consolidation characteristics of soils-compression index and coefficient of consolidation (square root of time fitting method, logarithmic time fitting method).

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

Shear strength parameters of cohesion less and saturated cohesive soils, Principle of effective stress, effect of rate of strain on shear parameters, Stress –Strain relationship, Pore pressure coefficients, Concept of stress path, Laboratory and Field testing their limitations, Numerical Problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

Stability Analysis of Slope: Effective and total stress approach, shape of slip surface, Swedish method, methods of slices, location of centre of critical slip circle, Friction circle method, Taylor's stability number, Bishop's rigorous analysis, stability during critical conditions, Numerical Problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

Elastic theories of stress distribution in soils -Bousinesq's, Westergaard's, Birmister's theories. Different conditions of loading, Isobars, Newmark's chart, Numerical problems. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. An Introduction to the Mechanics of Soils and Foundation -Atkinson J. H. - McGraw-Hill Co. (1993)
2. Soil Mechanics SI version - Lambe, T. W. and Whitman, R. V, John Wiley & Sons.(2011)
3. Soil Mechanics and Foundations, Muniram Budhu(2007), John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Geotechnical Engineering-Donold P Coduto Phi Learning Private Limited, New Delhi
2. Soil Mechanics - J A Knappett and R F Craig Eighth Edition (4012), SponPress Taylor & Francis

V Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 1 - IV
SOIL STRUCTURE INTERACTION

Sub Code : 19SCV534

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To provide an understanding of the relevance and significance of soil-structure interaction in the case of different types of structures
2. Ability to understand different types of soil response models
3. Ability to evaluate Numerical analysis of finite plates
4. Ability to understand Beam on Elastic Foundation
5. Ability to understand Elastic Analysis of Pile.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Analyze and able understand soil-foundation interaction problems

CO2: Analyze and able to estimate beams of finite length

CO3: Analyze and able to understand Classification of finite beams in relation to their stiffness

CO4: Able to analyse beams and foundations

CO5: Able to analyse pile foundation.

MODULE 1

Soil-Foundation Interaction: Introduction to soil-foundation interaction problems, Soil behaviour, Foundation behaviour, Interface behaviour, Scope of soil foundation interaction analysis.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

Soil response models, Winkler, Elastic continuum, two parameter elastic models, Elastic plastic behaviour, Time dependent behaviour.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

Beam on Elastic Foundation- Soil Models: Infinite beam, two parameters, Isotropic elastic half space, Analysis of beams of finite length, Classification of finite beams in relation to their stiffness.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

Plate on Elastic Medium: Thin and thick plates, Analysis of finite plates, Numerical analysis of finite plates, simple solutions.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

Elastic Analysis of Pile: Elastic analysis of single pile, Theoretical solutions for settlement and load distributions, Analysis of pile group, Interaction analysis, Load distribution in groups with rigid cap. Laterally Loaded Pile: Load deflection prediction for laterally loaded piles, Subgrade reaction and elastic analysis, Interaction analysis. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. N.P. Kurien, Design of Foundation Sytems: Principles & Practices, Narosa, New Delhi1992.
2. E.S. Melerski, Design Analysis of Beams, Circular Plates and Cylindrical Tanks on ElasticFoundation, Taylor and Francis, 2006.
3. L.C. Reese, Single piles and pile groups under lateral loading, Taylor & Francis, 2000
4. G. Jones, Analysis of Beams on Elastic foundation, Thomas Telford, 1997.

V Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 1-V
SOIL AND ROCK MECHANICS

Sub Code : 19SCV535

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine various classifications of rocks
2. To estimate the various tests on rocks
3. To determine stability of rocks slopes and foundations on rocks
4. To explain the concept underground and open excavation

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand the various classifications of rocks

CO2: To understand the various tests on rocks

CO3: To possess knowledge on stability of rocks slopes and foundations on rocks

CO4: To understand the concept underground and open excavation

MODULE 1

Engineering Classification of Rocks: Classification of intact rocks, Rock mass classifications, Rock Quality Designation (RQD), Rock Structure Rating (RSR), Rock Mass Rating (RMR), Norwegian Geotechnical Classification (Q-system), Strength and modulus from classifications, Classification based on strength & modulus and strength and fracture strain, Geo Engineering classification. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 2

Laboratory and In-Situ Testing of Rocks: Physical properties, Compressive strength, Tensile strength, Direct shear test, Triaxial shear test, Slake durability test, Schmidt rebound hardness test, Sound velocity test, In-Situ Tests: Seismic methods, Electrical resistivity method, In situ stresses, Plate loading test, Goodman jack test, Plate jacking test, In-situ shear test, Field permeability test. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 3

Strength, Modulus and Stresses-Strain Responses of Rocks: Factors influencing rock response, Strength criteria for isotropic intact rocks, Modulus of intact rocks, effect of confining pressure, Uniaxial Compressive strength, Strength criteria for intact rocks, Strength due to induced anisotropy in rocks,. Stress Strain Models: Constitutive relationships, Elastic, Elasto- plastic, Visco-elastic, Elastovisco plastic stress- strain models. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 4

Stability of Rock Slopes and Foundations on Rocks: Rock slopes, Modes of failure, Rotational failure, Plane failure, Design charts, Wedge method of analysis, Buckling failure, Toppling failure, Improvement of slope stability and protection. Foundations on Rock: Introduction, Estimation of bearing capacity, Stress distribution, Sliding stability of dam foundations, strengthening measures, Settlements in rocks, Bearing capacity of pile/pier in rock, Remedial measures, Foundations located on edge of jointed slope. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

MODULE 5

Underground and Open Excavations: Blasting operational planning, Explosive products, Blast Design, Underground blast design, controlled blasting techniques, blasting damage and control, Safe practice with explosives and shots. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstrations.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Goodman – Introduction to Rock mechanics, Willey International (1980).
2. Ramamurthy, T. – Engineering in Rocks for slopes, foundations, and tunnels, Prentice Hall India (2007).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Jaeger, J. C. and Cook, N. G. W. – Fundamentals of Rock Mechanics, Chapman and Hall, London.(1979)
2. Hoek, E. and Brown, E. T. – Underground Excavation in Rock, Institution Mining and Metallurgy, 1982.
3. Brady, B. H. G. and Brown, E. T. – Rock Mechanics for Underground Mining, Chapman & Hall, 1993.

V Semester B.Tech
OPTIONAL ELECTIVE II -1
MANAGEMENT & ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Sub Code : 19SCV541

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the scope and functional areas of management and approaches
2. Analyze nature and purpose, types of any organization
3. Outline the qualities of a successful entrepreneur
4. Understand the objective, scope, role of SSI in economic development
5. Identify the project and select, report with proper planning and guidance.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand scope and levels of management with modern management

CO2: Able to solve the problems of selection and recruitment

CO3: Able to understand the concept of entrepreneurship – evolution, development and stages of entrepreneurship.

CO4: Able to understand the policies of impact of liberalization, privatization, and globalization on SSI

CO5: Able to identify the project and select, report with proper planning and guidance.

MODULE 1

Management: Nature and Functions of Management – Importance, Definition, Management Functions, Levels of Management, Roles of Manager, Managerial Skills, Management & Administration, Management as a Science, Art & Profession (Selected topics of Chapter 1, Text 1). Planning: Planning-Nature, Importance, Types, Steps and Limitations of Planning; Decision Making – Meaning, Types and Steps in Decision Making. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 2

Organizing and Staffing: Organization-Meaning, Characteristics, Process of Organizing, Principles of Organizing, Span of Management (meaning and importance only), Departmentalization, Committees– Meaning, Types of Committees; Centralization Vs. Decentralization of Authority and Responsibility; **Staffing**-Need and Importance, Recruitment and Selection Process. Directing and Controlling: Meaning and Requirements of Effective Direction, Giving Orders; Motivation-Nature of Motivation, Motivation Theories (Maslow's Need- Hierarchy Theory and Herzberg's Two Factor Theory); Communication – Meaning, Importance and Purposes of Communication; Leadership-Meaning, Characteristics, Behavioral Approach of Leadership; Coordination-Meaning, Types, Techniques of Coordination; Controlling – Meaning, Need for Control System, Benefits of Control, Essentials of Effective Control System, Steps in Control Process. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 3

Social Responsibilities of Business: Meaning of Social Responsibility, Social Responsibilities of Business towards Different Groups, Social Audit, Business Ethics and Corporate Governance
Entrepreneurship: Definition of Entrepreneur, Importance of Entrepreneurship, concepts of Entrepreneurship, Characteristics of successful Entrepreneur, Classification of Entrepreneurs, Myths of Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Development models, Entrepreneurial development cycle, Problems faced by Entrepreneurs and capacity building for Entrepreneurship. **10**

Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 4

Modern Small Business Enterprises: Role of Small Scale Industries, Impact of Globalization and WTO on SSIs, Concepts and definitions of SSI Enterprises, Government policy and development of the Small Scale sector in India, Growth and Performance of Small Scale Industries in India, Sickness in SSI sector, Problems for Small Scale Industries, Ancillary Industry and Tiny Industry (Definition only) Institutional Support for Business Enterprises: Introduction, Policies & Schemes of Central Level Institutions, State Level Institutions.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 5

Projects Management: A Project. Search for a Business idea: Introduction, Choosing an Idea, Selection of product, The Adoption process, Product Innovation, Product Planning and Development Strategy, Product Planning and Development Process. Concepts of Projects and Classification: Introduction, Meaning of Projects, Characteristics of a Project, Project Levels, Project Classification, Aspects of a Project, The project Cycle, Features and Phases of Project management, Project Management Processes. Project Identification: Feasibility Report, Project Feasibility Analysis. Project Formulation: Meaning, Steps in Project formulation, Sequential Stages of Project Formulation, Project Evaluation.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Principles of Management – P.C. Tripathi, P.N. Reddy, Tata McGraw Hill.
2. Dynamics of Entrepreneurial Development & Management – Vasant Desai – Himalaya Publishing House
3. Poornima M. Charantimath , —Entrepreneurship Development and Small Business Enterprises, Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd., Licensees of Pearson Education
4. Harold Koontz, Heinz Weihrich, —Essentials of Management: An International, Innovation, and Leadership perspective, T.M.H. Edition, New Delhi
5. Chris Hendrickson and Tung Au, —Project Management for Construction - Fundamentals Concepts for Owners, Engineers, Architects and Builders, Prentice Hall, Pittsburgh.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Robert L. Peurifoy, Clifford J. Schexnayder, Aviad Shapira, Robert Schmitt — Construction Planning, Equipment, and Methods (Civil Engineering), McGraw-Hill Education
2. Harold Koontz, Heinz Weihrich, -Essentials of Management: An International, Innovation, and Leadership perspective, T.M.H. Edition, New Delhi
3. Frank Harris, Ronald McCaffer with Francis Edum Fotwe — Modern Construction Management, Wiley-Blackwell
4. Mike Martin, Roland Schinzinger, -Ethics in Engineering, McGraw-Hill Education
5. Chris Hendrickson and Tung Au — Project Management for Construction - Fundamental Concepts for Owners, Engineers, Architects and Builders, Prentice Hall, Pittsburgh
6. James L. Riggs , David D. Bedworth , Sabah U. Randhawa — Engineering Economics 4 ed. Tata McGraw Hill.
7. S.C. Sharma —Construction Equipments and its management — Khanna Publishers.

V Semester B.Tech
OPTIONAL ELECTIVE II - 2
PRINCIPLES OF ARCHITECTURE

Sub Code : 19SCV542 Hrs/

Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To acquaint the students with fundamental knowledge of space and spatial organization
2. Basic aesthetic principles involved in architectural design
3. Approach to conceptualize and develop architectural design.
4. To analyze the massing and circulation in building.
5. To know the historical development in architecture.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to know the fundamental of space and spatial organization
CO2: Able to understand the aesthetic principles of architectural design
CO3: Able to understand the concept of architectural design a systematic approach
CO4: Able to analyze the massing and circulation in building.
CO5: Able to know the historical development in architecture designs.

MODULE 1

ARCHITECTURE, SPACE AND MASS: Introducing Architecture as a profession and role of an Architect, Definition of architecture- elements of architecture - Concept of space, Articulation of form and space (Primary forms, properties of form, transformation of forms – dimensional transformation, subtractive, additive forms, organization of additive forms), Organization of spaces, sense of enclosure, openings in space defining elements. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 2

AESTHETIC COMPONENTS OF DESIGN: Exploration of the basic principles of design such as Proportion, scale, balance, rhythm, contrast, harmony axis, symmetry, hierarchy, datum; Golden proportion, Theories of scale and proportion, Vitruvian theory, Modular man, Relationship between Art and Design with man, space and environment. To be explained with building examples both historical as well as contemporary. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 3

SPATIAL ORGANISATION AND CIRCULATION: Different types of spatial organizations of masses linear, centralized, radial, clustered, grid Organization illustrations of buildings both historical & contemporary. Building approach, building entrance, Configuration of path, Path space relationship. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 4

DESIGN PROCESS: Integration of aesthetics, function and form - Understanding of formative ideas, organization Concepts, and spatial characteristics. Massing and circulation in design analysis of the following buildings: Falling water house & Guggenheim museum by F. L. Wright - Villa Savoye & Chapel of Notre dame Du Haut by Le Corbusier. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study.

MODULE 5

Case studies of historical and contemporary site and buildings (Study of spatial organization, form, element and art). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Architect: A Candid Guide to the Profession, by Roger K. Lewis
2. Understanding Architecture: Its Elements, History, and Meaning by Leland M. Roth, West View Press Place publication.
3. Francis D. K. Ching, Architecture - Form, Space and Order, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1979 (Canada), 1979.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Roger H. Clark, Michael Pause, Precedents in Architecture, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1996
2. K.W. Smithies, Principles of Design in Architecture, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1981
4. Sam F. Miller, Design Process - A Primer for Architectural & Interior Design, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1995
3. Ernest Burden, Elements of Architectural Design – A Visual Resource, Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1994
4. V.S. Prammar, Design Fundamentals in Architecture, Somaiya Publications, New Delhi, 1973.
5. Vitruvius, Translation: Morris, H. M. (1960). The Ten Books on Architecture.

V Semester B.Tech
OPTIONAL ELECTIVE II - 3
PRINCIPLES OF CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT

Sub Code : 19SCV543

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand the broad principles and concepts of construction management
2. To create awareness of MCM techniques in construction industry
3. Represent various works measurement standards
4. Understand the quality and safety management
5. Estimate the cost and government policies of infrastructure.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Ability to take responsibilities as construction manager
CO2: Application of MCM technique in the real time construction operation
CO3: Knowledge of work measurement application in construction industry
CO4: Able to understand the safety of buildings
CO5: Able to understand the rules and regulations followed in the construction contract.

MODULE 1

Project Scheduling: Construction Scheduling, Work break down structure, activity cost and time estimation in CPM, PERT, RPM (Repetitive Project Modeling) techniques. LOB technique, Mass haul diagrams. Precedence Network Analysis. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 2

Project Controlling: Monitoring and Control, Crashing, Resource Leveling, Updating Construction Quality: Construction quality process, inspection, quality control and quality assurance, cost of quality, ISO standards. Introduction to concept of Total Quality Management.

Teaching Methodology:

10 Hours

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 3

- a) Causes of Accidents on various sites, safety measures and safety policies to be adopted, determination of safety parameters, personal protective equipment. Workmen Compensation Act, Minimumwages act
- b) Type of Industrial Hazards-Nature, Causes And Control Measures, Hazard Identifications And Control Techniques -HAZOP, FMEA, FMECA. -Cost of Construction Injuries-Legal Implications
- c) Safety Organization –Safety Policy, Safety Record Keeping, Safety Culture, Safety and First Line Supervisors, Middle Managers, Top Management Practices, Sub contractual obligation, Project Coordination and Safety Procedure. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 4

Administration of Incentive Schemes a) Necessity, Merit rating, job evaluation, installation, modification and maintaining of incentive schemes based on implementation experience.

b) Introduction to artificial intelligence technique ANN, Fuzzy Logic, Genetic Algorithms

Introduction to BIM.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Demonstration

MODULE 5

Work Study: Definition, Objectives, and basic procedure, and method study and work measurement, Work study applications in Civil Engineering.

Method study –Definition, Objective, Procedure for selecting the work, recording facts, symbols, flow process charts, multiple activity charts, string diagrams.

Work measurement –Time and motion studies, Concept of standard time and various allowances, time study, equipment performance rating. Activity sampling, time-lapse, photography technique, Analytical production studies.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Demonstration

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PART A:

Ten MCQs to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Dr. U.K. Shrivastava — Construction Planning and Management, Galgotia Publications Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
2. Bureau of Indian standards – IS 7272 (Part-1) 1974 : Recommendations for labour output constant for building works.
3. P C Tripathi and P N Reddy, -Principles of Management, Tata McGraw-Hill Education.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Robert L Peurifoy, Clifford J. Schexnayder, Aviad Shapira, Robert Schmitt, — Construction Planning, Equipment, and Methods (Civil Engineering), McGraw-Hill Education
2. Harold Koontz, Heinz Weihrich, -Essentials of Management: An International, Innovation, and Leadership perspective, T.M.H. Edition, New Delhi
3. Frank Harris, Ronald McCaffer with Francis Edum-Fotwe, -Modern Construction Management, Wiley-Blackwell
4. Mike Martin, Roland Schinzinger, -Ethics in Engineering, McGraw-Hill Education
5. Chris Hendrickson and Tung Au, -Project Management for Construction - Fundamentals Concepts for Owners, Engineers, Architects and Builders, Prentice Hall, Pittsburgh.

V Semester B.Tech
OPTIONAL ELECTIVE II - 4

PRINCIPLES OF TOWN PLANNING & URBAN DEVELOPMENT

Sub Code : 19SCV544 Hrs/

Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To remember the basic components for planning of urban areas.
2. To Develop Drawings to develop urban Areas and Townships.
3. Different requirements for urban development.
4. To understand zoning of different sectors for land use.
5. To understand the overall concept of master plan for a town or city.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Basic components required for planning of urban areas.

CO2: Drawings required for Town Planning and development.

CO3: Requirements for Urban Development.

CO4: Able to prepare zoning for land use.

CO5: Able to develop master plan for a town or city.

MODULE 1

TOWN PLANNING: Introduction - evolution of planning, objects, principles and necessity of town planning, growth of towns, requirements of new towns, present position of planning in India, land use planning and neighbourhood planning. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 2

ZONING: Meaning of the term zoning, objectives, principles, importance aspects and advantages of zoning, zoning powers, transition zones.

HOUSING: importance, demand, requirements, low cost housing, slums-causes and effects, clearance of slums, building bye laws. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 3

Development of master plan-objectives, necessity and features of master plan, data collected, drawings prepare, stages of preparation and method of execution of development plan. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 4

Urban Development: Architectural design, development economics, planning & transportation policy, landscape management. Urban development includes neighbourhood analysis, street design, master plan framework, design guidelines, architecture, detailed public space design.

Teaching Methodology:**10 Hours**

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

MODULE 5

Redevelopment concepts: Studies for urban redevelopment strategies, urban parking policies, balance of Gentrification with new development. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case Study

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:**PART A:**

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** fullquestion from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Town Planning by Rangwala, Charotar Publishing House Pvt.Ltd.
2. Building Planning, Designing, and Scheduling, Gurucharan Singh and Jagadish Singh - Standard Publishers, New Delhi.
3. Hutchinson, B.G, _Introduction to Urban System Planning', McGraw Hill.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Town and Country Planning by K.S.Ramegowda.
2. Dicky, J.W., _Metropolitan Transportation Planning', Tata McGraw Hill.
3. Bruton M.J., _Introduction to Transportation Planning', Hutchinson of London.

V Semester B.Tech
OPTIONAL ELECTIVE II - 5
GROUND IMPROVEMENT TECHNIQUES

Sub Code : 19SCV545

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours:50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand the fundamental concepts of ground improvement techniques
2. Apply knowledge of mathematics, Science and Geotechnical Engineering to solve problems in the field of modification of ground required for construction of civil engineering structures.
3. Understand the concepts of chemical compaction, grouting and other miscellaneous methods.
4. Impart the knowledge of geo synthetics, vibration, grouting and Injection.
5. Educate students with numerous ground improvement principles and methods to overcome the problems related to soil on site

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the problematic soil

CO2: Suggest the appropriate ground improvement technique as per the requirement of the project (dewatering, densification, stabilization, swelling control etc.)

CO3: Analyze and design the technique for ground improvement

CO4: Learn how to change the properties of soil to overcome these problems by modifying the soil and by suitable interventions with the soil.

CO5: Able to understand the types of grouts, equipment's and machinery.

MODULE 1

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GROUND: Introduction, Formation of Rock, soil and soil profile, Soil distribution in India, Alterations of ground after formation, Reclaimed soils, Natural offshore deposits; Ground Improvement Potential – Hazardous ground conditions, poor ground conditions, favorable ground conditions, Alternative Approaches, Geotechnical processes.

COMPACTION: Introduction, compaction mechanics, Field procedure, surface compaction, Dynamic Compaction, selection of field compaction procedures, compaction quality control.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 2

DRAINAGE METHODS: Introduction, Seepage, filter requirements, ground water and seepage control, methods of dewatering systems, Design of dewatering system including pipe line effects of dewatering. Drains, different types of drains.

PRECOMPRESSION AND VERTICAL DRAINS: Importance, Vertical drains, Sand drains, Drainage of slopes, Electro kinetic dewatering, Preloading.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-I: Definition, cement stabilization, sandwich technique, admixtures. Hydration – effect of cement stabilization on permeability, Swelling and shrinkage and strength and deformation characteristics. Criteria for cement stabilization. Stabilization using Fly ash.

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-II: Lime stabilization – suitability, process, criteria for lime stabilization. Other chemicals like chlorides, hydroxides, lignin and hydrofluoric acid. Properties of chemical components, reactions and effects. Bitumen, tar or asphalt in stabilization. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 4

VIBRATION METHODS: Introduction, Vibro compaction– blasting, vibratory probe, Vibro displacement compaction – displacement piles, vibro flotation, sand compaction piles, stone columns, heavy tamping **GROUTING AND INJECTION:** Introduction, Effect of grouting. Chemicals and materials used. Types of grouting. Grouting procedure, Applications of grouting.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

GEOSYNTHETICS: Introduction, Geosynthetic types, properties of Geosynthetics – materials and fibre properties, Geometrical aspects, mechanical properties, Hydraulic properties, Durability; Applications of Geosynthetics - Separation, Filtration and Fluid Transmission, Reinforcement,

MISCELLANEOUS METHODS (ONLY CONCEPTS & USES): Soil reinforcement, Thermal methods, Ground improvement by confinement – Crib walls, Gabions and Mattresses, Anchors, Rock bolts and soil nailing. Stone Column, Micro piles. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Ground Improvement Techniques-** Purushothama Raj P. (1999) Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. **Construction and Geotechnical Method in Foundation Engineering-** Koerner R.M. (1985) - Mc Graw Hill Pub. Co., New York.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Engineering principles of ground modification-** Manfred Hausmann (1990) - McGraw Hill Pub. Co., New York.
2. **Methods of treatment of unstable ground-** Bell, F.G. (1975) Butterworths, London.
3. **Expansive soils-** Nelson J.D. and Miller D.J. (1992) – John Wiley and Sons.
4. **Soil Stabilization; Principles and Practice-** Ingles. C.G. and Metcalf J.B. (1972) - Butterworths, London.

V Semester B.Tech
CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY LABORATORY

Sub Code : 19SCVL55

Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T

Credits : 2

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 3

Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Ability to function on multi-disciplinary teams in the area of materials testing.
2. Ability to use the techniques and skills necessary for selecting suitable structural materials.
3. Understanding of professional and ethical responsibility in the areas of material testing.
4. Ability to communicate effectively the different properties of materials.
5. To understand different types of tests performed for construction materials.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Suitable materials for buildings and adopt suitable construction techniques.
- CO2:** Mix Design of Concrete works as per Indian Standard.
- CO3:** Identify, formulate and solve engineering problems of elements subjected to flexure.
- CO4:** Evaluate the impact of engineering solutions on the society and also will be aware of contemporary issues regarding failure of structures due to unsuitable materials.
- CO5:** To conduct different tests for construction materials.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Bricks–Test on Table Remolded Bricks
2. Blocks –Testing Hollow Concrete Blocks
3. Strength tests on
 - Roofing
 - Interlocking pavement blocks,
4. Strength tests on
 - Mosaic tiles
 - Ceramic tiles
 - Vitrified tiles
5. Mortar: Flow table test of mortar,
6. Compressive strength of mortar cubes
7. Mix Proportioning of Concrete using IS-10262
8. Concreting: Batching mixing and placing concrete
9. NDT of Concrete Specimen-Rebound Hammer & Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test 10.Bar bending: Straightening, bending, hooking demo for slab, beam and column construction, Lapping.

Scheme of Examination:

- ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks
- ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks
- Viva – voce = 10 marks
- Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. A.J. Fenner-Mechanical testing of materials George newness Ltd., -1965
2. MOHAN RAJ AND JAI SINGH, -Advanced Building Materials and Constructionll, CBRI Publications, Roorkee.
3. B.C. PUNMIA, -Building Constructionll, Lakshmi Publications, New Delhi

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Relevant IS Codes, EFNARC code and IRC Codes
2. Highway Material Testing Laboratory Manual –New Chand and Bros.
3. M.S. Shetty, Concrete Technology -Theory and Practice Published by S. Chand and Company, NewDelhi. M.L. Gambhir –Concrete Manual –Dhanpat Rai and sons New –Delhi.

V Semester B.Tech

CIVIL CAD LABORATORY

Sub Code : 19SCVL56
Hrs/ Week : 2L + 1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the basics of principles adopted in drawing
2. To use the computer to apply numerical techniques
3. To learn the fundamentals of Computer Aided Drafting
4. To understand Civil Engineering Drawing concepts
5. To learn the bye laws adopted in structural drawing

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to know the basic tools and shortcut commands used
CO2: Able to know the architectural concepts
CO3: Able to implement Computer Aided Drafting
CO4: Able to apply Building concepts to Civil Engineering
CO5: Able to know the bye laws adopted in Civil Engineering Drawing

1. AUTOCAD

Basics of AUTOCAD:

DRAWING TOOLS: Lines, Circle, Arc, Polyline, Multiline, Polygon, Rectangle, Spline, Ellipse, *Modify tools:* Erase, Copy, Mirror, Offset, Array, Move, Rotate, Scale, Stretch, Lengthen, Trim, Extend, Break, Chamfer and Fillet, *Using Text:* Single line text, Multiline text, Spelling, Edit text, Special Features: View tools, Layers concept, Dimension tools, Hatching, Customising toolbars, working with multiple drawings. **6 Hours**

Use of AUTOCAD in Civil Engineering Drawings:

Following drawings are to be prepared for the data given using AUTOCAD

- i) Cross section of Foundation - masonry wall, RCC columns (isolated)
- ii) Different types of staircases
- iii) Lintel and chajja
- iv) RCC slabs and beams
- v) Drawing of Plan, elevation and sectional elevation of single storied residential and public buildings given the single line diagram and preparing excavation plan.

36 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Computer Aided Design Laborator-** Dr M.N.Shesha Prakash,Dr.G.S.Suresh, Lakshmi Publications
2. **CAD Laboratory-** M.A.Jayaram, D.S.Rajendra Prasad- SapnaPublications
3. **AUTOCAD 2002-** Roberts JT, -BPB publications
4. **AUTOCAD 2004-** Sham Tickoo, A beginner's Guide, WileyDreamtech India Pvt Ltd.,
5. **Learning Excel 2002-** Ramesh Bangia, -Khanna Book PublishingCo (P) Ltd.,
6. **Microsoft Excel-** Mathieson SA, Starfire publishers

V Semester B. Tech

GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING

LABORATORY

Sub Code : 19SCVL57
Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To estimate the engineering properties of the soils by density test, CBR test permeability test and consolidation test.
2. To estimate shear strength of soils by direct shear test, triaxial shear test, vane shear test & unconfined compressive test.
3. To analyse the properties of soil
4. To categorize soil based on its properties
5. To choose suitable soil for construction activities.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand Compaction and consolidation behavior of soil.

CO2: Perform and analyze the coefficient of permeability of soil.

CO3: Evaluate shear strength parameters of soil.

CO4: Able to select suitable soil for foundation design

CO5: Able to categorize soil based on its properties and strength parameters.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Standard Proctor Compaction Test (IS light compaction test).
2. Coefficient of permeability by constant head and variable head methods.
3. Strength Tests
 - a. Unconfined Compression Test
 - b. Direct Shear Test
 - c. Laboratory vane shear test
4. One Dimensional Consolidation Test.
5. Determination of California Bearing resistance.
6. Demonstration tests:
 - a. Miscellaneous equipment's such as Augers, Samplers, and Rapid Moisture meter, Proctor's needle.
 - b. Hydrometer Test.
 - c. Free Swell Index and Swell Pressure Test

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks
Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Goodman – Introduction to Rock mechanics, Willey International (1980).
2. Ramamurthy, T. – Engineering in Rocks for slopes, foundations, and tunnels, Prentice Hall India (2007).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Jaeger, J. C. and Cook, N. G. W. – Fundamentals of Rock Mechanics, Chapman and Hall, London.(1979)
2. Hoek, E. and Brown, E. T. – Underground Excavation in Rock, Institution of Mining and Metallurgy, 1982.
3. Brady, B. H. G. and Brown, E. T. – Rock Mechanics for Underground Mining, Chapman & Hall, 1993.

V Semester B.Tech

MOOC

Subject Code	19SCV58	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- To improve learnability
- Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- Skill development
- Industry readiness
- Increased confidence level

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

- CO1: Improve learnability
- CO2: Acquire additional knowledge in the field of study
- CO3: Develop the skill
- CO4: Industry ready
- CO5: Have more confidence level

About the Course:

- A common Online MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is offered in Blended mode.
- The MOOC Coordinator will recommend a department specific common course in MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA to all the students of the batch.
- The assessment will be taken by the MOOC Coordinator for 25 Marks at the end of the Course and the remaining 25 marks will be awarded for the Course Completion.
- The student must attend all continuous assessment taken by the MOOC/COURSERA Course Faculty.

Assessment Method for MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course:

- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course has to recommend a common course for the students to register the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for a Specific Title.
- The Students have to take all continuous assessment as recommended by the Course Faculty in the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course for the internal assessment of 25 Marks.
- The Department Faculty Coordinator for the MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Course is responsible to conduct Assessment (MCQs) for 25 Marks in the Internal Assessment of 50 Marks.

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Weightage	Marks
1	Continuous Assessment taken by the MOOC/Coursera Course Faculty	50	25
2	MOOC/SWAYAM/COURSERA Faculty Coordinator has to Conduct Assessment (MCQs & Assignments)	50	25
Total			50

PART-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 3

Subject Code	19SQA59	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives: This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART – A

Sentence completion - a. Using sentence clues. b. Using Hints.c. Structure Words.d. Visualize. e. Pro-active thinking. f. Reactive thinking (signpost words, root words, prefix suffix, sentence structure clues).g. Structure Words. h. Elimination.i. Working Backwards.

Verbal classification - a. Familiarity. b. Systematic approach.c. Logical thinking. d. Elimination. e. Practice makes perfect.

Time, Speed and Distance - a. Basics of time, speed and distance b. Relative speed c. Problems based on trains d. Problems based on boats and streams e. Problems based on races.

Average, Problems on Ages Profit and Loss, Discount' - a. concept of Average b. Weighted Average c. Problems on Ages(based on average) d. Problems on ages (based on Ratio) e. Concept and Problem solving technique in Profit and Loss f. Successive Discount.

Syllogism and Venn diagrams, Blood Relations - a. Syllogisms b. Venn Diagrams – Interpretation c. Venn Diagrams – Solving d. Basic concept and terminology in Blood Relations e. Option Elimination method in Blood Relation.

Logarithms, Algebra - a. Logarithm concept and problem solving technique b. Different types of Algebraic expressions c. Different types of Algebraic equations.

Verbal reasoning - a. Reading techniques. b. Removing assumptions.c. Managing time. d. Honing analytical skills. e. Practicing the right format. f. Learning from mistakes.

Spotting errors - a. Subject Verb Agreement.b. Right usage of Participles and Infinitives.
c. Right usage of Verbs.d. Right usage of Adjectives. e. Checking spelling and punctuation errors.

PART - B

Highway and Traffic engineering

Design of RCC structures

Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering

Bridge, Railways, Airport Engineering

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	19SQA59	IA Marks	-
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method: Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

VI Semester B.Tech

ADVANCED DESIGN OF RC STRUCTURES

Sub Code :	19SCV61	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	4	Exam Marks :	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the stress strain behavior of steel and concrete
2. To understand the concept of working stress and limit state methods
3. To gain the knowledge of limit state design for flexure, shear, torsion, bond and anchorage
4. To understand the behavior of columns subjected to eccentric load and use of interaction diagrams
5. To study the design of various foundation

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Able to describe about composition and characteristics of Portland cement.
- CO2:** Able to classify the aggregate and their various properties.
- CO3:** Able to identify the various properties of concrete and analyzing its workability.
- CO4:** Able to illustrate design philosophies.
- CO5:** Able to solve problems in context to singly, doubly and flanged Beam.

MODULE 1

1. Layout Drawing: General layout of building showing, position of columns, footings, beams and slabs with standard notations.
2. Detailing of Beam and Slab floor system, continuous beams.
3. Detailing of Staircases: Dog legged and Open well.
4. Detailing of Column footings: Column and footing (Square and Rectangle)

25 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visit

MODULE 2

1. Design and detailing of Rectangular Combined footing slab and beam type
2. Design and detailing of Retaining walls (Cantilever and counter fort type)
3. Design and detailing of Simple Portal Frames subjected to gravity loads. (Single bay & Single storey)

25 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visit

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module I	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	5 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **TWO** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module

20 Marks x 02 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Structural Design & Drawing Reinforced Concrete & Steel**- N. Krishnaraju, University Press.
2. **Structural Design and Drawing**- Krishnamurthy -, (Concrete Structures), CBS publishers, New Delhi. Tata Mc-Graw publishers.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Reinforced Concrete Structures** - B.C. Punmia – Laxmi Publishing Co.
2. **Reinforced Concrete Design** – S.N.Sinha, Mc Graw Hill Education,

ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 19SCV62
Hours per week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To Understand Quality Aspects of the water
- Gain Knowledge about Water Treatment Methods
- Understands the Criteria for the sewer Design
- Understands methods of Disposal of effluents
- Knowledge of Process of Treatment of waste water

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understands the Importance of Quality Aspects of water

CO2: Understands design Criteria of sewer and Sewerage treatment plant

CO3: Evaluate degree of treatment and type of treatment for disposal, reuse and recycle.

CO4: Manage sewage and industrial effluent issues.

CO5: Analyse and Evaluate different treatment processes for waste water.

MODULE 1

QUALITY OF WATER: Objectives of water quality management. Wholesomeness & palatability, water borne diseases. Water quality parameters – Physical, chemical and Microbiological. Sampling of water for examination. Water quality analysis (IS: 3025 and IS: 1622) using analytical and instrumental techniques. Drinking water standards BIS & WHO guidelines. Health significance of Fluoride, Nitrates and heavy metals like Mercury, Cadmium, Arsenic etc. and toxic / trace organics.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 2

WATER TREATMENT

SEDIMENTATION: Theory, settling tanks, types, design. Coagulant aided sedimentation, jar test, chemical feeding, flash mixing, and Clariflocculator.

FILTRATION: Mechanism – theory of filtration, types of filters, slow sand, rapid sand and pressure filters including construction, operation, cleaning and their design – excluding under drainage system – back washing of filters. Operational problems in filters.

DISINFECTION: Theory of disinfection, types of disinfection, Chlorination, chlorine demand, residual chlorine, use of bleaching powder. UV irradiation treatment – treatment of swimming pool water

SOFTENING – definition, methods of removal of hardness by lime soda process and zeolite process RO & Membrane technique.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

WASTE WATER DISPOSAL & DESIGN OF SEWERS: Necessity for sanitation, methods of domestic waste water disposal, types of sewerage systems and their suitability. Dry weather flow, factors affecting dry weather flow, flow variations and their effects on design of sewerage system; computation of design flow, estimation of storm flow, rational method and empirical formulae of design of storm water drain. Time of concentration.

DESIGN OF SEWERS: Hydraulic formulae for velocity, effects of flow variations on velocity, self-cleansing and non-scouring velocities, Design of hydraulic elements for circular sewers flowing full and flowing partially full (No derivations).

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 4

SEWER MATERIALS AND APPURTENANCES: Sewer materials, shapes of sewers, laying of sewers, joints and testing of sewers, ventilation and cleaning of sewers. Catch basins, manholes, flushing tanks, oil and grease traps, Drainage traps. Basic principles of house drainage. Typical layout plan showing house drainage connections, maintenance of house drainage.

WASTE WATER CHARACTERIZATION: Sampling, significance, techniques and frequency. Physical, Chemical and Biological characteristics, Aerobic and Anaerobic activity, CNS cycles. BOD and COD. Their significance & problems

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

DISPOSAL OF EFFLUENTS & TREATMENT OF WASTE WATER: Disposal of Effluents by dilution, self-purification phenomenon. Oxygen sag curve, Zones of purification, Sewage farming, sewage sickness, Effluent Disposal standards for land, surface water & ocean. Flow diagram of municipal waste water treatment plant. Preliminary & Primary treatment: Screening, grit chambers, skimming tanks, primary sedimentation tanks – Design criteria

SECONDARY TREATMENT: Suspended growth and fixed film bioprocess. Trickling filter – theory and operation, types and designs. Activated sludge process- Principle and flow diagram, Modifications of ASP, F/M ratio. Anaerobic Sludge digestion, Sludge digestion tanks, Low cost waste treatment method. Septic tank, Oxidation Pond and Oxidation ditches. Reuse and recycle of waste water.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module,

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Water supply Engineering –S.K.Garg, Khanna Publishers
2. Environmental Engineering I –B C Punima and Ashok Jain
3. Manual on Water supply and treatment –CPHEEO, Ministry of Urban Development, New Delhi

REFERENCES

1. Hammer, M.J., (1986), Water and Wastewater Technology –SI Version, 2nd Edition, John Wiley and Sons.
2. Karia, G.L., and Christian, R.A., (2006), Wastewater Treatment – Concepts and Design Approach, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Metcalf and Eddy, (2003), Wastewater Engineering, Treatment and Reuse, 4th Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd.
4. Peavy, H.S., Rowe, D.R., and Tchobanoglous, G., (1986), Environmental Engineering –Mc Graw Hill Book Co.
5. Raju, B.S.N., (1995), Water Supply and Wastewater Engineering, Tata McGraw Hill Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
6. Sincero, A.P., and Sincero, G.A., (1999), Environmental Engineering – A Design Approach –Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
7. Water and Wastewater Engineering Vol-II: - Fair, Geyer and Okun: John Willey Publishers, New York.

**VI Semester B.Tech CORE ELECTIVE 2 - I
TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING**

Sub Code : 19SCV631
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the importance of transportation, road characteristics, highway development and planning.
2. To study the geometric design of highways, highway alignment and surveys to be carried out.
3. To study the basics and design of various components of railway engineering, types and functions of track, junctions and railway stations.
4. To learn about the aircraft characteristics, planning and design of components of airport.
5. To study the importance of tunneling, types of tunnels, drilling, types and components of docks, harbours, various urban transportation systems and Intelligent Transportation Systems.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** To understand the principles of transportation engineering, need, characteristics, operations, planning and schemes provided by State & Central Govt.
- CO2:** Able to collect and analyze the information required for the highway planning and design of highway construction.
- CO3:** Able to carry out the surveys for railways, design of sleepers-ballast-points-crossings.
- CO4:** Able to select suitable site for the airport, to prepare plan and layout of different types of terminals.
- CO5:** Able to select suitable location for the construction of harbour-docks-tunnel, to select appropriate drilling pattern for tunneling, able to demonstrate the fundamentals of Intelligent Transportation Systems.

MODULE 1

PRINCIPLES OF TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING:

Importance of transportation, Different modes of transportation and comparison, Characteristics of road transport, Jayakar committee recommendations and implementation – Central Road Fund, Indian Roads Congress, Central Road Research Institute.

HIGHWAY DEVELOPMENT AND PLANNING: Road types and classification, Road patterns, Planning surveys, Saturation system of road planning, Phasing Road Development in India, Salient Features of 3rd and 4th Twenty Year Road Development Plans, Present scenario of road development in India (NHDP & PMGSY) and in Karnataka (KSHIP & KRDCIL) Road development plan - vision 2021.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration.

MODULE 2

HIGHWAY ALIGNMENT AND SURVEYS: Ideal Alignment, Factors affecting the alignment, Engineering Surveys-Map study, Reconnaissance, Preliminary and Final location & detailed survey.

HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN: Importance, Terrain classification, Design speed, Factors affecting geometric design, Cross sectional elements-Camber- width of pavement- Shoulders, Width of formation- Right of way, typical cross sections.

Sight Distance-Restrictions to sight distance- Stopping sight distance-Overtaking sight distance-overtaking zones- Examples on SSD and OSD- Sight distance at intersections, **Horizontal alignment**- Radius of Curve- Super elevation – Extra widening. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

INTRODUCTION: Role of railways in transportation, Indian Railways, Selection of Routes, Permanent way and its requirements, Gauges and types, Typical cross sections-single and double line B G track in cutting, embankment and electrified tracks, Coning of wheels and tilting of rails, **Rails**- Functions-requirements—types and sections length-defects-wear-creep.

SLEEPERS AND BALLAST: Functions, requirements, Types, Track fitting and fasteners- Dog spike, screw spike and Pandrol clip, Fish plates, Bearing plates, **Tractive resistance** and hauling capacity.

POINTS AND CROSSING: Components of a turnout, Details of Points and Crossing, types of switches, Track junctions, Stations and Types, Signaling-Objects and types of signals, Station, Turn table, Fouling mark, level crossing. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 4

INTRODUCTION: Layout of an airport with component parts and functions, Site selection for airport, Aircraft characteristics affecting the design and planning of airport, Airport classification, Runway orientation using wind rose with examples

RUNWAY- Basic runway length-Corrections and examples, Runway geometrics, **Taxiway-** Factors affecting the layout - geometrics of taxiway-Design of exit taxiway with examples, **Visual aids-** Airport marking – lighting-Instrumental Landing System.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

TUNNELS: Advantages and disadvantages, Size and shape of tunnels, Surveying-Transferring centre line, and gradient from surface to inside the tunnel working face, Tunneling in rocks- methods, Tunneling methods in soils-Needle beam, Liner plate, Tunnel lining, Tunnel ventilation, vertical shafts, Pilot tunneling, mucking and methods, drilling and drilling pattern.

HARBOURS: Harbour classifications, Layout with components, Natural phenomenon affecting the design of harbours - wind, wave and tide, currents, Breakwater, Wharf and Quays, Jetties and Piers, Dry dock and wet docks, Slipways, Navigational Aids (Intelligent Transportation Systems). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Highway Engineering – S K Khanna and C E G Justo, Nem Chand Bros, Roorkee
2. Highway Engineering - L R Kadiyali, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi
3. Transportation Engineering – K P Subramaniam, Scitech Publications, Chennai
4. Transportation Engineering – James H Banks, Mc.Graw. Hill Pub. New Delhi
5. Highway Engineering –R. Sreenivasa Kumar, University Press. Pvt. Ltd. Hyderabad
6. Railway Engineering - Saxena and Arora, Dhanpat Rai & Sons, New Delhi
7. Indian Railway Track – M M Agarwal, Jaico Publications, Bombay
8. Airport Planning and Design – Khanna Arora and Jain, Nem Chand Bros, Roorkee
9. Docks and Tunnel Engineering – R Srinivasan, Charaotar Publishing House
10. Docks and Harbour Engineering –H P Oza and G H Oza Charaotar Publishing House.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Relevant IRC Codes
2. Specifications & Guidelines for Roads and Bridges-MORTH, IRC, New Delhi
3. Specifications & Guidelines – Ministry of Railways
4. Specifications & Guidelines – Ministry of Civil Aviation and DGCA.
5. Specifications & Guidelines – Ministry of Shipping and National Maritime Foundation.

VI Semester B.Tech
CORE ELECTIVE 2 - III
HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN

Sub Code : 19SCV632
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Develop an understanding of the principles of geometric design in the context of transportation planning and traffic design.
2. To focus on environmental factors, aesthetics and adaptation to surroundings.
3. Apply basic science principles in estimating stopping and passing sight distance requirements.
4. Understand the design criteria for geometric design of highways.
5. Design basic horizontal and vertical alignment of the highway.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Learn concepts and characteristic for pavement design and cross sectional elements.

CO2: Apply standards, guidelines, and practiced knowledge to perform designs.

CO3: Assess the environmental impacts of location and design of roads

CO4: Prepare detailed plans for such infrastructure elements.

CO5: Understand the road building process within the context of laws and regulations.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Geometric Control factors like Topography – design speed – design vehicle – Traffic – Capacity – volume – environment and other factors as per IRC and AASHTO standards and specifications - PCU concept – factors controlling PCU for different design purpose.

CROSS SECTIONAL ELEMENTS: Pavement surface characteristics – friction – skid resistance – pavement unevenness - light reflecting characteristics – camber – objectives – types of camber – methods of providing cambers in the field – problems – carriage way – kerb – median – shoulder – foot path – parking lanes – service roads – cycle tracks – Driveways – Right of way – Factors influencing right of way – Design of Road humps as per latest IRC provisions. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 2

SIGHT DISTANCE: Importance, types, Side distance at uncontrolled intersection, derivation, factors affecting side distance, IRC, AASHTO standards, problems on above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

HORIZONTAL ALIGNMENT: Definition, Checking the stability of vehicle, while moving on horizontal curve, Super elevation, Ruling minimum and maximum radius, Assumptions problems – method of providing super elevation for different curves – Extra widening of pavement on curves – objectives – Mechanical widening – psychological widening – Transition curve – objectives – Ideal requirements – Types of transition curve – Method of evaluating length of transition curve – Setting the transition curve in the field, set back distance on horizontal curve. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 4

VERTICAL ALIGNMENT: Gradient – Types of gradient – Design criteria of summit and valley curve – Design of vertical curves based on SSD – OSD– Night visibility considerations - Design standards for hilly roads – problems on the above.

INTERSECTION DESIGN: Principle – At grade and Grade separated junctions – Types – channelization – Features of channelizing Island – median opening – Gap in median at junction. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

ROTARY INTERSECTION: Elements – Advantages – Disadvantages – Design guide lines – problem on the above – Grade separated intersection – Three legged inter section – Diamond inter change – Half clover leaf – cloverleaf- Advantages- Disadvantages only.

HIGHWAY DRAINAGE: Importance – sub surface drainage – surface drainage – Design of road side drives – Hydrological – Hydraulically considerations and design of filter media, problems on above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Principle and practice of Highway Engineering-** L R KADIYALI& N B LAL: Khanna publications
2. **Highway Engineering** – Khanna S K & Justo, Nemchand & Bros.
3. **Highway Engineering** by Srinivas Kumar.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Highway Engineering-** Kadiyali L R: Khanna publications
2. **Relevant IRC** Publications
3. **Transportation Engineering and Planning-** Papa Coastas and Prevendors PHI, New Delhi.

**CORE ELECTIVE 2 - IV
URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING**

Sub Code : 19SCV633

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To know about the process and concepts of transportation planning
2. To study about zoning, types of surveys and inventory facilities
3. To study about trip generation and trip distribution
4. To study about modal split analysis and trip assignment
5. To study about urban transport planning for Indian cities, Metro, MRTS, BRTS.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Apply the principles of the transportation planning process and estimation of demand for transportation

CO2: Organise and Analyse the Survey, Zoning of study area

CO3: Analyze the trip production and trip attraction models, growth factor, gravity and opportunity models

CO4: Apply the mode choice behavior and mode split models, Traffic Forecasting

CO5: Analyse the challenges and apply the urban transportation planning for Indian cities.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Scope of Urban transportation and planning, Urban class groups, Impact of urban transportation, Inter dependency of land use and traffic – System Approach to urban planning - Modeling Techniques in Planning Stage.

STAGES IN URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING: Trip generation – Trip production - Trip distribution – Modal split – Trip assignment. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 2

URBAN TRANSPORT SURVEY - Definition of study area, Organisation of Survey, Zoning-Types of Surveys – Inventory of transportation facilities. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

TRIP GENERATION: Trip purpose – Factors governing trip generation and attraction – Category analysis – Problems on above

TRIP DISTRIBUTION: Methods – Growth factors methods – Synthetic methods – Fractorand Furness method and problems on the above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration.

MODULE 4

MODAL SPLIT: Factors affecting – characteristics of split – Model split in urban transport planning.

TRIP ASSIGNMENT: Assignment Techniques – Traffic forecasting –Land use transport models – Lowry Model – Garin Lowry model –Applications in India – (No problems on the above). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration.

MODULE 5

URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING FOR INDIAN CITIES: Introduction – Difficulties in transport planning – Metro Rail – Mass Rapid Transportation System, Bus Rapid Transit System - Intelligent Transport System - Recent Case Studies. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of theModule 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Traffic Engineering and Transport Planning-** L.R. Kadiyali -Khanna Publishers.
2. **Principles of urban transport system planning** - B.G. Hutchinson- Scripta Book Co., Washington D.C. & McGraw Hill Book Co.
3. **Introduction to transportation engineering-** JotinKristey and Kentlal - PHI, New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Urban Transport planning-** Black John - Croom Helm ltd, London.
2. **Urban and Regional models in geography and planning-**Hutchison B G - John Wiley and sons London.
3. **Entropy in urban and regional modeling-** Wilson A G - Pion ltd, London.

CORE ELECTIVE 2 - V
REINFORCED EARTH STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 19SCV634

IA Marks : 50

Hrs/ Week : 4

Exam Hours : 2

Credits : 4

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Identify, formulate reinforced earth techniques that are suitable for different soils and in different structures;
- Understand the laboratory testing concepts of Geosynthetics
- Design RE retaining structures and Soil Nailing concepts
- Determine the load carrying capacity of Foundations resting on RE soil bed.
- Assess the use of Geosynthetics in drainage requirements and landfill designs

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Engineering knowledge in the Earth Reinforcement

CO2: Understand the Application of the Earth Reinforcement

CO3: Analysis and Design of the reinforced Structures

CO4: Know the Other Applications of the Geosynthetics

CO5: Understand the use of geosynthetics in filters

MODULE 1

Basics of Reinforced Earth Construction:

Geosynthetics and Their Functions:

Historical developments, Recent developments, manufacturing process woven & non-woven, Raw materials – Classification based on materials type – Metallic and Non-metallic, Natural and Man-made, Geosynthetics.

Properties and Tests on Materials Properties –

Physical, Chemical, Mechanical, Hydraulic, Endurance and Degradation requirements, Testing & Evaluation of properties.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 2

Design of Reinforced Earth Retaining Walls:

Concept of Reinforced earth retaining wall, Internal and external stability, Selection of materials, Typical design problems.

Soil Nailing Techniques:

Concept, Advantages & limitations of soil nailing techniques, comparison of soil nailing with reinforced soil, methods of soil nailing, Construction sequence, Components of system, Design aspects and precautions to be taken. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

Design of Reinforced Earth Foundations:

Modes of failure of foundation, Determination of force induced in reinforcement ties – Location of failure surface, tension failure and pull out resistance, length of tie and its curtailment, bearing capacity improvement in soft soils, General guidelines. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration.

MODULE 4

Geosynthetics for Roads and Slopes:

Roads - Applications to Temporary and Permanent roads, Role of Geosynthetic in enhancing properties of road, control of mud pumping, Enhancing properties of subgrade, Design requirements Slopes – Causes for slope failure, Improvement of slope stability with Geosynthetic, Drainage requirements, Construction technique. Simple Numerical Stability Checking Problems on Reinforced Slopes. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 5

Geosynthetics- Filter, Drain and Landfills

Filter & Drain – Conventional granular filter design criteria, Geosynthetic filter design requirements, Drain and filter properties, Design criteria – soil retention, Geosynthetic permeability, anti-clogging, survivability and durability (No Numerical Problems) Landfills – Typical design of Landfills – Landfill liner & cover, EPA Guidelines, Barrier walls for existing landfills and abandoned dumps (No Numerical Problems). **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Koerner. R.M, -Design with Geosynthetics, Prince Hall Publications
2. Koerner. R.M. & Wesh, J.P, -Construction and Geotechnical Engineering using synthetic fabrics, Wiley Inter Science, New York, Sivakumar Babu G. L., -An introduction to Soil Reinforcement and Geosynthetics, Universities Press, Hyderabad
3. Swami Saran, -Reinforced Soil and its Engineering Applications, I. K. International Pvt.Ltd, New Delhi
4. Venkattappa Rao, G., & Suryanarayana Raju., G. V.S, -Engineering with Geosynthetics, Tata McGraw Hill publishing Company Limited., New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Jones, -Earth reinforcement and Soil structure, CJEP Butterworths, London
2. Ingold, T.S. & Millar, K.S, -Geotextile Hand Book, Thomas, Telford, London.
3. Hidetoshi Octial, Shigenori Hayshi & Jen Otani, -Earth Reinforcement Practices, Vol. I,
4. A.A. Balkema, Rotterdam
5. Bell F.G, -Ground Engineer's reference Book, Butterworths, London
6. Ingold, T.S, -Reinforced Earth, Thomas, Telford, London.
7. Sarsby R W- Editor, -Geosynthetics in Civil Engineering, Woodhead Publishing Ltd & CRC Press, 2007

OPEN ELECTIVE 1-I
OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH & SAFETY IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

Sub Code : 19SCV641
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Students will be able to recognize and evaluate occupational safety and health hazards in the workplace
2. Determine appropriate hazard controls following the hierarchy of controls.
3. Able to analyze the effects of workplace exposures, injuries and illnesses, fatalities
4. Methods to prevent incidents using the hierarchy of controls,
5. Effective safety and health management systems and task oriented training.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Evaluate workplace to determine the existence of occupational safety and health hazards

CO2: Identify relevant regulatory and national consensus standards along with best practices that are applicable.

CO3: Select appropriate control methodologies based on the hierarchy of controls.

CO4: Analyze injury and illness data for trends.

CO5: Able to know the importance of different policies and labor act.

MODULE 1

Occupational Hazard and Control Principles: Safety, History and development, National Safety Policy. Occupational safety and Health Act (OSHA), Occupational Health and Safety administration - Laws governing OSHA and right to know. Accident – causation, investigation, investigation plan, Methods of acquiring accident facts, Supervisory role in accident investigation

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 2

Ergonomics at Work Place: Ergonomics Task analysis, Preventing Ergonomic Hazards, Work space Envelops, Visual Ergonomics, Ergonomic Standards, and Ergonomic Programs. Hazard cognition and Analysis, Human Error Analysis – Fault Tree Analysis – Emergency Response - Decision for action – purpose and considerations.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Site visits.

MODULE 3

Fire Prevention and Protection: Fire Triangle, Fire Development and its severity, Effect of Enclosures, early detection of Fire, Classification of fire and Fire Extinguishers. Electrical Safety, Product Safety: Technical Requirements of Product safety

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 4

Health Considerations at Work Place: Types of diseases and their spread, Health Emergency. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) – types and advantages, effects of exposure and treatment for engineering industries, municipal solid waste. Environment management plans (EMP) for safety and sustainability. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 5

Occupational Health and Safety Considerations: Water and wastewater treatment plants, handling of chemical and safety measures in water and wastewater treatment plants and labs, Construction material manufacturing industries like cement plants, RMC Plants, precast plants and construction sites. Policies, roles and responsibilities of workers, managers and supervisors. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of theModule 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

08 Marks x 05 Question = **40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Goetsch D.L., (1999), -Occupational Safety and Health for Technologists, Engineers and Managers, Prentice Hall.
2. Heinrich H.W., (2007), -Industrial Accident Prevention - A Scientific Approach, McGraw-Hill Book Company National Safety Council and Associate (Data) Publishers Pvt. Ltd., (1991).
3. Industrial Safety and Pollution Control Handbook

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Colling D.A., (1990), -Industrial Safety Management and Technology, Prentice Hall, New Delhi.
2. Della D.E., and Giustina, (1996), -Safety and Environmental Management, Van Nostrand Reinhold International Thomson Publishing Inc.

OPEN ELECTIVE 1- II
AIR POLLUTION & CONTROL

Sub Code : 19SCV642
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To take up the basic concepts of air pollution.
2. To introduce students to basic concepts of pollution.
3. The contents involved the knowledge of causes of air pollution.
4. The contents involved the knowledge of health related to air pollution.
5. To develop skills relevant to control of air pollution.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Concepts of air pollution.
CO2: To estimate the quantity of air pollutant in the environment.
CO3: Be able to develop control technologies.
CO4: Able to understand the location of industrial plants to reduce pollution
CO5: Able to impart the knowledge of global warming and environmental policies

MODULE 1

Introduction: Definition, Sources, classification and characterization of air pollutants. Effects of air pollution on health, vegetation & materials. Types of inversion, photochemical smog.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 2

Meteorology: Temperature lapse rate & stability, wind velocity & turbulence, plume behavior, measurement of meteorological variables, wind rose diagrams, Plume Rise, estimation of effective stack height and mixing depths. Development of air quality models-Gaussian dispersion model.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 3

Sampling: Sampling of particulate and gaseous pollutants (Stack, Ambient & indoor air pollution), Monitoring and analysis of air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SOX, NOX, CO, NH₃)

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 4

Control Techniques: Particulate matter and gaseous pollutants- settling chambers, cyclone separators, scrubbers, filters & ESP. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

MODULE 5

Air pollution due to automobiles, standards and control methods. Noise pollution causes, effects and control, noise standards. Environmental issues, global episodes, laws, acts, protocols. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video Demonstration, Case Study.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/Cost Estimation/Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of theModule 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A: TEN Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

1 Marks x 10 = **10 Marks**

PART B: TWO questions to be set from each module.

Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. **08 Marks x 05 Question = 40 Marks**

TEXT BOOKS:

1. M. N. Rao and H V N Rao, -Air pollution, Tata Mc-G raw Hill Publication.
2. H. C. Perkins, -Air pollution. Tata McGraw Hill Publication
3. Mackenzie Davis and David Cornwell, -Introduction to Environmental Engineering, McGraw-Hill Co.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Noel De Nevers, -Air Pollution Control Engineering, Waveland Pr Inc.
2. Anjaneyulu Y, -Text book of Air Pollution and Control Technologies, Allied Publisher

CIVIL DESIGN LABORATORY (Design of C-D Structures)

Subject Code : 19SCVL65

IA Marks : 50

Hours per week : 2L+1T

Exam Hours : 3

Credits : 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 42

Course Objectives:

1. To make the student to understand the purpose of design of the unique structures in Civil Engineering.
2. To make the students to select the suitable structure.
3. To make the student understand the basic Design Principles of various structures.
4. To make the student understand the various design steps.
5. To understand the students to familiar with design of irrigation structures.

Course outcomes

- CO1: Able to understand the purpose of the C-D structures
- CO2: Able to select the suitable structures for irrigation engineering
- CO3: Able to understand the Design Principles of the Structures
- CO4: Will understand the various design Steps
- CO5: Able to prepare drawings of Culverts and Causeways.

Experiments:

1. Types of culverts and design aspects
2. Geometric design aspects
3. Determination of the discharge
4. Structural design aspects of pipe culvert
5. RCC slab Culvert design Aspects
6. RCC Box culvert design Aspects
7. Drawings related to Culverts
8. Drawing related to Causeways

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR SEMESTER END EXAMINATION (SEE):

PART A (Theory):

4 questions will be asked 5 marks each.

Student should answer 2 questions = 10 marks

PART B (Design and Drawing):

Three questions will be asked for 20 marks.

Student should answer 2 full questions,

Each question will have 10 marks for design and 10 for related drawings = 40 marks

Text Books:

1. Johnson Victor. D —Essentials of Bridge Engineering, Oxford Publishing Company.
2. N Krishna Raju — Design of Bridges, Oxford and IBH publishing company
3. T R Jagadeesh and M A Jayaram —Design of bridge structures, Prentice Hall of India

Reference Books:

1. Jain and Jaikrishna —Plain and Reinforced Concrete, Vol.2, Nem Chand Brothers.
2. Standard specifications and code of practice for road bridges, IRC section I, II, III and IV.
3. Concrete Bridges, The Concrete Association of India.

HIGHWAY MATERIAL TESTING LABORATORY

Sub Code : 19SCVL66

IA Marks: 50

Hrs / Week : 2L+1T

Exam Marks: 50

Credits 2

COURSE OBJECTIVE:

1. To learn the principles and procedures of testing of highway materials
2. To learn the selection of different materials for highway construction
3. To learn the QA & QC aspects of highway construction materials
4. To analyse the test results of payment materials
5. To understand the importance of strength characteristics of payment materials.

COURSE OUTCOME:

CO1: Able to learn the procedures of testing of highway materials

CO2: Able to select suitable type and grade of materials for highway construction

CO3: Able to learn and apply QA & QC aspects and standards in highway / road construction

CO4: Able to analyse the test results and to take correct decision

CO5: Able to prepare documentation for the tests on highway materials.

EXPERIMENTS:

1. Specific Gravity Test for Bitumen
2. Water Absorption Test
3. Penetration Test
4. Ductility Test
5. Softening Point Of Bitumen
6. Flash and Fire Point Test
7. Viscosity Test
8. Bituminous Mix Design by Marshall Method
9. California Bearing Ratio Test
10. Aggregate Crushing Strength Test
11. Abrasion Test
12. Impact Test
13. Shape Test (Flakiness & Elongation Index)

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Veeraragavan, S.K Khanna and C.E.G. Justo, Highway Engineering, Nem Chand & Brothers, 2014.
2. Soil Mechanics & Foundation Enggll, Dr.B.C. Punmia, Ashok Kumar Jain, Arun Kumar Jain, Laxmi Publications (P)

REFERENCES:

1. Highway Materials and Pavement Testing, Nem Chand and Bros., Roorkee, RevisedFifth Edition, 2009
2. Methods for testing tar and bituminous materials, IS 1201-1978 to IS 1220- 1978,Bureau of Indian Standards
3. Methods of test for aggregates, IS 2386 – 1978, Bureau of Indian Standards

VI Semester B.Tech

EXTENSIVE SURVEY PROJECT

Sub Code : 19SCVL67

Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T

Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the practical applications of Surveying
2. To understand the utilisation of Total Station and other Measurement Equipment's
3. To work in team and learn time management, communication and presentation skills
4. To understand the surveying procedures of new tank and old tank project
5. To understand the surveying of village water pipeline and all weather road construction.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to apply Surveying knowledge and to use different surveying tools effectively

CO2: Able to understand Team environment, Goals, responsibilities, Task focus, working in Teams towards common goals, Organizational performance expectations, technical and behavioral competencies.

CO3: Able to prepare contour plans for Old Tank and New Tank project

CO4: Able to prepare drawings for village road and water supply pipeline

CO5: Able to take up medium works in water supply and road construction project.

NEW TANK PROJECT:

The work shall consist of:

- a) Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b) Alignment of center line of the proposed bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the center line.
- c) Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
- d) Design and preparation of drawing with report.

WATER SUPPLY AND SANITARY PROJECT:

The work shall consist of

- a) Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b) Examination of sources of water supply, Calculation of quantity of water required based on existing and projected population.
- c) Preparation of village map by using total station.
- d) Survey work required for laying of water supply and UGD
- e) Location of sites for water tank. Selection of type of water tank to be provided. (Ground level, overhead and underground)
- f) Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report.

HIGHWAY PROJECT:

The work shall consist of:

- a) Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b) Preliminary and detailed investigations to align a new road (min. 1 to 1.5 km stretch) between two obligatory points. The investigations shall consist of topographic surveying of strip of land for considering alternate routes and for final alignment. Surveying by using total station.
- c) Report should justify the selected alignment with details of all geometric designs for traffic and design speed assumed.
- d) Drawing shall include key plan initial alignment, final alignment, longitudinal section along final alignment, typical cross sections of road.

RESTORATION OF AN EXISTING TANK: The work shall consist of:

1. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
2. Alignment of center line of the existing bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the centerline.
3. Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
4. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report.

TOWN/HOUSING / LAYOUT PLANNING:

The work shall consist of:

1. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project. Detailed survey required for project execution like contour surveys
2. Preparation of layout plans as per regulations
3. Centerline marking-transfer of centre lines from plan to ground
4. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report as per regulations

NOTE:

- To be conducted between 5th & 6th Semester for a period of 2 weeks including training on total station.
- An extensive project preparation training involving investigation, collection of data is to be conducted. For TWO projects use of Total Station is compulsory.
- The student shall submit a project report consisting of designs and drawings.
- Drawings should be done using CAD and survey work using total station
- Students should learn data download from total station, generation of contours, block leveling, longitudinal and cross sectional diagrams, and capacity volume calculation by using relevant software.
- The course coordinators should give exposure and simulate activities to achieve the course outcomes

SCHEME OF END SEM EXAMINATION:

At the end of the semester students should submit the Project Report

Viva Voce will be conducted

Report will be evaluated for **20 marks**

Individual Viva Voce will carry **30 marks.**

ESEP-MINI ROJECT

Sub Code : 18SCV68

IA Marks : 50

Hrs / Week : 1+2

Exam Hours : -

Credits : Non-Credit (Audit) Course

Exam Marks : -

Course Objectives:

At the end of the course, the student will be able to:

- Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
- Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
- Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
- Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
- Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

Instructions/Guidelines:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work.

Students should select a problem which addresses some basic home, office or other real life applications. Students have to collect an International Journal paper on the topics of their interest, prepare a write up and present with suitable demonstration by software or experimental work. Evaluation will be based on relevant topic student has studied, communication skill and reporting/documenting procedure.

PART-A: Employability Skills Enhancement Programme 4

Subject Code	19SQA69	IA Marks	50
Lecture Hours/Week	2	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	25		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

This course enables students to develop their ability to reason by introducing them to elements of formal reasoning. The primary focus will be on recognizing the logical structure of arguments. Topics will include types of statements, symbolism, logical connectives, logical relations, basic deductive inferences, truth tables, validity, invalidity, and soundness. To enhance the problem-solving skills, to improve the basic mathematical skills and to help students who are preparing for any type of competitive examinations.

Course Outcomes:

After studying this course, students will be able to:

- Understand the basic concepts of QUANTITATIVE ABILITY
- Understand the basic concepts of LOGICAL REASONING Skills
- Acquire satisfactory competency in use of VERBAL REASONING
- Solve campus placements aptitude papers covering Quantitative Ability, Logical Reasoning and Verbal Ability
- Compete in various competitive exams like CAT, CMAT, GATE, GRE, GATE, UPSC, GPSC etc.

PART - A

Clocks, calendars, Direction Sence - a. Concepts on Clocks b. angles between the hand of a clock c. concept of Calendar d. Concept of Leap year, days and datee. Basic concept and Problem solving tecnic for various types of problem in Direction sence"

Critical reasoning- a. Argument – Identifying the Different Parts (Premise, assumption, conclusion)
b. Types of Questions

Surds, Indices and Simplification - a. Surdsb. Indices c. Simplification exercises

Set Theory - a. Set definition and formulas b. Power set c. Sub set d. Set multiplication

Functions - a. Roots of a function b. Domain and range c. Problems involving multiple functions

Cryptarithmic - Problem solving technique on cryptarithmic

Trigonometry - a. Heights and distance problems b. Identities, angles c. Simplification

Letter and Symbol Series, Visual Sequence, Alpha numeric problems - a.Problem solving tecnic for Letter and Symbol seriesb.VisualSequencC. Alpha numeric problems

Analogy - a. Synonyms/Antonyms. b. Object/Purpose. c. Source/Product. d. Part/Whole.
e. Animal/Habitat. f. Characteristics.

Letter and Email Writing - a. Types (Formal, Informal, Semi-Formal). b. Formats.
c. Samples.
d. Practice using the right salutations, greetings, subject line, addresses, conciseness and preciseness.

PART –B

Design of steel structures

Construction Management

Pre-stressed concrete

Applied Mechanics and Graphic Statics

Assessment Pattern:

- 10 assessment tests will be conducted based on Multiple Choice Questions.
- Final marks are based on the test marks conducted during the semester.

Reference Books

1. Quantitative Abilities by Arun Sharma
2. Quantitative Aptitude for Competitive Examinations by R S Agrawal
3. Verbal and Non-Verbal Reasoning by R S Agrawal.

PART-B: INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATION COURSE ON CURRENT TRENDS

Subject Code	19SQA69	IA Marks	-50
Lecture Hours/Week	-	SEE Marks	-
Total Hours	-		
Credits	2		

Course Objectives:

- Exposure to the latest development in the field
- Learn the new skills
- To make the students Industry ready
- To increase the confidence level of students
- To provide additional knowledge

Course Outcomes:

On completion of this course, students will be able to:

CO1: Have exposure on the latest development

CO2: Acquire new skills

CO3: Become Industry ready

CO4: Have more confidence

CO5: Get additional knowledge

About the Course:

- A common Certification Course on current trend will be offered to all the students of the batch.
- The course will be conducted on blended mode.
- At the end of the course, the student has to produce/submit the certificate issued by the certification agency after completing the assessment for the programme.

Assessment Method: Assessment will be conducted for 2 Hours duration for 50 Marks on completion of the course and based on the marks scored, grading will be done.

Srinivas University
College of Engineering and Technology
Mukka, Mangaluru – 574 146

VII& VIII SEMESTER

B.TECH
CIVIL ENGINEERING

SCHEME & SYLLABUS
2019

**B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING
VII SEMESTER**

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV71	Design & Drawing of Steel Structures	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	19SCV72X	Core Elective-3	3			50	50	100	03
3	19SCV73X	Core Elective-4	3			50	50	100	03
4	19SCV74X	Open Elective-2	4			50	50	100	04
4	19SCV75	Quantity Surveying & Valuation	4		2	50	50	100	04
5	19SCVL76	Environmental Engineering & Water Quality Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
6	19SCVL77	Project Phase I	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	19SCV78	ESEP-Computer Aided Design Structural Laboratory	1		1	25	25	50	02
8	19SQA79	ESEP-Employability Skill Enhancement Programme -Patent Filing & IPR	2	0	0	50	-	50	02
		Total Marks/Credit						800	26

Core Elective - 3		Core Elective - 4		Open Elective - 2	
19SCV721	Quantity Analysis & Quality Control	19SCV731	Pre-Stressed Concrete	19SCV741	Research Methodology
19SCV722	Solid Waste Management	19SCV732	Design of Bridges	19SCV742	Environmental Impact Assessment
19SCV723	Sustainable Development in Civil Engineering	19SCV733	Finite Element Analysis	19SCV743	Introduction to Smart City
19SCV724	Water Resources Management	19SCV734	Structural Dynamics	19SCS741	Social and Web Analytics
19SCV725	Industrial Waste Water Treatment	19SCV735	Earthquake Resistant Structures	19SCS742	Information Security
19SCV726	Contract Procedures & Arbitration	19SCV736	Matrix Method of Structural Analysis	19SCS743	Software Testing
19SCV727	Building Services, Facilities, Planning & Management	19SCV737	Theory of Plates & Shells	19SEC741	Artificial Intelligence
19SCV728	Rural Water Supply and Drainage System	19SCV738	Advanced Concrete Technology	19SEC742	Virtual Reality
19SCV729	Pavement Design	19SCV739	Advanced Foundation Design	19SEC743	Telecommunication Management
				19SME741	Nano Technology
				19SME742	Operations Management
				19SME743	Quality Control

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

VIII SEMESTER

SL. No	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	19SCV81	Seminar				100		100	02
2	19SCVL82	Internship				50	50	100	03
3	19SCVL83	Project (with patent Application)				100	100	200	13
		Total Marks/Credit						400	18

DESIGN & DRAWING OF STEEL STRUCTURES

Sub Code :	19SCV71	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	4	Exam Marks :	50
Total Hours :	50		

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn IS 800-2007 code of practice for the design of Compression, Tension and Flexural members using various cross-sections
2. To study the behavior and design of compression and tension members using simple and built-up sections
3. Analysis and design of steel members and connections
4. To study the components of truss, loads on trusses, analysis and design of purlins and truss members
5. To study the design of bolted and welded connections.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to apply the IS code of practice for the design of steel structural elements
 CO2: Design tension and compression members using simple and built-up sections
 CO3: Able to calculate forces on the various members of the truss and design them.
 CO4: Able to analyze the behavior of bolted connections and design them
 CO5: Able to design welded connections for both axial and eccentric forces.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Advantages and Disadvantages of Steel structures, Loads and Load combinations, Design considerations, Limit State Method (LSM) of design, Failure criteria for steel, Codes, Specifications and Section classification.

BOLTED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Behavior of Bolted joints, Design strength of ordinary Black Bolts, Design strength of High Strength Friction Grip bolts (HSFG), Simple Connections, Moment resistant connections, Beam to Beam and Beam to Column connections. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 2

WELDED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Welding process, Welding electrodes, Advantages of Welding, Types and Properties of Welds, Types of joints, Weld symbols, Weld specifications, Design of welds, Simple joints, Moment resistant connections, Beam to Beam and Beam to Columnsplices.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 3

Design of Tension Members: Introduction, Types of tension members, Behavior of tension members, Modes of failure, Factors affecting the strength of tension members, Angles undertension, Splices, Gussets, Problems on Design of tension members. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 4

Design of Compression Members: Introduction, Failure modes, Behaviour of compression members, Elastic buckling of slender compression members, Sections used for compression members, Effective length of compression members, Design of compression members, Design of built up compression members. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

MODULE 5

Design of Roof Truss - Bolted connection, for both Tension and Compression forces, Design of bottom chord, top chord, inclined and vertical member of the roof truss, Forces in the members to be given.

Design of Gantry Girder – Electrically operated gantry girder, Welded connection, Combination of Channel section, Top flange, I section and Bottom flange. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration, Site visit.

Note: Study of this course should be based on IS: 800-2007

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	Open Book Test on Design of Roof Truss / Gantry Girder (Module 5)	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks:**

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

Text / Reference Books

1) Structural Design & Drawing – N. Krishna Raju, Universities Press, India

- 2) Design of Steel Structures, N. Subramanian, Oxford, 2008
- 3) Design of Steel Structures - Negi - Tata McGraw Hill Publishers
- 4) Limit State Design of Steel Structures, Duggal. TATA McGraw Hill 2010
- 5) Bureau of Indian Standards, IS800-2007, IS875-1987
- 6) Steel Table – Birla Publications, New Delhi.

VII Semester B.Tech
QUANTITY ANALYSIS & QUALITY CONTROL

Sub Code : 19SCV721

Hrs/Week: 4

Credits : 3

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. Understanding the basic concepts of TQM
2. Develop a thinking towards Quality systems and Thinking.
3. Understand the application and processes of The various Quality Awards and also Know how ISO9000:2000 works
4. Understand Principle of ISO
5. Apply TQM in Construction Projects

COURSEOUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Evaluate the principles of quality management and to explain how these principles can be applied within quality management systems.
- CO2:** Identify the key aspects of the quality improvement cycle and to select and use appropriate tools and techniques for controlling, improving and measuring quality.
- CO3:** Critically appraise the organizational, communication and teamwork requirements for effective quality management
- CO4:** Critically analyze the strategic issues in quality management, including current issues and developments, and to devise and evaluate quality implementation plans
- CO5:** Can Apply TQM in Construction Projects

MODULE 1

Concept of Quality:

Definition of quality as given by Deming, Juran, Crosby, difference between Quality Control, Quality Assurance (QA/QC). Total quality control (TQC) and Total Quality Management(TQM), Need for TQM in construction industry.

Organization necessary for implementation of quality, Quality manual-Contents, and data required, preparation, responsibility matrix, monitoring for quality- PDCA Cycle. Quality aspects in every phase in the life cycle of Construction project.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Quality Control tools and statistical quality Control:

(A) Histogram, Pareto diagram, Fishbone diagram, Quality control chart-Testing required for quality control of construction material used in RCC Work- destructive and Non destructive Test (NDT)

(B) Statistical Quality Control- Necessity, Benchmarking, Application of dispersion methods in quality control of construction activity.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Training and development of Human Resources:

Training needs assessment, technical and managerial competencies necessary for achieving quality, preparation for training. Training on Project Rework Reduction Tool (PRRT) software-training for preparation of checklist necessary for RCC work, for commonly used formats.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Study of ISO 9004- Quality System Standards.

Purpose of ISO Standards. Difference between ISO 9001 and ISO 9004. Certification process for ISO9001. Certification bodies involved. Eight Principles of ISO-Basic meaning, applying these principles for an effective quality process in the organization. Management support and commitment necessary for achieving implementation for quality system standards.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Achieving TQM on Construction Projects:

Advantages, barriers, principles, steps in implementation, seven types of construction defects. Determining cost of poor quality including hidden cost. Quality functions deployment (QFD). Importance of third party quality audits. CIDC CQRA, quality rating systems, customers satisfaction surveys, Non Conformity Reports (NCR), remedial strategy for reducing NCR's.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions,
Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. International Standards Organization – ISO 9001 and ISO 9004
2. Mantri Handbook – A to Z of Construction – Mantri Publications
3. Juran's Quality Handbook – Joseph M. Juran, A. Blanton. Godfrey – Mc Graw Hill International Edition (1998)
4. Probability and Statistics for Engineers – Miller, Freund-Hall, Prentice India Ltd.
5. Quality Control and Total Quality Management, P.L. Jain, Tata Mc Graw Hill Publ.

VII Semester B.Tech
SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

Sub Code: 19SCV722

Hrs/Week:4

Credits: 3

IA Marks: 50

ExamHours:2

Exam Marks:50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

This course will enable students to

1. Study the present methods of solid waste management system and to analyze their drawbacks comparing with statutory rules.
2. Understand different elements of solid waste management from generation of solid waste to disposal.
3. Analyze different processing technologies and to study conversion of municipal solid waste to compost or biogas.
4. Evaluate landfill site and to study the sanitary landfill reactions.
5. Will understand the design aspects

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify improper practices of solid waste disposal and their environmental implications.

Know the basic engineering principles of solid waste management

CO2: Describe the need for economics in collection and transportation of solid waste and clearly discuss various types of collection systems and analyse system dynamics

CO3: Understand the management concepts, define 4 R approach, apply PPP model and community involvement for effective management of solid waste

CO4: Develop a concise idea on various conventional and advanced treatment options for solid waste

CO5: Conceive the design aspects of engineered disposal options and apply the gained knowledge to solve numerical examples.

MODULE 1

Sources and engineering classification, characterization, generation and quantification; Objectives, principles, functional elements of solid waste management system – Regulatory aspects of solid waste management, major problems. Environmental implications of open dumping, Construction debris – management & handling, E- Waste Management, Rag pickers and their role.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Waste Generation: Rate of generation, frequency, storage and refuse collection, physical and chemical composition, quantity of waste, engineering properties of waste, prediction, modeling concepts.

Collection, Segregation and Transport: Handling and segregation of wastes at source, Collection (primary & secondary) and storage of municipal solid wastes, collection equipment, transfer stations, collection route optimization and economics, regional concepts. System dynamics

Waste Minimization: 4R: reduce, recover, recycle and reuse, case study, guidelines.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration site visits.

10Hours**MODULE 3**

Treatment Methods: Refuse processing technologies. Mechanical and thermal volume reduction. Biological and chemical techniques for energy and other resource recovery: composting, vermin-composting, termi-gradation, fermentation. Incineration of solid wastes.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration site visits.

10Hours**MODULE 4**

Disposal Methods: Impacts of open dumping, site investigation and selection, sanitary land filling - Types, geotechnical considerations, design criteria and design, Liners - earthen, geo membrane, geo synthetics and geo textiles.

Operational aspects of MSW Landfills: Daily cover, leachate disposal, Ground Water monitoring, leachate and gas collection systems – Design, leachate treatment. Landfill Final Cap Design and Water Balance, Modelling (HELP – Hydraulic Evaluation of Landfill Performance), post-closure environmental monitoring; landfill remediation.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration site visits.

10 Hours**MODULE 5**

Recent Developments in Solid Wastes Reuse and Disposal: Power Generation, Blending with construction materials and Best Management Practices (BMP). Community based waste management, Waste as a Resource concept, Public private partnership (PPP).

Role of various organizations in Solid Waste Management: Governmental, Non - Governmental, Citizen Forums.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration site visits.

10 Hours**Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:**

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks:**

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Tchobanoglous G., Theissen H., and Eliassen R., "Solid Waste Engineering Principles and Management Issues", McGraw Hill, New York.
2. Pavoni J.L., "Handbook of Solid Waste Disposal".
3. Peavy, Rowe and Tchobanoglous, "Environmental Engineering", McGraw Hill.
4. Mantell C.L., (1975), "Solid Waste Management", John Wiley.

REFERENCES

1. CPHEEO Manual on Solid Waste Management.
2. WHO Manual on Solid Waste Management.
3. Vesiland A., "Solid Waste Engineering", Thompson Books.
4. Flintoff F., (1976), "Management of Solid Wastes in Developing Countries", WHO Regional Publications, South East Asia, New Delhi

VII Semester B.Tech
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

Sub Code : 19SCV723

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours:2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

To expose the students to the concepts of sustainability in the context of building and conventional engineered building materials

1. To use and compare relevant codes
2. Exposing the student to concepts of embodied, operational and life cycle energy, minimizing energy consumption by optimal design
3. Learn the principles of planning orientation of buildings and reuse of building materials
4. Acquire knowledge on various aspects of green construction
5. Understand various codal provisions

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify and compare existing energy codes, green building codes and green rating Systems.

CO2: Identify and use construction materials and methods that more easily allow for salvage and re-use of building materials.

CO3: Perform demolition in ways that allow for salvage of re-usable building materials.

CO4: Understand the techniques and benefits of building performance testing, monitoring and metering.

CO5: Identify and make use of techniques for weatherization and sustainable remodeling of existing structures.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Green Building, Principles of Green Building – Site aspect, Soil conservation, Vegetation retention, Energy efficiency, Materials and Resources, Water efficiency, Rainwater Harvesting, Grey water gardening, Solid waste management, Solar energy system.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Green Materials

Necessity and importance of sustainable construction materials, Material composition and properties, Production, Storage, Distribution, Testing, Acceptance criteria, Limitations of use, Economic consideration, and recent developments related to the following materials to be studied.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Admixtures in Concrete

Various construction chemicals / admixtures, Fly ash and its use in concrete, GGBS and its use in concrete, Silica fume concrete, Self-compacting concrete, Fiber reinforced plastics and concrete, Light weight concrete, Light weight cement blocks.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration factory visits. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Special Concrete

High performance concrete, Nano Technology in cement concrete, Ferro cement Technology, Crumb modified bitumen rubber, Glenium concrete, Materials used in nuclear containment structures.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration factory visits. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Green Standards

Energy Conservation Building Codes, Indian Green Building Council, Application, Compliance Mechanism, Procedure for erection of Code compliant building, Renewable Energy, Responsibilities and duties - Owners, Empanelled Energy Auditors (Building), State designated agency.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, case study. **10 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PARTA:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS :

1. Concrete Technology by Neville
2. Construction Materials, Methods & Techniques (3e) by William P Spence, Yesdee Publication 2012, Pvt. Ltd, Chennai, India
3. Concrete Structure properties & Materials by Mehta P.K & Mantreio P.J.M, Prentice Hall.
4. Concrete Technology by M.S.Shetty, S.Chand Publications
5. Building Materials by M L Gambhir, Neha Jamwal, Tata McGraw Hill Publ.
6. New Building Materials and Construction World magazine
7. Ferro cement Construction Mannual by Dr. D.B.Divekar, 1030, Shivaji Nagar, Model Colony, Pune
8. Civil Engineering and Construction Review magazine
9. Engineering Materials by Dr. S.V.Deodhar

VII Semester B.Tech
WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Sub Code: 19SCV724

Hrs/Week:4

Credits: 3

IA Marks: 50

ExamHours:2

Exam Marks:50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To build on the student's background in hydrology and hydraulics and understanding of water resources systems
2. To develop the skills in modeling of flood flows and flood routing
3. To develop skills in the ground water flow, type of aquifer and yield from the well
4. To provide the knowledge of design of reservoir, operation and sedimentation
5. To study the effect, causes and remedial measures of water logging

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to design various channel systems

CO2: Design head and cross regulator structures

CO3: To identify various types of reservoir and their design aspects

CO4: Will establish the understanding of cross drainage works and its design

CO5: Design different types of dams.

MODULE 1

Surface and Ground water Resources

Hydrologic Cycle, Global water resources and Indian Water resources, Surface Water Resources, Water Balance, Available Renewable Water Resources, Water Scarcity, The Water Balance as a Result of Human Interference, Groundwater Resources, Types of Aquifers, Groundwater as a Storage Medium.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE2

Water Resources Planning and Management

Necessity, System components, planning scales, Approaches, planning and management aspects, Analysis, Models for impact prediction and evaluation, Adaptive Integrated Policies, Post Planning and management Issues.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE3

Integrated Water Resources Management:

Definition of IWRM, Principles, Implementation of IWRM, Legislative and Organizational Framework, Types and Forms of Private Sector Involvement.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration.

10 Hours

MODULE4

Water Governance and Water Policy

Legal Framework of Water, Substance of National Water Laws Other key issues, Changing incentives through Regulation, National Water Policy, National Level Commissions, Irrigation Management, Transfer Policies and Activities – Legal Registration of WUAs – Legal Changes in Water Allocation, Role of Local Institutions, Community Based Organizations, Water Policy Reforms: India.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, visit to concerned govt. department.

10 Hours

MODULE5

Water Harvesting and Conservation

Water Harvesting Techniques – Micro-catchments, Design of Small Water Harvesting Structures – Farm Ponds – Percolation Tanks, Yield from a Catchment, Rain water Harvesting- various techniques related to rural and urban area.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration, site visit.

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. K. Subramanya, "Engineering Hydrology", Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishers, New Delhi.
2. H.M. Raghunath, "Ground Water", Wiley Eastern Publication, New Delhi.
3. Daniel P. Loucks and Eelco van Beek, "Water Resources Systems. Planning and Management", UNESCO Publication.
4. Mollinga, P. et al, "Integrated Water Resources Management", Water in South Asia Volume I, Sage Publications, 2006.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Singh, Chhatrapati "Water Rights in India," Ed: Chhatrapati Singh. Water Law in India: The Indian Law Institute, New Delhi, 1992.
2. DhruvaNarayana, G. Sastry, V. S. Patnaik, "Watershed Management", CSWCTRI, Dehradun, ICAR Publications, 1997.

VII Semester B.Tech
INDUSTRIAL WASTE WATER TREATMENT

Sub Code : 19CV725

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES

1. To make Students understand the difference between domestic and industrial waste water
2. To make the student to understand various industrial waste water treatment methods
3. To make the student to understand combined treatment methods
4. To make the students to know about treatment of various industrial wastes
5. To prepare the students to make decisions on the method to be adopted for the industrial waste treatment methods

COURSE OUTCOMES

CO1: Understand the characteristics of industrial wastewater.

CO2: Identify sampling method and analyze industrial waste.

CO3: Design facilities for the processing and reclamation of industrial waste water.

CO4: They understand the extent of treatment required for the various industrial wastes

CO5: Analyze proposed development project plans for possible environmental effects and to improve treated effluent quality to confirm standard prescribed by regulatory agencies.

Module 1

Introduction

Difference between Domestic and Industrial Wastewater, Effect on Streams and on Municipal Sewage Treatment Plants. Stream Sampling, effluent and stream Standards and Legislation to Control Water Pollution.

Stream Quality: Stream Quality, Dissolved oxygen Sag Curve in Stream, Numerical Problems on DO prediction.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration, visit to treatment plant. **10 Hours**

Module 2

Treatment Methods

Volume Reduction, Strength Reduction, Neutralization, Equalization and Proportioning. Removal of Inorganic suspended solids, Removal of Organic Solids, Removal of suspended solids and colloids. Treatment and Disposal of Sludge Solids.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration, visit to treatment plant. **10 Hours**

Module 3

Combined Treatment

Feasibility of combined Treatment of Industrial Raw Waste with Domestic Waste, Discharge of Raw, Partially Treated and completely treated Wastes to Streams. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration, visit to treatment plant.

Module 4**Treatment of Selected Industrial Wastes**

Process flow sheet showing origin / sources of waste water, characteristics of waste, alternative treatment methods, disposal, reuse and recovery along with flow sheet. Effect of waste disposal on water bodies. The industries to be covered are Cotton Textile Industry, Tanning Industry. Cane Sugar Industry & Distillery Industry, Dairy Industry, Pharmaceutical Industry.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration, visit to treatment plant. **10 Hours**

Module 5

Provision of various acts pertaining to industrial wastes / effluents, introduction to environmental impact assessment and environmental audit. Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs): Location, Need, Design, Operation & Maintenance Problems and Economical aspects.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration, visit to treatment plant. **10 hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:
PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. Waste Water Treatment: Rao & Datta, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co.
2. Environmental Pollution and control in chemical process industries: S.C. Bhatia, Khanna Publication.
3. Industrial Water Pollution Control: W W Eckenfelder Jr, McGraw Hill.
4. Industrial Water Pollution Management: E F Gurnham, John Wiley

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Pollution Control in Process Industries: S P Mahajan, Tata Mc Graw Hill.
2. Industrial Waste: W Rudolfs, (Ed), L E C Publishers Inc.
3. Environmental Impact Analysis Handbook :G.J. Rao and C.D. Weeten, Mc Graw Hill
4. Environmental Audit, Mhaskar A.K, Enviro Media Publications.

VII Semester B.Tech
CONTRACT PROCEDURES & ARBITRATION

Sub Code : 19SCV726
Hrs/Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks: 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the present stage of contract documentation in national and international contracts
2. To study on preparing tender documentations and its evaluation process
3. To understand the stages in contract conditioning; arbitration and resolution of contracts
4. To understand the office Engineering and procedures
5. To understand the process of Arbitration.

COURSEOUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Adopting the ethical knowledge for making construction contracts & Tenders.
- CO2:** The students will get the experience to make Estimation, Bill of Quantity for construction work.
- CO3:** The student will get in depth knowledge of special aspect of tender & contract management.
- CO4:** To learn various aspects of Arbitration to resolution of disputes in construction projects.
- CO5:** Able to know the process of Arbitration.

MODULE 1

Introduction: To law, Indian legal system, Laws governing structure & Working of Construction Organization Firms,. Laws of Tort

Construction Contract Documents:

Evaluation of contract documents, need for documents, present stage of national and international contract documents, types of construction contracts, roles and functions of parties to the contract.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, departmental visit, study departmental procedures.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Stages in Contracting:

Preparation of tender documents estimating, pre-qualification, bid evaluation, award of contract, project financing and contract payments, contracts close out and completion. Preparation of tender documents estimating, pre-qualification, bid evaluation, award of contract, project financing and contract payments, contracts close out and completion.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, departmental visit, study departmental procedures.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Contract Conditions:

Interpretation by parties to contract, obligations and responsibilities of the parties, protection and Indemnification, bonds and insurance, laws and liens, subsurface conditions, inspection of work, change of work, rejected work and deficiencies.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, departmental visit, study departmental procedures.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Office Engineering:

Proper record keeping in contract administering, establishment of standard procedures, coordination between various agencies involved, providing data for interpretation of contract clauses Special aspects of contract management.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, departmental visit, study departmental procedures.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Arbitration

Comparison of Actions and Laws - Agreements , subject matter-Violations-Appointment of Arbitrators-Conditions of Arbitrations-Powers and duties of Comparison of Actions and Laws, Agreements ,subject matter Violations-Appointment of Arbitrators-Conditions of Arbitrations, Powers and duties of Arbitrator-Rules of Evidence-Enforcement of Award-costs. Causes and resolution of disputes, settlement of claims and extra items, Arbitration Indian Contract Act, Arbitration Act

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, departmental visit, study departmental procedures.

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks:**

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Explanation of Indian Contract Act: Mulla and SanjeevaRao, B.D. Virmani, B.T.Gajaria
2. Handbook of Contracts: Hudson.
3. Construction Contracting, Clough Richarch, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1986.
4. Construction Contract Management, Prakash V.A., NICMAR, BOMBAY

VII Semester B.Tech

BUILDING SERVICES, FACILITIES PLANNING & MANAGEMENT

Sub Code : 19SCV727

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits 3

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the types of MEP systems and its suitability in construction industry
2. To plan various types of mechanical services and HVAC as per the requirements of buildings
3. To apply various types of electrical and fire fighting services as per the requirements of building and Govt Regulations
4. To provide Plumbing, Sound and Thermal insulation as per the needs of client
5. To know the importance and requirement of rain water harvesting, Solid Waste Management.

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Demonstrate an understanding of the need for different types of MEP systems and select suitable type

CO2: Recognize the implications of building design for mechanical, electrical and plumbing(MEP) service provision including appreciation of the design and construction for high efficiency and sustainable building services

CO3: Illustrate services installation including fire safety and ventilation

CO4: Manage the hand-over and commissioning processes for services

CO5: Plan for Rain Water Harvesting and Solid Waste Management in the new buildings.

MODULE 1

Water Supply, Drainage and Solid Waste Disposal

Water requirements for different types of buildings, simple method of removal of impurities, water saving practices and their potential, Service connection from mains, sump and storage tank, Types and sizes of pipes used in multistoried buildings.

Types of fixtures and fitting for a contemporary bathroom – taps – quarter turn, half turn, ceramic, foam flow etc, hot water mixer, hand shower. Rainwater harvesting, sizes of rainwater pipes and typical detail of a water harvesting pit. Principles of drainage, surface drainage, shape and sizes of drains and sewers, storm water over flow chambers. Approaches for solid waste management, Solid wastes collection, On-site processing and disposal methods.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE2

Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC)

Behaviour of heat propagation, thermal insulating materials and their co-efficient of thermal conductivity. General methods of thermal insulation: Thermal insulation of roofs, exposed walls. Ventilation: Definition and necessity, system of ventilation. Principles of air conditioning, Air cooling, Different systems of ducting and distribution, Essentials of air-conditioning system.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Electrical Services

Electrical systems, Single/Three phase supply, Protective devices in electrical installation, Earthing and Grounding, ISI Specifications. Electrical installations in buildings - Types of wires, Wiring systems and their choice, Planning electrical wiring for building, Main and Distribution boards, Preparation of Electrical Layout for a house or building.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Fire Fighting Services

Classification of buildings based on occupancy, causes of fire and spread of fire, Standard fire, Firefighting, protection and fire resistance, Firefighting equipment and different methods of fighting fire, means of escape, alarms, etc., Combustibility of materials, Structural elements and fire resistance, Fire escape routes, Wet risers, dry risers, sprinklers, heat detector, smoke detectors, fire dampers, fire doors, etc., Provisions of NBC, Preparation of Plumbing and Fire Fighting layout for a residential or public building.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Engineering Services

Engineering services in a building as a system, Lifts, escalators, cold and hot water systems. Pumps and Machineries: Reciprocating, Centrifugal, Deep well, Submersible, Automatic pumps, Sewerage pumps, Compressors, Vacuum pumps, Hot water boilers – Classification and types of lifts, Escalators - their uses, types and sizes, safety norms to be adopted – Social features required for physically handicapped and elderly, Generators.

Building Maintenance: Preventive and protective maintenance, Planning of Scheduled and contingency maintenance, Maintenance standards. Economic maintenance decisions.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks:**

PART A:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS / REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Charangith Shah, Water supply and sanitary engineering, Galgotia publishers.
2. Kamala & DL Kanth Rao, Environmental Engineering, Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd.
3. Technical teachers Training Institute (Madras), Environmental Engineering, Tata McGraw Hill publishing Co. Ltd.
4. M. David Egan, Concepts in Building Fire Safety.
5. O.H.Koenigsberger, "Manual of Tropical Housing and Building", Longman Group United Kingdom
6. V.K.Jain, Fire Safety In Building 2edition, New Age International Publishers
7. E.G.Butcher, Smoke control in Fire-safety Design.
8. E.R.Ambrose, Heat pumps and Electric Heating, John and Wiley and Sons Inc, New York
9. Handbook for Building Engineers in Metric systems, NBC, New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. National Building Code
2. HSE Regulations.

VII Semester B.Tech
RURAL WATER SUPPLY AND DRAINAGE SYSTEM

Sub Code : 19SCV728

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits 3

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. Water sources, water borne diseases and drinking water quality standards.
2. Water treatment methods and to control contamination of water.
3. The usage of pumps.
4. Refuse collection system and disposal.
5. Principles of rural sanitation and rain water harvesting.

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify and select water supply systems in rural areas.

CO2: Distinguish between urban and rural water supply systems.

CO3: Categorize the different types of water borne and communicable diseases and apply the principles of rain water harvesting.

CO4: Explain overall management of rural water supply and other components like milk sanitation.

CO5: Examine overall management of solid waste collection, disposal and other components like composting of waste to energy.

MODULE 1

Rural Water Supply: Introduction: Need for a protected water supply, Investigation and selection of water sources, water borne diseases, Protection of well waters, drinking water quality standards.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Types of Pumps: Supply systems viz., BWS, MWS, PWS, water treatment methods- disinfection, defluoridation, hardness and iron removal, ground water contamination and removal.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Rural Sanitation: Conservancy, public latrine, concept of eco-sanitation, trenching and composting methods, two pit latrines, aqua privy, W.C, septic tank, soak pit.

Drainage Systems: Storm water and sullage disposal, rain water harvesting and uses.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Communicable diseases: Terminology, Classifications, Methods of communication, general methods of Control Refuse Collection and disposal: Garbage, ash, rubbish, collection methods, transportation and disposal-salvaging, dumping, controlled tipping, incineration and composting, dung disposal-digester, biogas plant.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Milk Sanitation: Essentials, Test for milk quality, pasteurization, quality control, cattle borne diseases, planning for a cow shed.

Insect Control: House fly and mosquito-life cycle, diseases, transmission and control measures.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study, site visit, video demonstration. **10 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PARTA:

Ten Multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01Mark x 10 Question = 10Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. S. K Garg: "Water Supply Engineering," (Chapters 1-3), Khanna Publishers, Delhi, 26th Edition, 2012, ISBN: 978-8174091208.

2 E. William: "Steel, Water Supply and Sewerage", (Chapters 4,5), Mc Graw-Hill Publishers, Delhi, 28th Edition, 2011, ISBN: 978-0471523772.

REFERENCES BOOKS:

- 1.K.Park: “Preventive and Social medicine”, (Chapters 4,5), Bhanot Publishers, Jabalpur (M.P ,India), 23rd Edition, 2015, ISBN: 978-9382219057.
2. Joseph. A. Solveto: “Environmental Engineering and Sanitation”, (Chapters1-3), Wiley-Inter science Publishers, New Delhi, 4th Edition, 2012, ISBN: 978- 0471523772.

E-RESOURCES:

1. <http://nptel.ac.in/courses/105105048/>
2. <http://nptel.ac.in/courses/105104102/>

**VIII Semester B.Tech
PAVEMENT DESIGN**

Sub Code : 19SCV729
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks : 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study about the types and components of pavements
2. To learn about the stresses in flexible pavements and equivalent single wheel load
3. To study the design of flexible pavements
4. To learn about the stresses in rigid pavements, design of dowel and tie bars
5. To study the failures, maintenance and evaluation of life of flexible and rigid pavements.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Identify the pavement components and compare highway and airport pavements
- CO2:** Calculate stresses and ESWL in flexible pavements
- CO3:** Design the flexible pavement using empirical and semi empirical methods
- CO4:** Analyze the warping, friction, wheel load stress, calculate the combined stress, design dowel and tie bars in rigid pavements
- CO5:** Analyze and Evaluate different types of failures, and suggest remedial measures for the maintenance of flexible and rigid pavement.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Desirable characteristics of pavement, Type's and components, Difference between Highway pavement and Air field pavement– Design strategies of variables – Functions of sub-grade, sub base – Base course – surface course – comparison between Rigid and flexible pavement.

FUNDAMENTALS OF DESIGN OF PAVEMENTS: Design life – Traffic factors – climatic factors – Road geometry – Subgrade strength and drainage, Stresses and deflections, Boussinesq's theory – principle, Assumptions – Limitations and problems on above - Burmister theory – Two layered analysis – Assumptions – problems on above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, Chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 2

DESIGN FACTORS: Design wheel load – contact pressure – ESWL concept – Determination of ESWL by graphical method - Equivalent deflection criteria – Stress criteria – EWL concept.

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT DESIGN: McLeod Method – Kansas method – Tri-axial method - CBR method – IRC Method (old) - CSA Method using IRC 37-2001. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 3

STRESSES IN RIGID PAVEMENT: Principle – Factors - Wheel load and its repetition – Properties of sub grade - External conditions – Joints – Reinforcement – Analysis of stresses - Assumptions – Westergaard's Analysis – Modified Westergaard's equations – Critical stresses - Wheel load stresses, Warping stress – Frictional stress – combined stresses (using chart / equations)

- problems on above.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF RIGID PAVEMENT: Design of C.C. Pavement by IRC: 58 –2002 for dual and Tandem axle load – Reinforcement in slabs – Requirements of joints – Types of joints – Expansion joint – contraction joint– warping joint – construction joint – longitudinal joint, Design of joints, Design of Dowel bars, Design of Tie bars – problems of the above. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

MODULE 5

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE AND EVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in flexible pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurement by using different techniques - Structural Evaluation by Benkelman Beam Deflection Method, Falling weight deflectometer, GPR Method.

RIGID PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE AND EVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in rigid pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurements.

Design factors for Runway Pavements - Design methods for Airfield pavements.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk, Video demonstration.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of theModule4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for ONE MARK each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer FIVE full questions, Choosing at least ONE full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Highway Engineering - Khanna & Justo
2. Principles & Practices of Highway Engineering- L R Kadiyalli & N B. Lal
3. Pavement Analysis & Design - Yang H. Huang- II edition.
4. IRC 37 and IRC 58 codes

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Principles of Pavement Design- Yoder and Witzack - 2nd edition, John Wileys and Sons
2. Principles of Pavement Design- Subha Rao
3. IRC 37 Code Book
4. IRC 58 Code Book

VII Semester B.Tech
PRE-STRESSED CONCRETE

Sub Code : 19SCV731
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

Course Objectives:

1. Students will be able to understand the general mechanical behavior of pre stressed concrete.
2. Students will be able to analyze and design pre stressed concrete flexural members.
3. Students will be able to analyze and design for vertical and horizontal shear in pre stressed concrete.
4. Students will be able to analyze transfer and development length as well as pre stress losses.
5. Students will be able to analyze and design for deflection and crack control connections of pre stressed concrete members.

Course Outcomes:

- CO1:** Students will be able to identify and apply the applicable industry design codes relevant to the design of pre stressed concrete members.
- CO2:** Student will be familiar with professional and ethical issues and the importance of lifelong learning in structural engineering.
- CO3:** Students will become familiar with the pre stressed concrete fabrication and construction process
- CO4:** Students will be able to perform an industry relevant design project in a team setting.
- CO5:** Students will be able to understand the effectiveness of the design of PSC after studying losses capable of analyzing the PSC element and finding its efficiency.

Module I

Introduction and Analysis of Members: Concept of Pre stressing-Types of Pre stressing-Advantages - Limitations -Pre stressing systems-Anchoring devices-Materials-Mechanical Properties of high strength concrete-high strength steel-Stress-Strain curve for High strength concrete. Analysis of members at transfer-Stress concept-Comparison of behavior of reinforced concrete-pre stressed concrete-Force concept-Load balancing concept-Kern point - Pressure line.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration. **10 Hours**

Module 2

Losses in Pre stress: Loss of Pre stress due to Elastic shortening, Friction, Anchorage slip, Creep of concrete, Shrinkage of concrete and Relaxation of steel-Total Loss. Deflection and Crack Width Calculations of Deflection due to gravity loads-Deflection due to pre-stressing force - Total deflection- Limits of deflection - Limits of span-to-effective depth ratio - Calculation of Crack Width - Limits of crack width. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration.

Module 3

Design of Sections for Flexure: Analysis of members at ultimate strength – Preliminary Design – Final Design for type 1 members. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration.

Module 4

Design of Shear: Analysis of shear components of shear-resistance- Modes of failures- Limit state of collapse for shear- Design of transverse reinforcement. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration.

Module 5

Composite Sections: Types of composite construction – Analysis of composite sections -Deflection - Flexural and shear strength of composite sections. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, Laboratory Demonstration.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PARTA:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

Text Books:

1. Krishna Raju, N. Pre stressed Concrete, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company, New Delhi 2006
2. Krishna Raju. N., Pre-stressed Concrete-Problems and Solutions, CBS Publishers and Distributors, Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Rajagopalan N, Pre-stressed Concrete, Narosa Publishing House, New Delhi

Reference Books:

1. "Design of Pre-stressed Concrete Structures" by T Y Lin and N H Burns
2. "Pre-stressed Concrete Analysis and Design: Fundamentals" by A E Naaman
3. "Limit State Design of Prestressed Concrete" by Y Guyan

VII Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF BRIDGES

Sub Code : 19SCV732
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

Course Objectives:

1. Students will be able to understand the analysis and design of concrete Bridges.
2. Students will be able to know the various loads that act on the bridges as per IRC..
3. Students will be able to analyze for the maximum BM and SF at critical section using load distributing theories.
4. Students will be able to design of various components using limit state method with reinforcement details.
5. Study the T beam bridges

Course Outcomes:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the load distribution and IRC standards.
CO2: Student will be familiar with Design the slab and T beam bridges.
CO3: Students will be familiar with Design Box culvert, pipe culvert
CO4: Students will be able to use bearings, hinges and expansion joints.
CO5: Students will be able to understand the Design Piers and abutments.

Module I

Introduction: Historical Developments, Site Selection for Bridges, Classification of Bridges Forces on Bridges. Bridge substructures: Abutments, piers and wing walls Balanced Cantilever Bridge: Introduction and proportioning.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, visit to typical bridge site.

10 Hours

Module 2

Box Culvert: Different Loading Cases IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled and Class A Loading, working out the worst combination of loading, Moment Distribution, Calculation of BM & SF with Reinforcement

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, visit to typical bridge site.

10 Hours

Module 3

Slab Culvert: Different Loading Cases IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled and Class A Loading, working out the worst combination of loading, Moment Distribution, Calculation of BM & SF with Reinforcement.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, visit to typical bridge site.

10 Hours

Module IV

T Beam Bridge Slab Design: Proportioning of Components Analysis of interior Slab & Cantilever Slab Using IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled Class A Loading, Structural Design of Slab with Reinforcement.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, visit to typical bridge site. **10 Hours**

Module V

T Beam Bridge Cross Girder Design: Analysis of Cross Girder for Dead Load & Live Load Using IRC Class AA Tracked, Wheeled Class A Loading A Loads, Structural Design of Beam with Reinforcement Details.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations, visit to typical bridge site. **10 Hours**

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

Text Books:

- 1.“Essentials of Bridge Engineering”- D Johnson Victor, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co New Delhi.
- 2.“Design of Bridges”- N Krishna Raju, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co New Delhi.
- 3.“Principles and Practice of Bridge Engineering”- S P Bindra Dhanpat Rai & Sons New Delhi.

Reference Books:

1. “Raina V.K., “Concrete Bridge Practice”- Tata McGraw Hill
2. Bakht B & Jaeggar, “Bridge Analysis Simplified”- McGraw Hill
3. Ponnuswamy . S, “Bridge Engineering”- Tata McGraw Hill.
4. Derrick Beckett, “An Introduction to Structural Design of Concrete Bridges” Surrey University Press.

5. IRC 6 - 1966 “Standard Specifications And Code Of Practice For Road Bridges”- Section II Loads and Stresses, The Indian Road Congress New Delhi
6. IRC 21 - 1966 “Standard Specifications And Code Of Practice For Road Bridges”-Section III Cement Concrete (Plain and reinforced) The Indian Road Congress New Delhi
7. IS 456 - 2000 “Indian Standard Plain and Reinforced Concrete Code of Practice”- (Fourth Revision) BIS New Delhi
8. IS 1343 - “Indian Standard Pre stressed Concrete Code of Practice”- BIS New Delhi

VII Semester B.Tech
FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Sub Code: 19SCV733

Hrs/Week: 4

Credits: 3

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the strain –displacement and linear constitutive relation
2. To understand the numerical techniques applied in FEM
3. Establishment of element stiffness and load vector
4. To study about the 2-D isoparametric concepts
5. To analyze the 2-D frame elements using FEM techniques

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Demonstrate the differential equilibrium equations and their relationship

CO2: Apply numerical methods to FEM

CO3: Demonstrate the displacement models and load vectors

CO4: Compute the stiffness matrix for isoperimetric elements

CO5: Analyze plane stress and plane strain problems

MODULE 1

Basic concepts of elasticity - Kinematic and Static variables for various types of structural problems - approximate method of structural analysis - Rayleigh - Ritz method - Finite difference method - Finite element method. Variation method and minimization of Energy approach of element formulation. Principles of finite element method - advantages & disadvantages - Finite element procedure. Finite elements used for one, two & three-dimensional problems - Element aspect ratio - mesh refinement vs. higher order elements - Numbering of nodes to minimize band width. **10**

Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 2

Nodal displacement parameters - Convergence criterion - Compatibility requirements - Geometric invariance - Shape function - Polynomial form of displacement function. Generalized and Natural coordinates - Lagrangian interpolation function - shape functions for one, two & three-dimensional elements. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 3

Isoparametric elements - Internal nodes and higher order elements - Serendipity and Lagrangian family of Finite Elements - Sub parametric and Super parametric elements - Condensation of internal nodes - Jacobian transformation Matrix. Development of strain - displacement matrix and stiffness matrix, consistent load vector, numerical integration. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 4

Application of Finite Element Method for the analysis of one & two-dimensional problems - Analysis of simple beams and plane trusses - Application to plane stress / strain / axisymmetric problems using CST & Quadrilateral Elements. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE5

Application to Plates & Shells- Choice of displacement function (C, C and C type) - Techniques for Non - linear Analysis. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:**PARTA:**

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Krishnamoorthy C S, "Finite Element Analysis"- Tata McGraw Hill
2. Desai C and Abel J F, "Introduction to the Finite Element Method"- East West Press Pvt. Ltd., 1972

3. Bathe K J, "Finite Element Procedures in Engineering Analysis"- Prentice Hall
4. Rajasekaran. S, "Finite Element Analysis in Engineering Design"-Wheeler Publishing
5. Cook R D, Malkan D S & Plesta M.E, "Concepts and Application of Finite Element Analysis" - 3rd Edition, John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1989.
6. Shames I H and Dym C J, "Energy and Finite Element Methods in Structural Mechanics"- McGraw Hill, New York, 1985.

VII Semester B.Tech
STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS

Sub Code : 19SCV734
Hrs/Week : 4
Credits 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks:50
Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To introduce the concepts of dynamic systems
2. To study the dynamic response of SDOF
3. To study the dynamic response of MDOF
4. To introduce the continuous systems subjected to different types of dynamic loads
5. To learn free and forced vibrations response of structural systems

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To apply the concepts of dynamic systems

CO2: To identify, formulate and solve dynamic response of SDOF

CO3: To identify, formulate and solve dynamic response of MDOF

CO4: To analyze continuous systems subjected to different types of dynamic loads

CO5: To identify, formulate and solve free and forced vibrations response of structural systems

MODULE 1

Introduction: Introduction to Dynamic problems in Civil Engineering, Concept of degrees of freedom, D'Alembert's principle, Principle of virtual displacement and energy principles
Dynamics of Single-degree-of-freedom systems: Mathematical models of Single-degree-of-freedom systems system, Free vibration response of damped and undamped systems. Methods of evaluation of damping. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 2

Response of Single-degree-of-freedom systems to harmonic loading (rotation unbalance, reciprocating unbalance) including support motion, vibration isolation, transmissibility, Numerical methods applied to Single-degree-of-freedom systems - Duhamel integral, principle of vibration-measuring instruments - seismometer and accelerometer. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 3

Dynamics of Multi-degree freedom systems: Mathematical models of multi-degree-of-freedom systems, Shear building concept, free vibration of undamped multi-degree-of-freedom systems - Natural frequencies and mode shapes - orthogonality property of modes. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 4

Response of Shear buildings for harmonic loading without damping using normal mode approach. Response of Shear buildings for forced vibration for harmonic loading with damping using normal mode approach, condition of damping uncoupling. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations

MODULE 5

Approximate methods: Rayleigh's method Dunkarley's method, Stodola's method. Dynamics of Continuous systems: Free longitudinal vibration of bars, flexural vibration of beams with different end conditions. Stiffness matrix, mass matrix (lumped and consistent); equations of motion for the discredited beam in matrix form. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PARTA:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Dynamics of Structures - Theory and Application to Earthquake Engineering"- 2nd ed., Anil K. Chopra, Pearson Education.
2. Earthquake Resistant Design of Building Structures, VinodHosur, WILEY (india)
3. Vibrations, structural dynamics- M. Mukhopadhaya : Oxford IBH.
4. Structural Dynamics- Mario Paz : CBS publishers.
5. Structural Dynamics- Clough &Penzien : TMH
6. Vibration Problems in Engineering Timoshenko, S, Van-Nostrand Co.

VII Semester B.Tech
EARTHQUAKE RESISTANT STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 19SCV735

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 50

Course Objectives:

1. To provide a coherent development to the students for the courses in sector of earthquake engineering.
2. To present the foundations of many basic engineering concepts related earthquake Engineering.
3. To give an experience in the implementation of engineering concepts which are applied in field of earthquake engineering.
4. To involve the application of scientific and technological principles of planning, analysis, design of buildings according to earthquake design philosophy.
5. To know the concepts of ductility detailing procedures.

Course Outcomes:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the principles of engineering seismology, Design and develop analytical skills.
- CO2:** Students will be able to summarize the Seismic evaluation and retrofitting of structures to give an exposure to earthquake engineering.
- CO3:** Students will be able to evaluate seismic forces for various structures as per relevant Indian standards
- CO4:** Students will be able to understand the design and ductile detailing of structures for seismic resistance as per Indian standards.
- CO5:** Students will able to understand apply concepts of repair and rehabilitation of earthquake affected structures.

Module I

Introduction to engineering seismology, Geological and tectonic features of India, Origin and propagation of seismic waves, characteristics of earthquake and its quantification - Magnitude and Intensity scales, seismic instruments. Earthquake Hazards in India, Earthquake Risk Evaluation and Mitigation.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

10 Hours

Module II

Structural behavior under gravity and seismic loads, Lateral load resisting structural systems, Requirements of efficient earthquake resistant structural system, damping devises, base isolation systems.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

10 Hours

Module III

The Response history and strong motion characteristics. Response Spectrum - elastic and inelastic response spectra, tripartite (D-V-A) response spectrum, use of response spectrum in earthquake resistant design.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Module IV

Design of Computation of seismic forces in multistoried buildings - using procedures (Equivalent lateral force and dynamic analysis) as per IS-1893. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Module V

Design of Reinforced concrete buildings for earthquake resistance-Load combinations, Ductility and energy absorption in buildings. Confinement of concrete for ductility, design of columns and beams for ductility, ductile detailing provisions as per IS-1893. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:**PARTA:**

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

Text Books:

1. Dynamics of Structures - Theory and Application to Earthquake Engineering- 2nd ed. - Anil K. Chopra, Pearson Education.
2. Earthquake Resistant Design of Building Structures, VinodHosur, WILEY (india)
3. Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures, Duggal, Oxford University Press.

Reference Books:

1. IS - 1893 (Part I): 2002, IS - 13920: 1993, IS - 4326: 1993, IS-13828: 1993
2. Design of Earthquake Resistant Buildings, Minoru Wakabayashi, McGraw Hill Pub.
3. Seismic Design of Reinforced Concrete and Masonry Buildings, T Paulay and M J N Priestley, John Wiley and Sons.

VII Semester B.Tech
MATRIX METHOD OF STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Sub Code : 19SCV736
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To provide basic concepts and principles of Stiffness and flexibility matrix
2. To give an ability to apply the concepts of flexibility and stiffness matrix to solve problems in beams, frames and trusses
3. To facilitate the concept of direct stiffness method to solve problems in beams, frames and trusses
4. To apply fundamental concepts related to force transformation of matrix
5. To apply fundamental concepts related to displacement transformation of matrix

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will be able to understand the concepts and principles of Stiffness and flexibility matrix
- CO2:** Students will be able to understand, formulate and solve problems with respect to Stiffness and flexibility matrix.
- CO3:** Students will be able to understand and formulate and solve problems with respect to direct Stiffness matrix.
- CO4:** Students will be able to analyze the beams, truss and frames by force transformation matrix
- CO5:** Students will be able to analyze the beams, truss and frames by displacement transformation matrix

MODULE 1

Introduction to flexibility method: Element flexibility matrix, Principle of contragradience, and Force Transformation Matrix, Member Flexibility matrix, Construction of structure flexibility matrix. Matrix determination of the displacement vector, Determination of member forces. Analysis of axially rigid continuous beams by flexibility method using Force Transformation Matrix. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 2

Analysis of rigid plane frames with axially rigid members by flexibility method using Force Transformation Matrix. Analysis of trusses by flexibility method Using Force Transformation Matrix.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Fundamentals of the stiffness method: equivalent joint loads, Displacement Transformation matrix. Member stiffness matrix, Total or system stiffness matrix, Truss analysis by stiffness method using Displacement Transformation Matrix. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 4

Continuous Beam and rigid frame analysis with axially rigid members by stiffness method using Displacement Transformation Matrix. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 5

Introduction to direct stiffness method: Local and global co-ordinate system, transformation Of variables, Transformation of the member displacement matrix, Transformation of the member Force matrix, Transformation of the member stiffness matrix, Transformation of the stiffness Matrix of the member of a truss, Transformation of the stiffness matrix of the member of the Rigid frame, Overall stiffness matrix, Boundary conditions, Computation of internal forces. Analysis of trusses and continuous beams by direct stiffness method. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk for Problem Solving, Video demonstration or Simulations.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:**PART A:**

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Matrix, finite elements, Computer and Structural analysis-** M Mukhopadhyay – Oxford & IBW, 1984
2. **Matrix Analysis of framed structures-** W. Weaver J.M. Gere - CBS publishers and Disributers, 1986).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Computational structural Mechanics-** S Rajshekharan. G SankaraSubramanian - PHI, 2001
2. **Structural Analysis A Matrix Approach-** G.S Pandit& S P Gupta Tata Mc Graw-Hill, 1981
3. **Basic structural Analysis-** C.S Reddy - Tata Mc Graw-Hill, 1996
4. **Structural Analysis-** L S Negi and R S Jangid - Tata Mc Graw- Hill, 1997
5. **Introduction to Matrix Methods of Structural analysis -** H C Martin -International text book Company, 1996

VII Semester B.Tech
THEORY OF PLATES AND SHELLS

Sub Code : 19SCV737
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Introduce the concept plate theory
2. Study the behavior and analysis of thin plates
3. Study the behavior and analysis of rectangular plates and circular plates
4. To present the foundations of the classical theory of shells
5. To study the classification of shell surfaces

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Students will able to assess the strength of plate panels under point, linearly varying and UDL loads
- CO2:** Students will be able to analyze plates under different boundary conditions by various classical methods and approximate methods
- CO3:** Students will be able to be familiar with classification of shells and classical shell theories and apply them in engineering design
- CO4:** Students will be able to be exposed to singly, cylindrical and doubly curved shells
- CO5:** Able to design and analyse shells and cylindrical structures.

MODULE 1

Bending of Long Rectangular Plates to a Cylindrical Surface: Differential equation for cylindrical bending of plates – Uniformly loaded rectangular plates with simple supported edges and with built in edges. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations. Site visits.

MODULE 2

Pure bending of plates: Slopes – Curvatures of bent plates – Relations between bending moments and curvature – Particular cases – Strain energy in pure bending – Limitations. Symmetrical bending of circular plates: Differential equation – Boundary conditions. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations.

MODULE 3

Simply supported rectangular plates under sinusoidal loading: Naviers solution and its application to concentrated load – Levy’s solution for uniformly distributed load or hydrostatic pressure.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations. Site visits.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Introduction to Shells: Parametric representation of a surface; The first quadratic form; Equation to the normal of a surface; The second quadratic form; Principal curvatures, Gauss curvature, and lines of curvature; Some definitions; Classification of shell surfaces. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations. Site visits.

MODULE 5

Cylindrical shells: Membrane theory of cylindrical shells; Bending theory of cylindrical shells loaded Symmetrically – Approximate solution by Schorer's method, Beam method of analysis. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Video demonstration or Simulations. Site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PARTA:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each. (01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. '1. Theory of plates and shells by S.P.Timoshenko and S.Woinowsky-Krieger, McGraw-Hill, 1959.
2. Stresses in plates and shells by A.C.Ugural, McGraw-Hill, 1999.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. "Analysis of plates" by T.K.Varadan and K.Bhaskar ,Narosa Publishing House, 1999.
2. "Stresses in Shells" by Flugge. Blaisdell Publishing Co, 1966
3. "Design and construction of concrete shell roofs" by G.S.Ramaswamy, CBS Publishers& Distributors, 1986.

VIII Semester B.Tech
ADVANCED CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY

Sub Code: 19SCV738

Hrs/Week: 4

Credits: 3

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand on cement chemistry and influence of other cementitious materials to the progress of hydration reaction
2. To know chemical and physical interaction of aggregates and admixtures with the hydrated cement paste and their effects on the performance of fresh and hardened concrete.
3. To know concrete durability problems
4. Expected physical and chemical changes occurring on the concrete microstructure during the progress of durability problems and precautions to be taken.
5. Manufacture of special concretes and their properties.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Discuss the concrete ingredients and its influence at gaining strength.

CO2: Design of concrete mix and grade as per IS codes.

CO3: Summarize the concepts of conventional concrete and its differences with other concretes like no fines, light weight etc.

CO4: Describe the application and use of fiber reinforced concrete.

CO5: Design and develop the self-compacting and high performance concrete.

MODULE 1

Importance of Bogue's compounds, Structure of a Hydrated Cement Paste, Volume of hydrated product, porosity of paste and concrete, transition Zone, Elastic Modulus, factors affecting strength and elasticity of concrete, Rheology of concrete in terms of Bingham's parameter.

CHEMICAL ADMIXTURES- Mechanism of chemical admixture, Plasticizers and super Plasticizers and their effect on concrete property in fresh and hardened state, retarder, accelerator, Air-entraining admixtures, new generation superplasticizer. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 2

MINERAL ADMIXTURE- Fly ash, Silica fume, GCBS, and their effect on concrete property in fresh state and hardened state.

MIX DESIGN - Factors affecting mix design, design of concrete mix by BIS method using IS10262 and current American (ACI)/ British (BS) methods. Provisions in revised IS10262-2004.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 3

DURABILITY OF CONCRETE - Introduction, Permeability of concrete, chemical attack, acid attack, efflorescence, Corrosion in concrete. Thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, specific

heat. Alkali Aggregate Reaction, IS456-2000 requirement for durability.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 4

RMC concrete - manufacture, transporting, placing, precautions, Methods of concreting- Pumping, under water concreting, shotcrete, High volume fly ash concrete, Self-compacting concrete concept and tests.

Fiber reinforced concrete - Fibers types and properties, Ferro cement - materials, techniques of manufacture, properties and application.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE5

Light weight concrete-materials properties and types. Typical light weight concrete mix High density concrete and high performance concrete-materials, properties and applications.

Test on Hardened concrete- Compression, tension and flexure tests. NDT tests concepts-Rebound hammer, pulse velocity methods.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guide lines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Properties of Concrete- Neville, A.M. - ELBS Edition, Longman Ltd., London
2. Concrete Technology- M.S. Shetty
3. Concrete Technology- A.R. Santhakumar,-Oxford UniversityPress.
4. Concrete- P.K. Mehta, P J M Monteiro, - Prentice Hall, New Jersey (Special Student Edition by Indian Concrete Institute Chennai)
5. ACI Code for Mix Design and IS 10262-2004.

REFERENCE BOOKS

1. Concrete Mix Design- N. Krishna Raju - Sehgal Publishers
2. Concrete Manual- Gambhir M.L.- DhanpatRai& Sons, New Delhi
3. Advanced Concrete Technology Processes- John Newman, BanSengChoo, - London.
4. Advanced Concrete Technology Constituent materials- John Newman, Ban SengChoo- London
5. Non-Destructive Test and Evaluation of Materials- J. Prasad, C GK Nair, McGraw Hill.

VIII Semester B.Tech
ADVANCED FOUNDATION DESIGN

Sub Code : 19SCV739
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the aspects of shallow foundation
2. To know the different types shallow foundations and well foundations
3. To learn the importance of single file and group pile foundations and testing
4. To learn the foundation treatment for structure in expansive soil
5. To learn the criteria for the design of Machine Foundations

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Understanding the aspects of shallow foundation
CO2: Knowledge of different types shallow foundations and well foundations
CO3: To understand the concept of design of pile foundations.
CO4: Understand the concept of foundation on expansive soils
CO5: Understand the design concepts of Machine foundations

MODULE 1

BEARING CAPACITY & SETTLEMENT: Presumptive bearing capacity according to BIS, Factors affecting bearing capacity, Factors influencing selection of depth of foundation, types of shallow foundations, Settlement of Shallow Foundations: Immediate, consolidation & differential settlements, Factors influencing settlement, Safe Bearing Capacity and Allowable Bearing Pressure.

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 2

SHALLOW FOUNDATIONS: Principles of Design of foundation, Definition for Shallow and Deep foundation, Requirements for geotechnical and structural aspects of design, Proportioning of isolated footing, combined footing, Strap footing, Strip footing and Raft foundation.

WELL FOUNDATIONS: Historical Development, Different shapes and characteristics of wells, Components of well foundation. Forces acting on well foundation. Sinking of wells. Causes and remedies for tilts and shifts

10 Hours

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 3

PILE FOUNDATIONS – SINGLE PILE: Historical Development, Necessity of pile foundations, Classification, Load bearing capacity of single pile by Static formula, Dynamic formula, Pile load test and Penetration tests, Laterally Loaded Pile.

PILE FOUNDATIONS – GROUP EFFECT: Pile groups, group action of piles in sand and clay, group efficiency of piles, settlement of piles, negative skin friction, Under reamed piles. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 4

FOUNDATIONS ON EXPANSIVE SOILS: Definition, Identification, Mineral Structure, Index properties of expansive soils, Swell potential and Swell pressure, Free swell, Tests on expansive soils, foundation treatment for structures in expansive soil, CNS layer. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

MODULE 5

MACHINE FOUNDATIONS: Basic definitions in vibration, free and forced vibrations, determination of natural frequency, types of Machine foundations, general criteria for design of machine foundation., vibration analysis of a machine foundation, degrees of freedom of a block foundation, vibration isolation and control. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology: Power Point Presentation, chalk and talk video demonstration, site visits.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Soil Mechanics & Foundation Engineering - V.N.S. Murthy - Pub: Sai Tech.
2. Foundation Engineering - Braja M. Das – Cengage Learning.
3. Soil Mechanics Foundations - Dr. B.C. Punmia - Pub :Laxmi publications, pvt. Ltd.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Foundation Analysis and Design - Bowles J.E. (1996) - 5th Ed, McGraw Hill Pub. Co., New York.
 2. Advanced Foundation Engineering - V.N.S. Murthy - Pub :Sai Tech.
 3. Pile Foundation.- Chellies
 4. Geotechnical Engineering.- P. Purushotham Raj
 5. Geotechnical Engineering - Dr. C. Venkataramaiah - Pub : New age Publications.
- Foundation Engineering - Dr. P.C. Varghese - Pub : Prentice

VII Semester B.Tech
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sub Code : 19SCV741

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits 4

IA Marks 50

Exam Hours 2

Exam Marks : 50

Total Hours 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. Understand some basic concepts of research and its methodologies
2. Identify appropriate research topics
3. Select and define appropriate research problem and parameters
4. Prepare a project proposal (to undertake a project)
5. Organize and conduct research (advanced project) in an appropriate manner

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Develop understanding on various kinds of research, objectives of doing research, research process, research designs and sampling.

CO2: Have basic knowledge on qualitative research techniques.

CO3: Have adequate knowledge on measurement & scaling techniques as well as the quantitative data analysis.

CO4: Have basic awareness of data analysis and hypothesis testing procedures.

CO5: Compare and contrast quantitative and qualitative research paradigms, and explain the use of each in research.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Research Meaning of research, types of research, process of research, Sources of research problem, Criteria / Characteristics of a good research problem, Errors in selecting a research problem, Scope and objectives of research problem, formulation of research hypotheses, Search for causation, Developing a Research Proposal, Format of research proposal, Individual research proposal, Institutional research proposal, Significance, objectives, methodology, Funding for the proposal, Different funding agencies, Framework for the planning.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, journal paper discussion, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE2

Literature Survey

Definition of literature and literature survey, Need of literature survey, Sources of literature, Elements and objectives of literature survey, Styles of literature survey, Strategies of literature survey.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, journal paper discussion, case study.

10Hours

MODULE3

Data Collection, Measuring, Sampling and Scaling

Classification of data, benefits and drawbacks of data, Evaluation of data, Qualitative methods of data collection, Methods of qualitative research, Sampling, sample size, sampling strategy, attitude measurement and scaling, types of measurements, criteria of good measurements, classification of scales.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, journal paper discussion, case study.

10Hours**MODULE4****Data Analysis Techniques**

Testing of hypothesis - concepts and testing, Analysis of variance techniques, introduction to non-parametric tests, Validity and reliability, Approaches to qualitative and quantitative data analysis, Correlation and regression analysis, Introduction to factor analysis.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, journal paper discussion, case study.

10 Hours**MODULE5****Report Writing**

Need of effective documentation, importance of report writing, types of reports, report structure, report formulation, Plagiarism, Research briefing, Presentation styles, Impact of presentation, Elements of effective presentation, Writing of research paper, Presenting and publishing paper, Patent procedure.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Report discussion, case study.

10 Hours**Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:**

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:**PARTA:**Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)**PART B:**

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Research Methodology: concepts and cases, Deepak Chawla and NeenaSondhi, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
2. Research Methods for Business, Sekaran Uma and RogureBoudie, Wiley, India.
3. Research Methodology: Methods and Trends, by Dr. C. R. Kothari, New Age International Publishers.
4. Research Methods in Education, Louis Cohen, Manion, Morrison, Routledge (Taylor &Francis Group) / Cambridge University Press India Pvt. Ltd.
5. Research Methodology: An Introduction, Wayne Goddard and Stuart Melville.
6. Research Methodology: A Step by Step Guide for Beginners, by Ranjit Kumar.
7. Research in Education, John Best and James Kahn, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.

VII Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Sub Code : 19SCV742

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits : 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To ensure that Environmental considerations are addressed properly and incorporated into decision making process.
2. To avoid, minimize or balance the adverse significant bio-physical, social and other relevant effects of developmental projects.
3. To protect the productivity and capacity of natural system and ecological processes with maintain their function.
4. To promote development that is sustainable and optimizes resources use and management opportunities.
5. Interpret options for evaluating environmental and social impacts

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: To encourage students to develop their own perspectives on impact assessment and to be able to relate this to other subject areas and to their wider understanding.

CO2: To identify and explore impact assessment fields and approaches.

CO3: To provide students with the knowledge and professional skills necessary to enable them to undertake environmental impact assessment.

CO4: To know importance of decision making

CO5: To know the importance of artificial infrastructure development

MODULE 1

Development Activity and Ecological Factors EIA, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA, EIS, FONSI. Need for EIA Studies, Baseline Information, Step-by-step procedures for conducting EIA, Limitations of EIA.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE2

Frame work of Impact Assessment. Development Projects-Environmental Setting, Objectives and Scope, Contents of EIA, Methodologies, Techniques of EIA.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE3

Assessment and Prediction of Impacts on Attributes Air, Water, Noise, Land Ecology, Soil, Cultural and Socio-economic Environment. EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA.

EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Public Participation in Environmental Decision making. Practical Considerations in preparing Environmental Impact Assessment and Statements. Salient Features of the Project Activity-Environmental Parameter Activity Relationships- Matrices.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

EIA for Water resource developmental projects, Highway projects: Nuclear-Power plant projects, Mining project (Coal, Iron ore), Thermal Power Plant, Infrastructure Construction Activities.

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, case study.

10 Hours

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of **50 marks**:

PARTA:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

TEXTBOOKS/ REFERENCE BOOKS :

1. Environmental Impact Analysis-Jain R.K.-Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
2. Environment Impact Assessment - Anjaneyalu. Y.
3. Guidelines for EIA of developmental Projects Ministry of Environment and Forests, GOI.
4. Environment Impact Assessment - Larry W. Canter – Mc Graw Hill Publication.

VII Semester B.Tech
INTRODUCTION TO SMART CITY

Sub Code : 19SCV743
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the dimensions and necessity of smart cities in India
2. To study various innovative smart technologies in urban infrastructure systems
3. To study the strategies for smart urban systems
4. To understand the Policy and Governance of smart cities in India
5. To study the technologies, standards and application of IoT in smart city.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to understand the need of smart city for the Indian scenario, challenges and resources required
- CO2: Able to gain a deep understanding of the nature of disruptive innovations (smart technologies) in urban infrastructure systems
- CO3: Able to learn about state-of-the-art strategies for effectively managing the transition from legacy infrastructures to smart urban systems
- CO4: Able to study the management of the transition phase from legacy infrastructure systems to smart cities by supporting innovations while avoiding early lock-in
- CO5: Able to understand potential applications of the materials learned in this course within the context of the management of smart urban transportation systems as well as smart urban energy systems.

MODULE 1

Introduction to Smart City: Definition, Need of Smart City, Difference between Satellite Town and Smart City, Advantages of Smart City, Challenges in setting up a Smart City, Resources required for setting up a Smart City, Dimensions of smart city, Smart City - International and Indian scenario, Smart City in India. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case study, Video demonstration.

MODULE 2

Planning a Smart City: Trends in Urban Development, Urban Planning, Future of smart cities, Smart City Planning and Performance, Surveying, GIS and Geo Data required, Various dimensions of smart city – Intelligent Transportation System, Healthcare, Smart Buildings, Disaster Management, Water Supply, Solid Waste Management, Electricity, Telephone, Internet, Cyber Security, Parking Facilities, Safety features against fire. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case study, Video demonstration.

MODULE 3

Policy and Governance of Smart City: Policy for AMRUT and Smart City in India, Review of - City energy systems and Urban transportation systems, Role of City-State-Central government and various other stakeholders in the design, setting-up and management of Smart Cities, City

Governance, Source of Finance, Public-Private-People Partnerships in smart cities, Different approaches to develop strategies for smart city. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case study, Video demonstration.

MODULE 4

IoT for Smart City: Data Analysis for Smart City, Building Management System, Energy Management System, Sensors, Smart Materials, Water Metering Management, Air Pollution Monitoring, Municipal Fleet Management, Smart cure for sick building syndrome, Equity & Accessible - Technology (AR, VR, IoT, Drone).

Sustainable Development: Green energy, Green building, Solar energy, Wind energy, Green buildings in smart city, Ratings and Standards. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case study, Video demonstration.

MODULE 5

Infrastructure, Technology and Development of Smart City: Design of smart city, Phases and Stages of Project, Approval Status, Smart Cities – Global Standards and Performance Benchmarks, Practice Codes, Case studies – Analysis of Amaravati, Surabaya, Chengdu. **10 Hours**

Teaching Methodology:

Power Point Presentation, Chalk and Talk, Case study, Video demonstration.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PARTA:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08Mark x 05Question = 40 Marks)

Text / Reference Books

- 1) Transforming City Governments for Successful Smart Cities, Editor: Manuel Pedro Rodriguez-Bolivar ISBN: 978-3-319-03166-8
- 2) Beyond Smart Cities: How Cities Network, Learn & Innovate, Tim Campbell, ISBN: 978-1-84971-426-6
- 3) Building Smart Cities: Analytics, ICT and Design Thinking, Carol L. Stimmel, ISBN: 978-1-4987-0276-8
- 4) Smart Cities for a Bright Sustainable Future: A Global Perspective, Shark, Toporkoff and Levy ISBN: 978-1-4973-3945-6
- 5) Draft Concept Note on Smart City Scheme, Govt of India - Ministry of Urban Development (http://indiansmartcities.in/downloads/CONCEPT_NOTE_-_3.12.2014_REVISED_AND_LATEST_.pdf)

VII Semester B.Tech
QUANTITY SURVEYING & VALUATION

Sub Code : 19SCV75

Hrs/Week : 4

Credits 4

IA Marks: 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours: 50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To know the importance of preparing the types of estimates under different conditions
2. To know about the rate analysis and bill preparations
3. To study about the specification writing
4. To understand the valuation of land and buildings
5. To know the essentials of contract and its legal provisions

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Apply different types of estimates in different situations.

CO2: Able Carry out analysis of rates and bill preparation at different locations.

CO3: Able to demonstrate the concepts of specification writing.

CO4: Able to carry out valuation and depreciation of assets.

CO5: Able to know the legal aspects on a breach of contract.

MODULE 1

ESTIMATION: Study of various drawings with estimates, important terms, units of measurement, abstract Methods of taking out quantities and cost –center line method, long and short wall method or crossing method.

Estimating quantities of load bearing structures- Single room & 2 rooms

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Preparation of detailed and abstract estimates for the following Civil Engineering works – Buildings – RCC framed structures with flat, sloped RCC roofs with all Building components.

ESTIMATES: Manhole and septic tanks, RCC Culverts.

MEASUREMENT OF EARTHWORK FOR ROADS: Methods for computation of earthwork – cross sections – mid section formula or average end area or mean sectional area, trapezoidal & prismatic formula with and without cross slopes.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

SPECIFICATIONS: Definition of specifications, objective of writing specifications, essentials in specifications, general and detail specifications of common item of works in buildings.

RATE ANALYSIS: Definition and purpose. Working out quantities and rates for the following standard items of works – earth work in different types of soils, cement concrete of different

mixes, bricks and stone masonry, flooring, plastering, RCC works, centering and form work for different RCC items, wood and steel works for doors, windows and ventilators.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

CONTRACTS: Types of contract – essentials of contract agreement – legal aspects, penal provisions on breach of contract. Definition of the terms –Tender, earnest money deposit, security deposit, tender forms, documents and types. Acceptance of contract documents. Termination of contract, completion certificate, quality control, right of contractor, refund of deposit. Administrative approval – Technical sanction. Nominal muster roll, measurement books – procedure for recording and checking measurements –preparation of bills.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Valuation- Definitions of various terms, types of property, depreciation, sinking fund method, Freehold & Leasehold properties, obsolescence, gross income, Outgoings and net incomes, capitalized value and year’s purchase. Rental method of valuation and typical problems.

Teaching Methodology:

Chalk and talk using PPT and Demo to explain the concept.

10 Hours

Suggested Activities:

- Conducting measurement and determining the estimate of buildup structure.
Items to be included for measurement: flooring, brick work, doors and windows, chejjas, lintels, ramps, beams and slab concrete, plastering internal and external walls, etc.,
- Proposing a new design road by determining the RL’s of the ground and estimating the total earth work required for the road.

Continuous Internal Assessment (CIA) Method:

Sl. No.	Type of Assessment	Mode of Assessment	Marks
1	Mini Project / Solving Challenging Problems / Case Study/ Cost Estimation/ Report Preparation	Regular Mode of Assessment	15
2	One Open Book Written Exam at the end of the Module 4	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
3	Assignments on Advanced Topics	Regular Mode of Assessment	10
4	MCQ based Test at the end of each Module	2 Marks for each Module	10
5	Attendance	As per the Guidelines given in the Regulations	5
Total			50

Scheme of examination for end semester examination of 50 marks:

PART A:

Ten multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module. (08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Datta B.N., “Estimating and costing”, UBSPD Publishing House, New Delhi
2. B.S. Patil, “ Civil Engineering Contracts and Estimates”, Universities Press
3. M. Chakraborti; “Estimation, Costing and Specifications”, Laxmi Publications
4. P.L. Basin S. Chand, “Quantity Surveying”, New Delhi.
5. S.C. Rangwala, “Estimating & Specification”, Charotar Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., 2015.
6. MORTH Specification for Roads and Bridge Works – IRC New Delhi

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. G.S. Birde, Dhanpath Rai and sons, “Text book of Estimating & Costing” , New Delhi.
2. D.D. Kohliand R.C. Kohli S. Chand, “A text book on Estimating, Costing and Accounts”, New Delhi.
3. B. S. Patil, “Contracts and Estimates” ,University Press, 2006.
4. Kohli D.D and Kohli R.C, "Estimating and Costing", 12th Edition, S. Chand Publishers, 2014.
5. Vazirani V.N and Chandola S.P, "Estimating and costing", Khanna Publishers, 2015.
6. Duncan Cartlidge, "Quantity Surveyor's Pocket Book", Routledge Publishers, 2012.
7. PWD Data Book, CPWD Schedule of Rates (SoR). and NH SoR – Karnataka.

VII Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING & WATER QUALITY TESTING
LABORATORY

Sub Code: 19SCVL76

Hrs/Week: 1T+2L

Credits: 2

IA Marks: 50

ExamHours:3

Exam Marks:50

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. To quantify the water and wastewater pollutant
2. To measure the concentration of air pollutants
3. To analyze the characteristics of water, wastewater and ambient air
4. To study the growth of microorganism and its quantification
5. To analyze optimum dosage of coagulant

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Quantify the pollutant concentration in water, wastewater and ambient air

CO2: Recommend the degree of treatment required for the water and wastewater

CO3: Analyze the survival conditions for the microorganism and its growth rate

CO4: Determine physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water and wastewater

CO5: Determine optimum dosage of coagulant

EXPERIMENTS

1. Determination of Solids in Sewage: Total Solids, Suspended Solids, Dissolved Solids, Volatile Solids, Fixed Solids, Settleable Solids.
2. Electrical conductivity. Determination of Chlorides and Sulphates.
3. Determination of Alkalinity, Acidity and pH.
4. Determination of Calcium, Magnesium and Total Hardness.
5. Determination of Dissolved Oxygen.
6. Determination of BOD.
7. Determination of COD.
8. Determination of percentage of available chlorine in bleaching powder, Residual Chlorine and Chlorine Demand.
9. Jar Test for Optimum Dosage of Alum, Turbidity determination by Nephelometer.
10. Determination of Fluorides SPANDS Method.

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCES

1. **Manual of Water and Wastewater Analysis** – NEERI Publication.
2. **Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Waste water**(1995), American Publication – Association, Water Pollution Control Federation, American Water Works Association, Washington DC.
3. **IS Standards: 2490-1974, 3360-1974, 3307-1974.**
4. **Chemistry for Environment Engineering.** Sawyer and McCarthy.

**VII Semester B.Tech
PROJECT – PHASE 1**

Sub Code : 19SCVL77

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 2

IA Marks: 100

Exam Hours: ---

Total Marks: 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to:

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected Project orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

Instructions:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work

1. Two reviews will be conducted (excluding the zeroth review and final review). Apart from this the guides have to review the project and the project report as per the specified guidelines.
2. The students have to submit the abstract (as per the given format) and based on willingness of the guide the students are permitted for Project work.
3. The assessments will be done in the scaling of 1-5 for each component of the project done through rubrics.

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Distribution of the marks is as follows:

Phase 1: 100 marks

- Synopsis 30 marks
- Evaluation of the work 40 marks
- Report 30 marks

Phase 1 marks distribution (100 marks):

- Guide: 40%
- Internal: 30%
- Final Review: 20%
- Publication: 10% (Scopus indexed/TR indexed journal)

Phase 1 - 1st Presentation (30 marks):

Identification of Problem Domain and Detailed Analysis – 10 marks

Study of the Existing Systems and Feasibility of Project Proposal – 10 marks

Objectives and Methodology of the Proposed Work using SPEED (student platform for Engineering education development) format – 10 marks

Phase 1 - 2nd Presentation (40 marks):

Design Methodology - 10 marks

Planning of Project Work and Team Structure – 10 marks

Demonstration and Presentation – 20 marks

Phase 1 - 3rd Presentation (30 marks):

Incorporation of suggestions – 10 marks

Project Demonstration – 10 marks

Presentation – 10 marks

VII Semester B.Tech

ESEP- COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN STRUCTURAL LABORATORY

Sub Code: 19SCV78

Hrs/Week: 1T+1L

Credits : 2

IA Marks 25

Exam Hours 3

Exam Marks : 25

COURSEOBJECTIVES:

1. Basics of computer aided Design of structural elements
2. Problem analysis
3. Computer aided design of RCC components
4. Computer aided design of steel components
5. Drawing of RCC and Steel components

COURSEOUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand of computer aided Design of structural elements

CO2: Can do Problem analysis

CO3: Can do Computer aided design of RCC components

CO4: Can do Computer aided design of steel components

CO5: Can do Drawing of RCC and Steel components

EXPERIMENTS

Detailing of RCC Structures

1. Beams – Simply supported, Cantilever and Continuous.
2. Slab – One way, Two way and One-way continuous.
3. Staircase – Doglegged
4. Cantilever Retaining wall
5. Counter Fort Retaining wall
6. Circular Water Tank, Rectangular Water Tank.

Detailing of Steel Structures

1. Connections – Beam to beam, Beam to Column by Bolted and Welded Connections.
2. Built-up Columns with lacings and battens
3. Column bases and Gusseted bases with bolted and welded connections.
4. Roof Truss – Welded and Bolted
5. Beams with Bolted and Welded
6. Gantry Girder

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. N Krishna Raju, “Structural Design and Drawing of Reinforced Concrete and Steel”, University Press
2. Krishna Murthy, “Structural Design and Drawing – Concrete Structures”, CBS Publishers, New Delhi

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. SP 34: Handbook on Concrete Reinforcement and Detailing, Bureau of Indian Standards
2. IS 13920:2016, Ductile Design And Detailing Of Reinforced Concrete Structures Subjected To Seismic Forces
3. Code of Practice, Bureau of Indian Standard

**VIII Semester B.Tech
SEMINAR**

Sub Code : 19SCV81
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: ---
Total Marks : 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected Seminar topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the seminar with sound technical knowledge and communication skills.

Instructions:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Seminar. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected Seminar, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the Seminar work

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Total: 100 marks

**VIII Semester B.Tech
INTERNSHIP**

Sub Code : 19SCVL82
Hrs/ Week : 6
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: 50
Total Marks : 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their internship area / topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to

CO1: Present the work done in his/her internship on the selected topic orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit two copies of the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the presentation with sound technical knowledge and communication skills.

Instructions:

Following are the guidelines to be followed for the Internship Programme:

1. The Internship Programme duration is of Four weeks.
2. The internship can be carried out in any industry / R and D Organization / Research Institute / Educational institute of repute.
3. The institutions may also suggest the students to enroll for the Internshala platform for free internships as there is MoU with the AICTE for the beneficial of the affiliated Institutions (<https://internshala.com/>)
4. The Examination of Internship will be carried out in line with the University Project Viva-Voce examination.
5. The Department/college shall nominate staff member/s to facilitate, guide and supervise students under internship.
6. The students shall report the progress of the internship to the guide in regular intervals and seek his/her advice.
7. After the completion of Internship, students shall submit a report with completion and attendance certificates to the Head of the Department with the approval of both internal and external guides.
8. There will be 50 marks for CIE (Seminar: 25, Internship report: 25) and 50 marks for Viva - Voce conducted during SEE. The minimum requirement of CIE marks shall be 50% of the maximum marks.
9. The internal guide shall award the marks for seminar and internship report after evaluation. He/she will also be the internal examiner for Viva-Voce conducted during SEE.
10. The external guide from the industry shall be an examiner for the viva voce on Internship. Viva-

Voce on internship shall be conducted at the college and the date of Viva-Voce shall be fixed in consultation with the external Guide. The Examiners shall jointly award the Viva- Voce marks.

11. In case the external Guide expresses his inability to conduct viva voce, the Chief Superintendent of the institution shall appoint a senior faculty of the Department to conduct viva-voce along with the internal guide. The same shall be informed in writing to the concerned Chairperson, Board of Examiners (BOE).

12. The students are permitted to carry out the internship anywhere in India or abroad. The University will not provide any kind of financial assistance to any student for carrying out the Internship.

Scheme of Examination:

Total: 100 marks

VIII Semester B.Tech
PROJECT WITH APPLIED PATENT

Sub Code : 19SCVL83
Hrs/ Week : 26
Credits : 13

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours : ---
Exam Marks: 100
Total Marks : 200

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

At the end of the course the student will be able to:

1. Demonstrate a sound technical knowledge of their selected project topic.
2. Undertake problem identification, formulation and solution.
3. Design engineering solutions to complex problems utilising a systems approach.
4. Communicate with engineers and the community at large in written and oral forms.
5. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

Each student, under the guidance of a Faculty, is required to:

CO1: Present the seminar on the selected Project orally and/or through power point slides.

CO2: Answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.

CO3: Submit the typed report with a list of references.

CO4: The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

CO5: Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and attitudes of a professional engineer.

Instructions:

Students in consultation with the guide/s shall carry out literature survey/ visit industries to finalize the topic of the Project. Subsequently, the students shall collect the material required for the selected project, prepare synopsis and narrate the methodology to carry out the project work

1. Two reviews will be conducted (excluding the zeroth review and final review). Apart from this the guides have to review the project and the project report as per the specified guidelines.
2. The students have to submit the abstract (as per the given format) and based on willingness of the guide the students are permitted for Project work.
3. The assessments will be done in the scaling of 1-5 for each component of the project done through rubrics.

Scheme of Examination:

CIE marks for the project report and seminar shall be awarded (based on the quality of report and presentation skill, participation in the question and answer session by the student) by the committee constituted for the purpose by the Head of the Department. The committee shall consist of two faculty from the department with the senior most acting as the Chairman.

Distribution of the marks is as follows:

Phase 2: 100 marks (Evaluation of the work 40 + Demonstration 30 + Report 30), 8th Semester

External Exam: 100 marks

Total: 200 marks

Phase 2 marks distribution (100 marks):

Guide: 40%

Internal: 30%

Final Review: 20%

Publication: 10% (Scopus indexed/TR indexed journal)

Phase 2 - Evaluation by the Guide (50 marks), 8th Semester:

Self Motivation and Determination – 10 marks

Working within a Team – 10 marks

Regularity – 10 marks

Technical Knowledge and Awareness related to the Project – 20 marks

Phase 2 - Project Report Evaluation (50 marks), 8th Semester:

Project Report – 20 marks

Description of Concepts and Technical Details – 10 marks

Conclusion and Discussion – 10 marks

Journal Publication – 10 marks

External Project Evaluation (100 marks)